

VALKYRIES

D4.6 Harmonization opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

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1. Executive Summary

This document first presents an analysis of the required capabilities of technological solutions applied to emergency scenarios nowadays. These expected capabilities are developed based on the requirements previously identified in the VALKYRIES project, performing an analysis for each one of the five tasks composing this work package.

After that, this report presents an analysis of the gaps detected in current technological solutions applicable to emergencies, which come from three sources. The first source corresponds to the surveys shared with European first responders, previously presented in the first deliverable of this work package entitled “Landscape of emerging opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters”. The second source comes from professional experience of the members of the Consortium, while the last one is based on literature already published.

Finally, after identifying limitations of nowadays technologies in emergency sectors, this report presents a list of opportunities that emerge from these gaps. These opportunities are especially useful for subsequently identifying a roadmap for pre-standardisation, which is the purpose of the third deliverable of this work package.

This deliverable is an update of the previously submitted document D4.2 - Harmonization opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters - VA/0. The new content with respect to the last version submitted has been highlighted in yellow for easy review and identification.

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

This section first presents the methodology followed during the elaboration of this report, which is essential to help understand and recreate the findings of this document. It also presents the structure of the document, which has been agreed and shared between the second deliverable of work packages WP4, WP5 and WP6. After that, it presents the exclusion criteria followed, which highlights essential aspects to understand which data have not been considered and why. Finally, a brief explanation of the data sources used is presented.

3.1. Methodology

The project has developed a common methodology for the second deliverable of technical work packages (WP4, WP5 and WP6). It has shown the need to link deliverables so that ideas flow from the primitive state to finally become a real opportunity for project stakeholders. In this way, no idea, gap or opportunity will go unanalysed, or its feasibility assessed.

This methodology clarifies the inputs and outputs of each of the stages defined. Particularly, it is composed of three stages, based on the pre-standardisation map designed earlier in the project, presented as follows:

- State of the art, and pre-identification of gaps.
- Gap and communalities analysis, and harmonisation opportunities.
- VALKYRIES outputs.

According with this step about harmonisation and opportunities, there are many benefits of having a common working methodology for the different work packages, one of them is to be able to work not only as a unit but also as a whole.

3.1.1. Structure criteria

The common structure of these technical deliverables has been composed by these chapters:

Required capabilities

This first chapter explains the capabilities required by the user in the emergency. This chapter serves as a link between the previous deliverable “D4.1 Landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters”, the analysis of the existing state of the art, and the analysis of surveys shared with other first responders. Based on the study of these capabilities required by users for both topic and tasks of the project, different desired capabilities could differ from those currently available. This situation creates a potential gap that will be reflected in the next chapter.

Identification of Gap

This chapter is the continuation of the pre-identified gaps in the previous deliverable “D4.1 Landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters”. In particular, this section presents problems or needs of the technical topic and that

limit the actuation of first responders and the capabilities of technological solutions. Thus, this chapter has two very different parts:

- Concept development. It indicates why a situation represents a gap, what problems it causes or harmonization necessities, among other aspects.
- Summary and codification of the gaps. It contains tables that summarise the gaps previously identified to ease their review and understanding.

Harmonisation opportunities

This chapter is the output of this deliverable and the inputs for the work in the incoming months and deliverables. This section aims to determine if the previously identified gaps can be solved and, if so, how they could be solved.

As in the previous chapter, the present one has two distinct parts:

- Concept development. It presents in a detailed way the potential solutions derived from the previous gaps, the problems they cause and harmonisation necessities, among other aspects of interest.
- Summary and codification of the opportunities. It presents tables to summarise the opportunities detected.

3.1.2. ID Codification/Traceability

All the gaps and opportunities identified in the document have been assigned an identifier to have a traceability. The code is created as follows:

- The 1st part of the code identifies if it is a gap or an opportunity, indicated by a G or an OP.
- The 2nd part of the code is for the task of the project that had more relationship with the gap/opportunity.
- The 3rd part of the code is just a hyphen to divide and improve legibility.
- The 4th part of the code is for the item number. This number starts from 1 to n. Any change in the first three parts of the code starts a new coding of part 4 from 1 to n.

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
G=Gap OP=Opportunity	Task number	-	Item number (1...n)
Example			
G	4.1	-	1

Table 1 - ID codification structure for traceability.

Traceability is crucial in this type of methodology both for readability and for establishing a link between different work packages and deliverables. Additionally, gaps and opportunities must

be identified in a useful and handy way. Only following a structured nomenclature can the items be identified and referenced without investing too much effort. At later stages, this codification also allows creating relations between gaps and opportunities.

3.2. Exclusion criteria

There are harmonization needs (gaps and opportunities) that although related to emergency and use cases are not part of the technical discussion.

Governance issues are outside the scope of the project. They are part of the political discussion. The project is not intended to work on these issues and therefore they are out of scope and do not appear within this deliverable.

3.3. Information source

The information collected and analysed in the report comes from different resources such as literature reviews, document analysis, professional experience, surveys, etc. Besides, the analysis of lessons learned from previous crisis management operations were carried out to identify needs/gaps and opportunities for improving technological aspects during emergency actuations.

3.4. Experts' consultation

Finally, the partners listed as contributors in WP4 developed a questionnaire to identify the technologies used by different first responder agencies and the gaps that they identify during their use. These data come from the previous WP4 deliverable, which listed both the questions included in the shared survey, as well as the most common responses obtained from first aid organisations consulted.

4. Required capabilities

This section presents the analysis of the required capabilities identified by both the members of the consortium and survey responses from first responders, in addition to the project requirements already documented in the VALKYRIES project. This section is essential to understand the expected functioning during emergency situations and, thus, subsequently identify gaps and opportunities for harmonisation.

4.1. First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units

Unmanned vehicles are able to carry out work in an environment not suitable for human beings such as high temperature, toxic gas, radioactivity, narrow passages under water or in destroyed buildings or similar whilst they are able to operate also during day and night.

As a part of our work, we have mapped the current situation and some wishes for the future through direct contact with different actors in the SAR area:

- We have asked all User case leaders in VALKYRIE about their expectations, needs and wishes. This is summarized in Table 2 below. Based on their answers we proposed several solutions. We will also make some following up questions to the UC leaders.
- We have carried out in depth interviews with first responder primarily in Norway and results from this will be given later in this document. A survey/questionnaire has been out in Norway for some weeks and a summary of this will be included in this report. Now the survey is sent out to a number of organizations and all VALKYRIE members and hopefully we will be able to include these results in a new report.

Table 2 shows that flying drones are regarded as most relevant in nearly all UC's except UC#4. Looking at the different UC descriptions we think that several ground vehicles also will be very relevant in logistics operations, as energy sources/charging station and in communication. Based on this we have included ground vehicles in the document.

4.1.1. Assistance to build common operational picture and have as correct situation awareness as possible

To have a common operation picture, updated continuous, should be a goal for all disaster relief operations. What areas can unmanned vehicles assist with this, based on inputs from first responders organisation areas like accurate weather data, up-to-date and detailed maps on how the affected area looks like after the disaster.

Questions	UC#1 - fire	UC#2 - toxic cloud	UC#3 - earthquake	UC#4 - sea
Necessary information in disaster area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weather (Temperature, wind, humidity) - Speed and direction of wind - Temperature - Topography - Composition of the forest stand - Precise map of the terrain and the nearby villages - For EMS, casualties and their location 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Toxicity - Extent of the fire - Casualties - Weather data - Map information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. information about the given object b. information about the surroundings (mainly in wind direction) - Availability of forces and resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Images - Map information - Weather data - Toxicity - Radio activity - Casualties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weather data such as temperature, wind, visibility, precipitation and so on - Sea related data such as wave height, current, tidal information - Imaging both visual and infra read - Casualties - Radio activity - Chemical composition / Toxicity
Useful type of drone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flying drone with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. camera b. infrared camera - Satellite data for ground and air traceable items will be available for crosscheck a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flying drone with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Camera b. infrared camera c. chemical detector d. RN detector e. Connectivity support (repeater) - Satellite data for ground and air traceable items will be available for crosscheck a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flying drone with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. IR and daylight camera b. sensors for pollution and toxicity c. Geiger counter d. moisture module e. concentrated gas detection module f. concentrated dust detection module g. gas analyser - two types of drone will be used: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. DeltaQuad VTOL b. DJI Mavic Zoom, Enterprise Advanced - Satellite data for ground and air traceable items will be available for crosscheck and reference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flying drone with sensors and cameras relevant to collect data as mentioned above - Remotely controlled or autonomous Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USV) with much of the same equipment as mentioned above - Autonomous underwater vehicles (AUV) can be used to search for casualties, debris and in some cases potentially dangerous specimens - Satellite data for ground and air traceable items will be available for crosscheck a
Operating condition to consider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - temperature - smoke - topography 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - topography - media - water - air 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weather conditions - Visibility - Waves - Any spill on the sea surface

Questions	UC#1 - fire	UC#2 - toxic cloud	UC#3 - earthquake	UC#4 - sea
Alternatives to the existing network failure	- Command and Control trucks - Cell phone network using the satellite network	- Here, communication connection is expected running well (radio-tetrapol and 4G)	- Mobile Deployable Broadband Cellular System (developed by BDI)	- Mobil phone/5G is normally not suitable - Possible solutions are Maritime broadband Radio (MBR), VHF and Satellite phone. Saltwater affects most units
Expected function from unmanned vehicles	- Small autonomous ground vehicles for mapping the disaster area	- Decontaminable	No	- Both AUV and USV are suitable equipment for some application where a flying drone fail
Limitation	No	- Interconnection, Education/training, Certification, Acquisition	- Considering about education and certification procedures	

Table 2 - Analysis of requirements of flying drones.

4.1.2. Preferences from first responders on types of communication in disaster area

The survey conducted with first responders had the question “How will you prefer to receive critical personal safety information during crisis?”

As Figure 1 shows, the majority prefer the alarm with sound or combined with vibration. The need for visual information is low. This must be taken into consideration when using unmanned vehicles in disaster management, implying the need for gathering, sorting and interpretation of information before the first responders is updated. The focus on “the right information, in the right amount on the right time” is important.

Figure 1 - Analysis of how first responders prefer to receive critical personal safety information during a crisis.

4.1.3. Standard and protocols

To reduce the need for first responders to acquire several different UAV / UGV, the autonomous systems should be flexible when it comes to attach different sensor packages. The idea is to standardize the connections and the data protocols to make it possible for the first responders to acquire sensors from different manufacturers regardless of type of drone.

4.1.4. Trade-offs between complexity of the system and easiness to use

As the technology develops the wants for the unmanned vehicles to conduct different tasks simultaneously increases. It is a trend, with manufacturers, to increase the complexity in the unmanned systems to answer the needs from the customers. This complexity will increase the threshold for personnel to become familiar with the autonomous units and may reduce its use. It is important to balance the usefulness with the complexity especially with volunteer first responders since they have a limited time to train and by that very limited time to familiarize with new equipment.

4.2. Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals

4.2.1. Introduction

Disaster communications encompass the communication needs of all phases of disaster management, namely prior to a disaster for the dissemination of early warning reporting, and during disaster response for search, rescue and relief. At times, it may also cover the recovery and reconstruction stages. Emergency communications involve a host of technologies, including terrestrial communications networks (land line as well as wireless systems), sirens, public address systems and satellite-based communication networks. It is a critical component of the overall disaster communication systems. It deals with the response stage of a disaster, especially for a major destructive disaster, when all other means of communications, particularly terrestrial-based communication networks no longer function, are disrupted or destroyed.

This section aims to promote emerging technology opportunities focused on creating a reliable communications infrastructure for first responders. The main gaps, challenges, and regulatory barriers to their adoption are reviewed, fulfilling the requirements in the VALKYRIES project framework. This technical analysis is to improve current procedures and technologies, evolving to more sophisticated and adaptable ones for multiple casualty emergencies. Network technologies must provide good coverage for those areas that are more complex to access and, therefore, to deploy a robust infrastructure. They should be adaptable to the most current technologies in use, trying not to vary the behaviour of the first responders so far.

Without ruling out the use of general access commercial mobile communication networks with wide coverage and a certain level of security and availability, in emergency situations and especially in more complex situations where damage or congestion of such commercial networks may occur, the potential benefits of having a specific highly available and secure network become more evident. The availability of national, and even transnational, networks serving all security and emergency forces could help optimise efforts and ensure full interoperability between the different services involved in emergency response.

Adaptability and convergence in emergency environments are one of the VALKYRIES' objectives. To achieve this, communication technologies must be selected according to the requirements of the environment, as long as a minimum of security in transmissions is guaranteed. This is a first approximation of the current requirements for an interoperability upgrade.

Data security and privacy purposes play a fundamental role at VALKYRIES. That is why a considerable effort has been put into identifying opportunities and authorization policy status in transmission confidentiality and communication availability throughout the platform infrastructure. Finally, standards and protocols for sharing, collaborating, and transmitting information from multiple parties have been identified.

According to the previous remarks, in any emergency situation a large amount of information is generated with the purpose to be successfully used for emergency cases. This information must be accessible to all authorised stakeholders with a common language and ensure that everyone understands the same information in the same way; it must also be accessible by all

necessary/required channels, both online and offline. Similarly, each emergency has unique characteristics, therefore, the people in charge of communications must have the necessary experience and skills for efficient performance.

All data that will be used must be properly handled and be secured in a right way so that the end-users will have specific information to make use depending on the emergency and the parties involved.

The authorised personnel assigned to these communication tasks must meet proper training and experience requirements that are always equivalent and recognized among border countries in order to optimize reaction and response capacity. That is why there is a need to have standards in the definition of policies, profiles, hierarchical equivalencies in all the different structures and uniform training in both theoretical skills and similar experiences.

4.2.2. Network coverage

Network coverage is a key resource in the events addressed by VALKYRIES. The coverage (ground area coverage) of the wireless network communication, which are the most used in the operational theatre, is limited by the technologies used (see Figure 2), the terrain morphology, the presence of obstacles, and the physical topology of the networks.

For the current analysis, Radio Frequency (RF) directional communication antennas are not considered because most of the operational scenarios occur in open field and all direction needs to be covered, except in the case of communication from offshore to inshore, where the communication direction can be of relevance.

Figure 2 - RF Networks coverage range.

Satellite communication is a particular type of technology that provides “global” coverage depending on the satellite antenna beam direction. The downside is the limited data rate, limited scalability and much higher cost. Where wireless (ground) networks like 4G are unavailable (e.g., sea waters), satellite communication might be the only possible option.

While some communication technologies are point to point (e.g., LoRa) - where their range depends on the emission power and antenna configuration - other solutions rely on a network infrastructure composed by multiple cell towers (e.g., 4G and 5G) or access points (e.g., Wi-Fi).

As such, communications technologies can be used in combination to obtain better performance, robustness and resilience: Wi-Fi technologies (e.g., 802.11a, 802.11b, 802.11n) might be a good high throughput choice to support a locally deployed group, however, if nodes become too distant (i.e., out of network reach) they can switch to 4G network (or satellite), thus extending the communication range.

A possible way to overcome some of the networks limitations is to combine the different networks in a commonly managed model by using GATEWAYS that can bridge data between networks, thus improving the overall solution resilience. Current USE CASES are supported on some of the communication coverage as displayed above. Potential gaps refer to the use of the digital device to device communications (Bluetooth, RFID, Lora).

As explained before, the operational theatre’s communication coverage depends on the type of communications that is used:

- The coverage of infrastructure-less (point-to-point) communications technologies is highly dependent on e.g., line-of-sight conditions, emission power, antenna configuration, presence of obstacles and terrain.
- The coverage of infrastructure-based communications technologies is highly dependent on the design, topology, and number of available infrastructure nodes (e.g., antennas and base station). See Figure 3 for more information.

Figure 3 - BTS Networks topology (1)

Operations conducted in areas supported by well-connected cell towers often deliver fast networks with global access (e.g., the Internet). However, it is important to consider the following constraints:

- Cell towers deployment can be scarce in low-population areas and even absent in remote areas (like mountains).
- Since the use of cellular networks is shared with citizens, in case of major incidents, cell access might be congested due to excessive demand (e.g., a large number of citizens trying to initiate calls)

The above constraints demand that authorities operating critical services (like medical emergency) rely on dedicated communications technologies, like TETRA (1) (or other dedicated communications networks) ensuring availability even in extreme circumstances. However, these dedicated technologies do not support high data rates, thus blocking the transition to the digitalization of security services.

A possible approach to overcome a limited number (or absence) of cell towers in each area consists in deploying mobile cell stations nodes mounted in Land or Aerial vehicles. In this case, ground mobile nodes connect to vehicles that in turn connect to the communications infrastructure.

Figure 4 - Increase area coverage with drone's relay (3).

Additionally, infrastructure-less communications, like Direct Mode Operation (DMO) and ad hoc networks, can be used to connect nearby nodes to each other. Herein, emerging mesh protocols, like 802.11s and Wi-Fi Direct (2), present interesting opportunities for challenging scenarios. For example, ad hoc networks can be especially useful to connect nodes in underground tunnels, where there is no network infrastructure and satellite communications are not an option. In case one or more nodes are also connected to a cell station, they can operate as a relay station providing “network infrastructure” access to the whole ad hoc network (see Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Extended connection range by using drone relay (5).

4.2.2.1. Terrestrial areas with normal-high connectivity

Areas with a high connectivity are typically found near urban areas, where traditional networks are strongly implemented. It usually provides good backbone communication and access points. In this scenario, all communications are well explored, and the challenge is to manage all the different communication channels and information overflow. Good filtering capability may be required to attain a good operational performance.

4.2.2.2. Areas with no communication coverage or difficult access

The extension of areas coverage can be achieved by means of relays radio, satellite connection or BTS networks mobile stations deployed. The deployment can either be done via Land, maritime or Air. However, these temporary extensions of coverage may have limited data rates.

There are other communications solutions, such as TETRA, which is designed to operate under such condition, and are deployed via a mobile station, thus providing coverage.

In the worst-case scenario, one way broadcasting communication channels can be used utilizing the Vertical Blank Interval (VBI) zone of TV frequencies, typically used for teletext services, as an emergency channel to distribute commands or directions to mobile C2s deployed. Such communication channels usually are not affected by the disasters.

4.2.3. Integration with existing communication technologies

As identified in the use cases, different communication technologies can be used and deployed in the theatre of operations, as have been presented in the previous chapter. Exploiting and combining existing and available technologies in the field can deliver a highly performing and/or robust network in a variety of challenging situations. As explained in D4.1, it can also provide “a wider connectivity, therefore, establishing bridges between the different networks will provide new actors access to the SIGRUN data, and enable higher level of interactions, resilience, and adaptability to different scenarios”. Especially important as well is to be able to integrate with technologies in use by security entities, while promoting at the same time digital innovation.

Security organisations over Europe operate on dedicated professional communications networks – like TETRA – that provide reliable voice services but offer very limited (if any) data support. Likely, their migration to data enabled services will rely on commercial networks like 4G and 5G operating on top of widely used Internet-based protocols like IP, which represents a strong potential enabler for communications integration between the different entities involved in the USE CASES events. Moreover, as explained in the previous chapter, satellite communications can represent the only viable option in extreme situations, like remote (non-populated) areas and in maritime environment.

As also proposed before, a GATEWAY can provide the function that support the multiple networks integration. Integrating heterogeneous communications technologies is challenging considering their different underlying characteristics, as presented in D4.1 (3) and herein reproduced in the Table 3.

Characteristics	Technologies					
	TETRA	Ad-hoc	Wi-Fi	2G 3G 4G	5G	Satellite Comms.
Congestion control	No	Partial	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Quality of Service	No	Partial	Partial	Yes	Yes	Partial
Mobility	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes	Yes	Partial
Interoperability and heterogeneity	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
Security and privacy	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Robustness and flexibility	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes	No
Data transfer rate	None/Low (for deployed networks)	Low	Medium High	Low Medium High	Very High	Medium

Table 3 - Characteristics of communication technologies.

For example, trying to directly integrate high data throughput networks (like 4G and 5G) with low throughput networks (like TETRA and Satellite) will create packets congestion and delivery failure. Moreover, it is easier to integrate networks supporting IP (e.g., Wi-Fi and 5G) than those that do not (e.g., TETRA).

In VALKYRIES, it was introduced the concept of an interoperable Gateway, see D2.8 (4), capable to connect different networks by handling low-level protocol conversion and delivering an all-over-IP network for VALKYRIES services. The VALKYRIES Gateway performs the following main functions:

In VALKYRIES, it was introduced the concept of an interoperable Gateway, see D2.8 (4), capable to connect different networks by handling low-level protocol conversion and delivering an all-over-IP network for VALKYRIES services. The VALKYRIES Gateway performs the following main functions:

- Interfaces with non-IP-based networks to operate in an IP Layer.
- Bridges and transfers data between different networks.

The following subsections detail the functions provided by the gateways in integrating the VALKYRIES infrastructure to ensure integration with existing network technologies. In this sense, the handling of networks with different data ratios, the prioritization of the data to be

transmitted, and the handling of heterogeneous protocols between different networks are identified.

4.2.3.1. Handling Networks with different Data Rates

Networks and communication devices offer different data rates and transfer data at different rates. For most cases, transaction data and control data consist of small data packets and are time asynchronous. However, streaming data and mission operation data tend to require bigger amounts of data and are time sensitive.

Therefore, connector modules (e.g., VALKYRIES gateway) will have to manage the different network speeds, especially in cases where data produced in broadband (high speed) networks needs to be transferred to narrowband (low speed) networks.

To handle this, techniques based on data queuing and prioritisation have been proposed for the VALKYRIES gateway. Moreover, additional services can be used as a backup structure in order to overcome package loss. Blockchain, as a decentralised database, can be used to store mission valuable data that can be shared with any authorised and interested party. Depending on the blockchain network, the transfer of data can be instant or performed in a matter of seconds even in low-bandwidth networks.

4.2.3.2. Handling Data Prioritisation between networks

Another situation that is linked to the previous topic, is related to the priority of the data being transferred. When application data is transferred within the same network, the principles of FIFO are used or, when QoS or SLA protocols reserves a specific data rate, degree of prioritization can be established.

When transferring data to a low data rate network or to another network that has already SLA and QoS assignments, it may result in less capacity to take in additional data. Therefore, the connecting elements between the networks are also required to select which data is critical from those that are not. This setting depends on 1) the nature of the data (e.g., synchronous or asynchronous); 2) the data time validity (e.g., data refers to an already closed incident, a reported victim location becomes less reliable as the time elapses); 3) operational data relevance (e.g., relevance to the decision maker, operational relevance, QoS).

The VALKYRIES gateway connector module implements data queuing and prioritisation privileging, when needed, critical data over non-critical data. Regardless, it is noted that by making use of blockchain networks, all high priority data becomes available to authorized parties, provided the network characteristics allow it.

4.2.3.3. Handling Heterogeneous Protocols between different networks

Not all networks or communication devices and artefacts support the same protocols. Therefore, it is needed to support data exchange between different networks using with different protocols, which involves protocol translation tools. This feature especially important when integrating with legacy systems that rely on custom or obsolete protocols.

In VALKYRIES, all data exchange occurs over IP, the most used protocol worldwide that connects the World Wide Web. Non-IP networks will require a gateway that provides the IP layer access point to non-IP devices.

A second level of harmonization is the contents of the data to be transferred and the referential data concerning taxonomy, dictionary, or units used. E.g.: two applications use different coordinates systems to report an actor position. If each application does not have the same referential it will generate wrong understanding of the data shared. So, a common referential is required and the services that allow the automatic conversion of the data. In addition, all services that will be deployed need to communicate with other in order to provide 'feedback' from one to another so that the right taxonomy or dictionary to be altered before is stored into databases.

The VALKYRIES gateway is the artifact that interconnects heterogeneous networks, handling all required protocol and data translation aspects.

4.2.4. Optimal network technology selection

In order to select the optimal network technology there is the need to define key factors, such as the platform requirements, security issues, mobile devices, among others. Depending on the requirements, obstacles such as speed, latency and performance issues must be taken into consideration and a new strategy should be established for new solutions to be valuable and comprehend with the data and the network adaptability. Moreover, security issues have to be exploit, how to prevent data leakage, ongoing daily basis monitoring, specific regulations that will be needed for the purposes of the platform and all according to the compliance with all the data networks.

Also, existing technology will always need for new integration, measures and a replacement method must be defined in order to be flexible by remaining into the same standards without the need of diversion. Each technology has its pros and cons but the selection criteria must be based on the needs of the platform. So, for the decision making must be take based on a concentrated table of contents that will best describe the regulations that will be followed, which users will use the network and in what way. Moreover, the integration of this technology must be adaptive to our needs and system specifications.

4.2.5. Communication availability

The deployment of wireless communications systems is typically among the first priorities when responding to any disaster-related emergency situation. However, terrestrial wireless equipment, such as cellular telephones or land mobile radios is only useful when communications towers and other fixed equipment are in place to connect it to the local and global communications backbone. Having the capability of rapidly establishing emergency terrestrial-based infrastructure is important for all countries, even for those with well-developed infrastructure, since that, it can be destroyed by disasters too. Examples of such situations include Hurricane Katrina in 2005, in the United States of America, and the Wenchuan earthquake in May 2008 in China. Emergency terrestrial-based infrastructure has also been used

in areas which did not have very well-developed infrastructure prior to the disaster, such as in the areas affected by Cyclone Nargis in Myanmar in 2008.

The success in mass-casualty emergency strongly depends on the availability of communication technologies. If communication gets disrupted, both inter and intra agency coordination gets affected, preventing an effective communication. Based on that, these critical scenarios the European Union must guarantee that communication systems are fault tolerant, and that there are several communication protocols to be used for different use cases that can be used interchangeably if needed.

4.2.6. Information confidentiality

For the information that will be stored and shared through the platform must be regulated in a proper way to which certain users can have access to specific datasets or information. Blockchain can make easier the distribution of data in a unique way into which data can be retrieved and who can view them. Blockchain can store data using encrypted methods so that the access level is only limited to those who have the proper credentials to access them . At any given time, data is available with no need of further authorization besides the private key. Also, the need for policy regulation(policy makers) is necessary in order to facilitate a better mapping of users to data so that access can be limited to those needed Due to the capabilities that blockchain provided at given moment who can retrieve actions that occurred making use of a distributed ledger. Through the ledger who can have access to the actions that occurred with the blockchain, so no data are visible to the outside world. Therefore, all data are encrypted, stored and replicated though the blocks of blockchain, in this case there is no risk for data loss.

In order for each time to interact with the blockchain (retrieve data) the need of the private key which was used to store the data is needed. One authorised personnel will have access to the key and thus they are the one responsible to interact with blockchain.

4.2.7. Deployment of redundant systems

To enable a SIGRUN solution that enables resilience, system availability, robustness, high service level, and operational performance, redundancy of the used system is a mitigation strategy to overcome any potential loss, degradation or unavailability of the system capabilities. The level of redundancy to set-up and the number of redundancy systems depends on the number of provided critical components and on the size of the deployed Forces. As established in D2.8 (4), clusters of services can be used to increase performance and reliability, as well as redundancy, as enumerated next:

1. Redundancy in data (e.g., data transferred and stored in multiple cluster nodes, redundant backups, blockchain).
2. Redundancy in communications (e.g., multiple and/or different networks deployed in field provides communication alternatives in case of localised failures and can extend communications range)
3. Redundancy in servers and services (e.g., cluster-based deployments in hardware and software components in “master-slave” mode).

Furthermore, operational redundancy may require additional capacity of assets, equipment, personnel, etc, to face potential scale-up of the event and mitigate potential operational bottlenecks. In this regard, “horizontal” scalability of services and resources (e.g., video stream servers, data analytics services) can be used to increase overall capacity of the SIGRUN solution dynamically and efficiently.

Due to the critical operational timing related with emergency response, redundancy in SIGRUN aims to deliver a smooth and efficient operational response, even in extreme circumstances.

4.2.8. Standards and protocols

Emergencies and natural disasters have the characteristic that they are not predictable, at least with enough time to plan and manage a response from their knowledge, so prevention, education and training in these scenarios is of crucial importance for the maximum success of interventions when they are needed. When they happen at a border, they acquire additional factors that increase complexity and pose a greater challenge in achieving success.

All countries around the world have faced these challenges and prepared different responses. In the face of these events, VALKYRIES takes special importance in coordinating the optimal response and resources. In order to respond to this need, different reference standards are collected to be used in a context of cooperation between interested and related parties in VALKYRIES for the different use cases.

ISO/TR 22351:2015 Emergency management – Message structure for exchange of information.

- The information generated in a context of high tension and emotion such as disasters and emergencies can cause it to not be communicated with a sufficient level of quality. This can result in the absence of critical information, use of unsuitable channels, delay in the delivery of information, among others. It is considered important to have a standard to structure the information in a uniform way for all those involved, reducing risks and optimizing the exchange of information between current systems and new information systems.
- The information can be dispatched automatically using a totally automated way. Current systems can be evolved using new methods and structure, to facilitate upcoming communication networks. Automation is needed for direct communication with first responders and minimize the channels that will be used for the transmission of data.

ISO 22396/2020 Community resilience – Guidelines for information exchange between organizations

- The exchange of information is carried out at multiple hierarchical levels and between different entities, they can be internal and external, so the information exchange agreements must be carefully analysed. There must be an information exchange methodology with all the necessary level of detail to overcome the challenges arising from a drop in service level due to the appearance of a crisis or disastrous event.

- There can be a mapping of hierarchical levels and define which levels must first be informed about any type of event to reduce the time response.
- Moreover, what data about the event will be shared, what are the minimum data of exchange for the first responders to comprehend with the crisis situation.
- It is considered necessary to remember that the standards must be developed up to the operational level through protocols, instructions and/or SOPs, having been deployed in a timely and appropriate manner among all interested parties and, as a good practice, under a quality standard such as ISO 9001.
- All data must follow along the regulations for data sharing and compliance that must be forced to the system. Also, all data must be mapped properly following GDPR compliance since we are taking into consideration personal data management.

ISO13606 - Health data sharing data and Protocol: In case of health data is required to be exchanged health services, a possible data structure to follow is established by the ISO13606 :2008 standard.

ISO 13606-1:2008 - Specifies the communication of part or all of the electronic health record (EHR) between EHR systems and a centralized EHR data repository or can be used between EHR entities that require access to health data, provided that the access credential as valid.

ISO 13606-1:2008 - Can be used to support the direct care given to victims, or to support population monitoring systems for population health surveillance or can support the exchange of disasters/Emergency victims' health data to allow for a better medical response, provided that the privacy is protected and that the proper authorizations are in order. In 2019 the standard was updated to the standard reference ISO 13606:2019.

Furthermore, the Joint Opinion on the Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space recently released by the EDPS and EDPB, supporting individuals to take control of their own health data and the use of health data for better healthcare delivery, better research, innovation and policy making shall introduce specific safeguards to offer a safe and secure exchange, use and reuse of health data. They will become state of the art once the Proposal will be enacted.

MQTT - Message Queuing Telemetry Transport

- MQTT is a standard messaging protocol used for the Internet of Things (IoT), managed by OASIS (5). MQTT is designed as a lightweight publish/subscribe messaging transport allowing connectivity with remote devices and other data sources, integrating them in an easy and distributed way using minimal network bandwidth.
- MQTT servers can be setup as standalone or in a cluster configuration (supporting redundancy and “horizontal” scaling). In this way, the protocol is reliable and highly scalable.

EIDO - Emergency Incident Data Object

- The NENA Standard for Emergency Incident Data Object (EIDO) is an ANSI Accredited Standard (NENA-STA-021.1a-2021) that defines a structure mapping Functional Elements related with emergency services. It includes the definition of emergency “incidents” including status, location, dispatching agencies and involved resources.
- EIDO is a standardized, industry-neutral format for exchanging emergency Incident information between disparate manufacturer’s systems located within one or more public safety agencies, and with other Incident stakeholders (6).

4.3. Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies

4.3.1. Introduction

This section will emphasise the possibilities to promote emerging technological opportunities for first responders in terms of Command and Control. Preliminary analysis of certification, regulation, standardisation, and harmonization opportunities of technologies are part of the related work stream for the VALKYRIES. Enhance existing cross-border technological procedures and fit avant-garde technologies.

The C2 suite shall be simple, practical, and operational at all levels. Some requirements are principles to get mission success by decision superiority. Reach out towards extremely complex hybrid MCI (Multi Casualty Incident) to achieve capacity of coalition cooperation. Develop and provide robust C2, which can be easily integrated with the user systems and platforms for achieving unmatched efficiency.

Standardising existing working environments with collaborative tools is one of the aims of VALKYRIES. To achieve this, the set of information shall be shared with other cross-border agencies regardless of their origin is a first approximation of the ongoing requirements for an interoperability upgrade.

Emergency services have largely sectorised tools. Such digital barriers to data access are critical in order to increase the harmonization and the information flow exchange for the relief of the injured. The FRs (First Responders) have categorized the most optimal data to share between countries as follows.

4.3.2. Dangerous Zones

The identification of dangerous zones is essential for coordinating any emergency. Particularly, the use of GIS environments is handy while analysing the most dangerous areas over a map, offering free access by coordinators to a repository where the documents are available in real time. Thus, the coordinators present at the ICP can visualise which are going to be the most critical areas.

In addition, the integration of C2 (Command and Control) applications with other data sources, such as drones and satellites images. They would make it easier to identify the cartographic

points where the major damage can be seen in the field. In this sense, Figure 6 presents a graphical representation of a point located over a map.

Figure 6 - Example of a location representation over a map (9).

In this context, the use of GIS (Geographical Information Systems) systems for identifying dangerous zones attend to the following functions and consequences:

Functions

- Plan for the protection of the first responder.
- Balanced deployment of cross-border resources.
- Analyse the state of the area.
- Possible difficulties for emergency vehicles.
- Increment of SA (Situational Awareness) by FR.
- Anticipate potential disasters.
- Use a limited number of entry points that can be guarded (7).
- Establish a safety perimeter to guarantee the division between triage zones.

Consequences

- Fast deployment of emergency resources.
- Provide real security for first responders.
- Free of delays during the actions of emergency teams.

In multiple-casualty incidents, efficiency and speed is necessary for logistics. For that, the use of these tools is essential for coordinating emergency actuations.

4.3.3. Number of victims

Introduction

The cooperation network between countries and organisations aims to create joint action protocols to improve emergency responses in major disasters. Coordinated management of shared casualty counts will allow for more agile organisation of the deployment of health

resources closest to the victims regardless of the country or territory to which they belong. Real-time casualty counts are the most critical data for EMS deployment.

Managing the victims during the emergency/disaster and fast development events is a complex activity and depends on the characteristics of each event, specific treatments required and safety measures to set-in place. It includes the different phases, from the emergency response to victims, their transportation, and the medical facility of destination, when required. CBRNE (Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear, and Explosives) events may require specific containments measures for the victims through these phases or dedicated medical facilities may be required to assist a victim with specific medical condition or treatment.

Managing the number of victims starts in the triage and identification of the victims and follows through the entire event crisis, requiring traceability of the victims' records, (including location information), compiling dashboard of the victims and response status, and the sharing and gathering of the victim's data. As first stage triage usually starts after handling the victim to a EMS dedicated person in the secured area, some critical information might be lost. For this, the alternative or parallel use of TAP2SOS system (provided by BL2050) logging data natively in blockchain, can reduce such handling risk.

In cross border events data shared between countries may be subjected to some level of authorization, registry and traceability, and control. In such cases, a pre-established agreement may simplify the process, and its integration in the data management process should be considered.

Functions

- Rank the disaster according to the number of victims (including their triage status).
- Generate victims' dashboards according to the medical service and status.
- Assign victims to the medical response according to the services and medical response availability.
- Provide victims health data in advance and ETA (estimated time of arrival) to the receiving medical centres / Hospitals.
- Cross border victims' data validation schema.
- Improve future disasters' response. Populate data to deploy lessons learnt increasing effectiveness.

In case of TAP2SOS:

- Assign a NFC unique number to a victim by anyone that has access to the APP
- Collect medical or non medical data, depending on the privileges of the first responder
- Link pictures of the victim (as found) or other pictures from the scene related
- Log the data with a time stamp and GPS location (provided by first responder's smartphone or tablet) in a blockchain file accessible by other systems
- Create the victims list

Consequences

- Reduce the number of victims waiting for medical assistance.
- Provide better care to casualties.
- More assistance with few resources.
- More efficient and effective medical response when victims arrive.
- Improve victims' data sharing between countries in cross border events.
- Improve future responses by incorporating lessons learned.

4.3.4. FR Information

Introduction

C2 Apps shall be able to collect data from the FR. Wearable devices are the equipment responsible for monitoring the vital signs of FRs, among many other functionalities. The exploitation of this data is essential to improve decision-making by the coordinators of the organisations involved in the MCI.

The wearable devices also enable the follow-up of the FR in field position, better optimization of the FR distribution to assist victims and to minimize the FR risks in case of potential hazardous or dangerous situations to FR. In particular, the position and time of the last known position in case of connection lost with the FR.

Another relevant data is the location of FR resources, such as FR Vehicles, ambulances, etc, its capabilities and availability. This information is critical for a fast and guided response according to the victim situational needs.

Functions

- Data gateway between FRs' wearables devices and the C2 app.
- Monitor and alert ICP coordinators to high stress level of FRs.
- Improve FR shift change times.
- FR distribution and location in the operational theatre.
- Determine last FR know position.
- Awareness of assets capabilities and location.
- Provide ambulances location to the medical service.

Consequences

- Closer incident follow-up.
- Decision-making support for Coordinators.
- Cross-border aid for FRs.
- Reduce risks faced by FR in the operations theatre.
- Know FR assets location to better manage the response and reduce number of FR victims.
- Post event assessment capability to generate new lessons to learn.

4.3.5. CBRNE

Introduction

Pick the right roadmap for the rescue and subsequent management of the injured in an expeditious and safe manner, together with the threat elimination and next related actions. CBRNE incident requires additional specific procedures and equipment. Especially in a dangerous zone. That is why the crucial task is to detect the threat, identify its source, predict its spreading, specify the safe and dangerous zones. In one word to have common operation picture (COP) as much detailed and as quickly as possible. Of course, in an effective way for different types of responders and positions. At the same time, standard operational procedures (SOPs) need to be available for particular case. Ideally, they should be harmonized between the responding units and also exercised in advance. Terrain monitoring, it is essential to deploy the correct equipment so that the Incident Command Post (ICP) whole information to be ready to deploy both material and human resources. This point pretends to analyse the full spectrum of CBRN threats in an operational context and provide advice and support to the whole Emergency Services (8). Using of autonomous systems is one of possible opportunities to mitigate personnel risks coming to unknown conditions.

Functions

- Relevant security physical measures need to be identified.
- Detect and identify the sources of the danger
- Determine the affected area and predict the development in the next few hours (days)
- Present (display) these data in effective manner to responsible persons on different positions
- Enable / improve communication and data exchange
- Improve critical infrastructure capabilities such as increased air flow traffic, access to intakes and outlets, etc. (9)

Consequences

- Progress on: (10)
 - Screening.
 - Sampling.
 - Monitoring.
 - Decontamination.
 - Clearance.
 - Waste management.

4.3.6. Relevant locations

Introduction

During an emergency situation, it is essential to identify and keep track of the locations that are relevant for the actuation. First, these actions help optimising time, which is a key aspect in

these adverse scenarios. Moreover, they ease the actuations of first responders during rescue tasks and threat fighting, and subsequent management of injured victims. Finally, it indirectly benefits patients also since they will receive an early and more adequate treatment.

However, incidents sometimes occur in areas that are not well known by first responders. In these situations, the ICP shall arrange as much information as possible aiming to be ready to deploy both material and human resources.

Functions

- Securing critical facilities to mitigate the disaster consequences, such as plants with chemical waste, or schools, among others. As an example, Figure 7 presents a list of strategic areas in which critical infrastructures are commonly present.

Figure 7 - Most common critical infrastructures sector (11).

Consequences

- Comprehensive protection of society such as minority groups.
- Avoid exposure of the catastrophe origin on expansion sources.
- Facilitate evacuation routes.

4.3.7. Standards

Command and Control technologies are one of the most efficient tools in modern day disaster management and in first response to emergencies. These technologies make the adoption of a common operational picture and situational awareness between agencies feasible. Common operational picture and situational awareness are two aspects which, although are the focal point of many research activities and technological developments, are still lacking to a significant extent.

The means for first responders to reach a common picture during an emergency, and especially in multi casualty incidents that require rapid deployment of resources and effective coordination

and support, are command and control technologies. These technologies span from robust communications in harsh and hostile environments, to secure data sharing systems, unmanned vehicles, geolocation and GIS technologies, triage systems, propagation models (e.g., for fire spread), real or near-real time acquisition of satellite images or sensor data and early warning systems for the timely mapping of risk evolution and alerting of endangered people.

In addition to the technological domain, common operational picture can be achieved also through an effective collaboration between first responders' organisations. To this end, it is crucial for agencies involved in first response, to be aligned, to the highest degree possible, in operational procedures and to adopt a common approach in their operations. Thus, interoperability, either procedural or technical, is the way to achieve situational awareness.

Standardisation is a very efficient tool for the homogenisation and harmonisation of operational procedures, as well as for the effective communication between technological systems. Although many standards exist, targeting not only at data sharing, interfaces, and other communications-related aspects, but also at procedures related to emergency management and inter-organisational collaboration, there is still quite a lot of research needed to reach an operative state of situational awareness. Many standards are developed by the several different technical committees of Standardisation Bodies both at an EU and international level. Indicative technical committees for the development of command-and-control related standards are listed in Table 4.

Standardisation Body	Technical Committee
ISO (12)	TC 292 Security and resilience
	TC 21 Equipment for fire protection and fire fighting
	TC 176 Quality systems
IEC (13)	TC 65 Industrial-process measurement, control, and automation
ISO/IEC (12) (13)	JTC 1 Information technology
IEEE (14)	C/CPSC Cybersecurity and Privacy Standards Committee
	C/LM LAN/MAN Standards Committee
	C/S2ESC Software and Systems Engineering Standards Committee
ITU-T (15)	SG11: Signalling requirements, protocols, test specifications and combating counterfeit products
	SG17: Security
	SG16: Multimedia
	SG 2: Operational Aspects
CEN (16)	SG20: Internet of things (IoT) and smart cities and communities (SC&C)
	TC 122 Ergonomics
	TC 224 Machine-readable cards, related device interfaces and operations

Standardisation Body	Technical Committee
	TC 391 Societal and citizen security
CEN/CLC (16)	JTC 13 Cybersecurity and data protection
ETSI (17)	TC Cyber (Cybersecurity)
	TC EMTEL (Emergency Telecommunications)
	TC EMC (electromagnetic compatibility) and radio spectrum matters (ERM)

Table 4 - Technical committees for the development of command-and-control related standards.

The above technical committees are responsible for the development of standards, either specific i.e., technical specifications for systems and tools, or generic, for the description of methods and procedures. For command-and-control technologies it is apparent that most standards are developed by specific technical committees relevant to the electrotechnical domain. However, there also other technical committees with a broader agenda, which, in the context of developing standards relevant to disaster management, also develop standards of cognate command-and-control technologies e.g., ISO TC 292 and CEN TC 391. In addition to the aforementioned organisations, which are official EU and international standardisation bodies, there also standards developed by industrial consortia. These consortia comprise of groups of experts in specific domains, and they provide standards, mainly of a technical character, that are widely adopted by end users. Examples of such consortia are the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) (18), which develops standards related to Geographic Information Systems, and the Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS) (19), which is related to the development of cybersecurity, Internet of Things and emergency management - related standards among others.

The use of standards and procedures between different organizations entails continuous coordination for the correct use, execution, and maintenance. Document management, the continuous improvement of the associated processes should be one more piece in the gear that allows the success of the objectives of the use of management tools. The simple fact of recognizing, approving, and coordinating standards between organizations is the first step towards success, although these new standards must be incorporated into the management systems of the participating organizations and make them part of their activity. This has been a point of view already contemplated by standards such as TC 176.

4.3.8. Sources of information

For the present context it is considered only the data gathering actions (OBSERVE phase of the OODA), and does not include the data analysis, imagery analysis algorithms, IA algorithm for intel and correlation of data, etc. It focuses only on the ability to collect the raw data of the scenarios.

In this context, the number of data sources can be as many as the available sensors in the platforms and sources presented below.

4.3.8.1. External GIS files

A wide number of GIS services are available in the market and used worldwide, and each application freely selects the GIS maps service and GIS engine to use, which is dependent to the earth projection model and standard, such as the GTRF, the georeferenced system used by Galileo, or the WGS84 datum, used by GPS. Although very close in precision, VALKYRIES exchange of georeferenced data should use a common reference, which in EU should use the GTRF (Galileo Terrestrial Reference Frame). Many of the GIS providers support multiple geo reference frames.

4.3.8.2. Other External Data Services

Weather Forecast and broadcast services

Several weather forecast and broadcast services are commercially available. Modelling of the weather evolution in specific location and the ground terrain effect on the weather conditions may require additional services, in particular for large fires, CBRNE and toxic release events, where atmosphere terrain interference is critical.

Ground, sea and air data services

Detailed and accurate information related with ground or lake or sea surface temperature, humidity, burring material, moving objects, gasses etc. are available also from ARATOS Satellite System.

Satellite EO services (COPERNICUS, etc.)

Critical situational data is also available from Earth Observation technologies such as satellites (COPERNICUS/EFFIS, NASA/FIRMS) through available APIs.

Maritime Vessel data services (AIS, ELRIT, etc.)

Maritime data related to vessels, boat and ships position and route can be partially gathered from maritime services, such as AIS signals, ELRIT our other similar services. Some of these services are cooperative, which means that the vessel, Ship may need to be subjected to cross verification.

4.3.8.3. Direct Data Sources

UAV / RPAS / DRONES

These systems can provide multiple data stream and data sources of the operational theatre. Equipped with different sensors, typically cameras EO and IR, Radar, Lidar or multispectral cameras, drones provide key information to understand the situational context, develop awareness and to plan the actions. The altitude position provides key information of the ground, day and night, and is scalable to a multiple of drones flying simultaneously. Drones can also provide data from remote or difficult access areas, deepening on the communication coverage and its operational limitations (Flight level (MSL), weather limitation, radio coms LoS or BLoS, etc).

Some key element of the data collected from drones refers to 1) the data resolution matching the needs of the operations, which depends on the sensor's resolution and altitude AGL of the drones; 2) The communication capability to transmit the data may limit the capability for real-time data transmission of high-resolution sensors and multiple sensors simultaneously; 3) visual obstacles, such as clouds and smoke can severely reduce the sensor visibility and DRI (Detect, Recognition and Identification) parameters. 4) Another relevant aspect is the compression rate and algorithms (Codecs) used to optimize the data transmission from the UAV to the ground.

Although different configuration may be used, typically the data collected by drones is sent to the UAV control station and from there relayed to the Operational C2 system. As the number of drones may be used in a scenario, the number of control station increases, and the data is feed into a data distribution system that deliver to the C2 consumers. In these cases, a coordination of the flight plans and expectation of data is required, to plan the flight and the sensors area of interest coverage.

The transmission of the data from the UAV platform usually has two segments, 1) from the UAV to the control station (GCS – Ground Control Station), using a dedicated datalink. And 2) from the GCS to the C2 system, uses another transmission system.

Many manufacturers use specific proprietary protocols in segment 1, and in segment 2 some of the most traditional video transmissions protocols are the H264 / H265 protocol.

CCTV

CCTV cameras are increasingly common, especially in urban and high traffic roads, for traffic management and for security, or in forest fire monitoring grid (Portugal). These technologies also provide a valuable information for C2, although its ground position limits the visual areas and do not provide direct location (2D coordinates) of the events, but only bearing. The data is usually collected in operational centre from where a connection could be established to the C2 system. The CCTV systems located in open areas usually respond to governmental authorities and authorization are required to relay the data to external services, if available. The CCTV usually provides low resolution data, with a small coverage range and may face visual obstacles.

IOT

The IoT networks now deployed can be also a useful source of data, if available in the area of interest. Ideally, IoT data is already structured according to common standards, such as the MQTT or the W3C (Web of Things). The Integration of this data into the C2 system can be mounted over several protocols - like Bluetooth, LoRa, 3/4/5G and MQTT – that can be feed into a C2 system through a gateway.

Broadcast TV

TV channel are also a good source of data of the operational context, but the low control over generated, this data is mostly used as a complementary source. Even though TV channels are

vital in public awareness/warnings, the use of their VBI zone (Teletext) as a backup/last resort mean of communication is one more opportunity.

Mobile Phones

Mobile phones can be a valuable source of data, but we need to separate the originator of this data. One situation is the mobile phone data originated by a FR, from which the trust level is high. Another is the mobile phone data originated from someone outside the operating personnel, which is mostly covered in the social media below.

The mobile data provided by trusted personnel can be directly feed into the system, although its metadata could improve the usability of this data, namely its location, orientation, time of origin and FR ID. Without this metadata the usability of the data, is reduced.

This data can also be directly supported by the C2 system, although some management process may be required. For that purpose, the mobile can use nr of the many different communication networks available, Wi-Fi, 4G /5G.

As for trusted communications requirements using such 3 or 4 or 5G channels between FR and their C2s, available protocols and encryption mechanisms following military standards by Aratos can be used during the Case trials through apps.

Social Media

Social media is an interesting data source during emergency scenarios (20) (21). In these adverse situations, the population tends to share information, such as text, images, or videos, in social networks. These resources can be greatly valuable since they present, almost in real time, the impact and progress of the emergency. Taking advantage of this open-source data, emergency organisations all over the world are studying the inclusion of these data sources for emergency management. In addition to being useful for providing quick information from hot zones, it is also useful to understand how population is reacting against the threat. Based on that, the response can be adapted to better deal with the consequences of the adverse situation. For this, the use of big data tools is essential to manage a huge information volume.

The use of social media is still under development of its SOP, as validation and trust of the social media data required validation prior to its injection in C2 system and required to be filtered to avoid misinformation.

4.3.9. Harmonization at national and supranational levels

The EU Civil Protection Mechanism helps coordinate disaster response, preparedness and prevention activities of national authorities and contributes to the exchange of best practices. This facilitates the continuous development of higher common standards enabling teams to understand different approaches better and work interchangeably when a disaster strikes.

The aim of VALKYRIES project is work against segregation systems. Even keeping current applications interoperability systems would be focused on transversal data transmission. This

section relies on the support for real-time data exchanges identifying sectorial gaps at national and supranational levels such as:

- Gain access to external Databases.
- There is no European communication platform for consistent and versatile communication.
- Cross-border single communication by via phone.
- Non-existing technological procedures for first rescue coordination management.
- May run to different levels of command.
- Applications independency.
- Protocol Interoperability. Heterogeneous protocols.
- Unique and flexible data model.
- Enable synergies between cross-border countries.
- Community engagement.

National/supranational harmonization is a challenge that, in any area or purpose, the result of harmonization always entails a great cost for countries and companies for the consequent adaptation. It is for this reason that the expectations and guaranteed achievable results must be of high value to all parties. Harmonization must be considered at different levels, focusing only on technical aspects and user experience, some of which could be the user interface, data and information to share, the methodology for using the tool, response times and functions; but they are not the only ones, because other regulatory levels must be considered that would affect the management of public and/or private services and resources in each country, for example, the data protection law.

It is considered interesting to generate a scale of adaptation to harmonization based on the fulfilment of requirements. This fast and convenient evaluation gives access to certain functions and is recognition of the harmonization based on technological, legal and other criteria, which allows a flexible deployment to national and supranational harmonisation.

Mannaionii A, Monet Jean-Paul et al. (22) proposed in 2020 a national and international methodology to evaluate the quality of the interoperability of the services in international crisis management, inspired by pre-existing tools, and redesigned in a scoring device. This tool assesses the degree of cooperation between the various first responder organizations on several layers of preparedness and response:

- Governance and Policies: Different level of international cooperation can be considered, from national agencies working separately to specific bilateral agreement(s) for join work and missions: existence of bilateral agreement, for example cross bordered, going further than multilateral ones.
- Standardised Operational Procedures (SOPs): from harmonized national SOPs to specific bilateral or cross bordered policies, implemented at « ground » level and giving bilateral SOPs to empower multilateral ones.

- Technologies: Transfer, exchanges of communications and data are keys-factors to illustrate the quality of interoperability.
- Training and exercises: Level of proximity of two working bodies could be also illustrated by the practice of common trainings or exercises.
- Language: Differing languages within an international civil protection operation may present a significant challenge to command, control, and communications, and potentially affect unity of effort if not mitigated.
- Operations: Operations management is pointed out as the most important domain. They measure it through the sharing of Command-and-Control practices and tools: from teams working together with limited communication to sharing a same incident command system: the collaborating agencies are fully interoperable, while using the same system, chart and communication network.

4.4. The digitalization on first aid actuations

4.4.1. Real Time Support

As the digitalization of the first aid actuations aims to optimize these actuations, real time support is a required capability than enables the implementation of the digitalization during the actuations. To do so, all the devices should be able to provide information to the digital environment, as well to receive information from other devices.

The majority of businesses today have made digital transformation one of their top strategic priorities. The core of digital transformation is the automation of crucial business operations, which is made possible by real-time data. This automation drives innovation and corporate strategy. Data performance, availability, and resilience are all aspects of real-time data. Real-time data means that IT services are always active and linked, and that data access is always quick and uninterrupted.

The technologies that supply real-time data are those that revolve around workload optimization and software-defined storage. Software-defined storage technology allows a single data integration platform that enables an organisation to query and access all types of data across the network on-premises within different sources and systems, as well as the data located in the cloud, as if it were stored in a single location. It establishes a “universal access” setting without ever transferring the data physically. No matter where the needed data is physically housed, business users and apps may instantly access it thanks to this frictionless access. Additionally, it allows the unification of endpoint management and streamlines application management.

These ultimately lead to faster query replies for analytics and business intelligence with enhanced understanding from data, allowing users to gain more agility to adapt to changing circumstances, something that can be of core-importance in a multi-casualty incident.

4.4.2. AI integration

Artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the most disruptive approaches used nowadays in a wide variety of scenarios. Using this approach, significantly more data can be processed by machines than by people. AI and, particularly, ML, are able to analyse data but also look for trends and uncover new information. Since emergency contact centres are frequently inundated with calls, these tools could aid in the analysis of calls and messages, which would ultimately shorten wait times and result in more lives being saved. They are also capable of objectively analysing a situation and as was already mentioned, are always looking for ways to get better.

There are several external influences that can affect a decision when handling an emergency. In a circumstance where survival is at stake, physiological pressure, environmental factors, or even emotions can cloud our judgement and impair our ability to act rationally. This dictates that organizations involved in public safety must be receptive to this new technology, which needs to be supported by a strong ethical framework and adhere to privacy laws.

The use of AI in emergency response must be carefully considered. If used properly, AI has enormous potential; thus, it is important to give ethics, fairness, and compliance with privacy laws priority.

Although AI is not a cure-all, it can be a great help to emergency services employees by boosting and complementing their work. The technology is already in use in other societal spheres and is rapidly moving toward dominating the field of public safety. If emergency services do not utilise these tools, opportunities can be wasted, which would result in lives being lost.

Additionally, the integration of emergency actuations with AI will provide intelligence that will enable capabilities to ease the decision making during the actuations, such as route optimization, evacuation priorities or calling for reinforcement to improve. This is especially beneficial in environments where there is intrinsic difficulties for coordination, both within and between agencies, in which it is difficult to have a common operational picture to make decisions according to existing data.

Moreover, this integration should involve multiple devices, such as wearables and command and control modules. In essence, there is a need for a common platform able to integrate data from multiple agencies and sources, offering a holistic view of the situation and offering recommendations to first responders. Since AI is useful in these environments, it is crucial that final decisions are taken by humans since AI is not mature enough to consider all possible aspects and outcomes from real life.

4.4.3. DTA Standards

Governments, organisations, local authorities, and individuals ought to be ready for disastrous events, both natural and man-made, which are an inevitable part of humanity's daily life. With the growth and expansion of human population, the harm and effects of natural and man-made disasters are growing more catastrophic. The pre- and post-disaster scenarios may not be appropriately anticipated. The use of DT poses a quite reliable answer to this challenge. By gathering data from various heterogeneous sensors, and storing it on cloud infrastructure, a

virtual replica of the affected area may be created. With the constant stream of data from the sensors, this virtual replica can be kept up-to-date and accurate.

AI/ML supported DT solutions for designed for disaster management systems, can greatly assist decision-making processes. Simulations in the virtual replica can lead to the optimization of decision-making and action-taking, both in speed and effectiveness. Even seconds after a disaster are crucial for preserving lives, and DT can provide solid support to solve such problems.

The implementation on DTA's should follow available standards in order to communicate multiple instances and to allow many-to-many information sharing that would allow to provide the same information to different instances.

4.4.4. Iconographic standards

To share the information between multiple organizations and nations, the use of standards will ease the sharing and comprehension during the first aid and emergency actuations.

4.4.5. Literacy levels

Digital literacy is the ability to locate, analyse, organise, understand and evaluate information using digital technology and apply the acquired knowledge to address or solve a problem. Digital competence in healthcare involves the use of ICT to achieve goals related to optimal patient care and improved quality of care.

Montero J.A. et al. (23) identify several key competences needed by healthcare professionals in the current digital scenario:

- Digital health literacy: knowledge of the digital ecosystem and obtaining the basic ability to use appropriately and safely the different digital devices and applications for healthcare purposes.
- Effective management of scientific-health information: ability to manage scientific information and knowledge in an effective way to make decisions based on scientific evidence and to improve patients' healthcare.
- Health communication 2.0: use of digital technologies, devices, and channels in an appropriate way to improve networking and non-face-to-face communication between health agents.
- Creation of scientific-health digital content: use of ICTs to facilitate and enhance scientific research and publication 2.0, as well as the design and production of digital health content.
- Collaborative networking with health teams: use of digital tools and resources that facilitate the development of interdisciplinary projects and non-face-to-face healthcare in collaboration with different healthcare agents, including patients.
- Data analysis and management: knowledge of the different sources of health data and how to process them to extract knowledge and results in real time to facilitate clinical decision-making.

Some barriers to effective digitalization in healthcare have been identified, including the organizational structures themselves, the interests of the stakeholders involved and the need for healthcare professionals themselves to develop the necessary skills to incorporate ICTs into clinical practice and patient care.

Emergency Medical Services face digitalization as a basis for optimizing patient care processes with maximum safety, coordination, and efficiency. Central to this strategy are the development of digital services, interoperability and the analysis of data and information.

To properly implement the digitalization, it is crucial to rely on proper literacy levels that would allow to optimize the results within the new-fangled capabilities. In order to ensure an effective digital transformation of the healthcare system, it is necessary to incorporate a training plan into the digitization strategy to ensure that healthcare professionals, decision-makers and managers have the appropriate digital skills. If the first responders' literacy levels cannot face the digitalization, it would be needed to make efforts to solve these requirements.

4.4.6. Common Operational Picture (COP)

One of the main pillars of the digitalisation is the information sharing. This is of the utmost importance since data federation through digitalisation is the main way to allow an effective communication flow between organisations participating in an emergency situation.

The gathering of this information enables to create a Common Operational Picture shared between nations and organizations to provide a common environment to share the information during the emergency actuations. Furthermore, having a homogenised view of the emergency is crucial for avoiding loss of information, for performing agreed decisions between intervening entities and to know the actuations performed by other entities that can affect the actuations during emergencies. Additionally, this is essential for the entities responsible for coordination, where the command and control post need to unify the information coming from different sources.

4.4.7. Educational purposes

With the advancement of the techniques developed to help first responders in this type of situation, the need has arisen to design a simple and fast learning method for them. For this, new technologies have emerged such as the use of virtual reality, or through gamification. These techniques are based on the principle that better training results are obtained when users are having fun or are more involved in the scenario. For this, scores, teamwork, and leader boards are used to assess the knowledge of each of the students.

However, this is not enough, so the trainees must be able to handle this type of technology, thus improving the efficiency of the training. In the same way, it improves the speed of use that can be obtained in a real use case.

The capabilities provided by the digitalization enable to create new and specialized ways to educate, train and prepare the first responders. The digitalization of these procedures also enables to analyse the results to improve them.

4.4.8. Supranational Harmonization

As the digitalization of first aid actuations aims to ease the coordination during cross-border incidents, it is necessary to follow international standards to enable efficient communications between different nations.

4.5. Instrumentation and health support wearable devices

4.5.1. Personal Tracking

Logistics tracking refers to the methods and systems used to track resources throughout their movement and storage. With logistics tracking, the physical location of a product, material or other resource is known at any point in time, and sometimes even where it is intended to be next.

In the response to an MCI or disaster, resource tracking is the process that all incident personnel and staff from associated organizations use to maintain information regarding the location and status of resources ordered for, deployed to, or assigned to an incident.

Applied to first responders, personal tracking is the ability to locate at any time where each of the first responders involved in the MCI is located.

In relation to the victims of an MCI or a disaster, tracking is the ability to identify and follow (upstream and downstream) the course of a victim through the chain of care, and to know his key information concerning his condition, evolution, and healthcare process.

It is necessary to track the location of each of the actors in an emergency situation, both for the patients affected and for the emergency personnel acting in the area. In this way, the available resources can be managed in a more appropriate way, knowing which triage or evacuation phase each patient is in, or how many first responders are attending each of the phases. In this way, a global vision of the distribution of resources can be obtained, facilitating their reallocation.

Adequate traceability in disaster response offers important advantages to:

- First responders: it facilitates the accurate management of individualized information on each victim (for location, for assistance, assignment of destination centres, evacuation, etc.), as well as an adequate distribution of logistical resources.
- Victims: it avoids duplication of processes, favours continuity of care, etc.
- Victims' families: it allows a complete list of victims by name or type to be quickly compiled and provides precise information on the location and status of a victim at any point in the chain of care.
- Destination hospitals: they can know in advance precisely which patients will be arriving and their main characteristics (age, predominant pathology, etc.).
- Investigation and planning: they allow for analysis of the response, once the crisis has passed, facilitating improvement actions.

However, there are some problems that need to be considered. Some of these issues are that these systems must work regardless of the coverage that exists or the adverse effects that may affect the devices.

4.5.2. Personal Identification

To make tracking possible in MCI, it is necessary:

- A proper identification of the elements to be tracked:
 - Vehicles: emergency service vehicles, in addition to the identification and signalling elements determined by the applicable law in each case, are generally assigned a specific identification code by the agency to which they belong. In many cases, there is also a geographical positioning and fleet tracking system using GPS. Additional identification details may include the crew's identity, cargo or payload, other equipment etc. Most of this information, if not all, may be coded for privacy and security reasons.
 - First responders: personnel belonging to the emergency services are usually also assigned a specific identification code, which can be at the individual or team level.
 - Victims: each patient must be assigned an individual identification code and, must be labelled in such a way that this identification is visible to all, along with the essential information that must accompany it. The current way of labelling victims of an MCI are triage cards, which have a unique and unrepeatable alphanumeric code that identifies the victim and allows the use of colour coding to visualize the severity of the victim at any given time. Traceability may also help reunite victims with their families after severe MCIs.
 - User access identification: Personnel using the SIGRUN system, are also required to have an identification at system level, and an application role that is mapped in to the SIGRUN role. These credentials are used to record the used of the federated system.
 - An adequate recording of information.
 - An adequate storage of information.
 - All relevant information should be stored in highly secure databases with redundancy features incorporated.
 - Critical information that are required to remain unaltered can be stored in a blockchain environment. Blockchain can ensure that information therein will remain untampered, providing also a timestamp for each stored record. As a result, in cases where a piece of information must be retrieved, the person who addresses the query is sure that the retrieved information is absolutely valid, trustworthy and it can be safely used for any purpose.
 - A solution that allows for the relevant information sharing.
 - Due to the fact that a blockchain environment is centralized, it is more than often used to create collaborative environments. Moreover, its redundant design offers a robust solution for information sharing, participants may store
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and retrieve information based on the permissions they have on the collaborative network. Since a blockchain environment is centralized, it is more than often used to create collaborative environments. Moreover, its redundant design offers a robust solution for information sharing and so, participants may store and retrieve information based on the permissions they have on the collaborative network.

It is necessary to identify each of the users participating in an indicator in order to, on the one hand, associate certain information to a certain user, as in the case of associating medical information to a certain patient. On the other hand, it is necessary to identify the first responders as it allows the assignment of responsibilities or information consultation. Thus, the identifiers must be unique, and must function independently of the coverage.

4.5.3. First Responders' Communications

In many realities, there is still no single mode of communication even between different agencies in the same country. To this must be added the problems related to the operation of communications networks in MCI (network saturation, shutdown for public safety reasons) and those related to cross-border operations.

A solution that allows you to communicate easily, in a hands-free way through wearables (wearables, smartwatches, helmets, glasses) using a dedicated network could bypass the above problems.

4.5.4. Patient vital signs monitoring

With the development of wearable and portable technologies - easy to deploy and supported in communication networks such as Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, 4G/5G - remotely monitoring victims' health status become available to emergency response organisations. A patient's vital signs information can provide valuable up-to-date information concerning her/his wellbeing, which can be used to update their triage status.

Relevant vital signs to collect are:

- Heart rate.
- Body Temperature.
- Blood Pressure.
- Blood Oxygenation levels.
- Abrupt movements.

To reduce the burden on responders, it is important that this data is automatically collected using medical IoT devices, portable equipment or other similar artifacts. These devices can connect to a network directly or may require a connection device (e.g., gateway, Access Point or smartphone) and send data to receiving medical services.

The transmitted data should not identify the victim. A unique code is assigned to the victim, allowing to protect her/his privacy.

4.5.5. Victims' triage support in disasters

To triage victims in disaster, it is necessary to obtain information about them: heart rate, blood oxygen level, etc. Wearables can be a source of information and can help first responders take decisions.

Since the beginning of the 21st century, work has been carried out on systems to locate and monitor certain constants of disaster victims, in order to facilitate the continuous assessment of their clinical condition, their categorisation, their follow-up and the information to the destination hospitals.

In recent years, advances in e-triage systems have accompanied developments in information and communication technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), using low-power electronic sensors to determine the vital signs of patients or even developing solutions based on machine learning.

However, more advanced, or sophisticated wearables may prove to be cost-inefficient. In addition, first responder agencies may find themselves poorly prepared in terms of quantity official devices in order to address all victims in an MCI, due to the unpredictability of the incident variables. Although sophisticated wearables can offer unique advantages during an MCI (e.g., vital signs monitoring), incidents with potentially thousands of affected people maybe better faced if low-cost solutions that can be purchased in much larger quantities are utilized. For example, hypoallergenic silicone wristbands that contain an NFC or RFID chip can be used for quicker triage. Color-coded wristbands can quickly show the victims' severity of health status and facilitate the work of first responders as well as treatment in the hospital, once they reach it. In addition, triage personnel may store small pieces of critical information about its victim's condition. Those critical information may vary from incident to incident but in any case, they can puddle of outmost importance for the quick treatment of the victim saving valuable time towards saving lives.

Of course, both solutions may be used simultaneously. The NFC/RFID-equipped silicon wristbands being used for quick identification of a victim and sophisticated wearables being attached only on victims with higher severity of health status.

The triage process during an MCI is mainly performed "manually" by triage staff and communicated to the Advanced Health Post/C2 by phone/radio. Providing digital tools to support this triage process, such as triage applications capable of communicating with the Advanced Health Post/C2 automatically, will not only streamline the notification process and the availability of information, but could also help triage staff by advising and harmonising the process, especially in cross-border incidents where different countries are involved.

4.5.6. First Responders Protection during crisis response

First responders must be in good health to carry out their work. Vital signs, such as stress or fatigue, should be monitored to ensure their health during crisis response. By using wearables, information such as stress levels or continuous working hours could be obtained in real time.

Security-related information at a worksite (HAZMAT, security threats or simply NO-GO zones) must be detected by an operator, in a discontinuous manner, sometimes through a hand-held equipment, transmitted to C2, and then disseminated to all FRs with local network boundaries. This creates a circuit with multiple parties involved, exposing the system to the risk of not being timely or inaccurate in reporting.

Incorporating sensors for hazardous substances into wearables would allow for continuous monitoring of this risk and, potentially, immediate, and automatic transmission of this information to C2. Similarly, “panic buttons” that, without the need for voice communications, could transmit a call for help by correlating it with the exact location of the FR would trigger an immediate response.

Finally, the possibility of geolocating the boundaries of NO-GO zones and transmitting the information, together with the image captured by the FR that is conducting the assessment, to C2 would be interesting. This information, essential for the safety of FRs, may be disseminated by C2 via short text or audio messages or pictures sent to rescuers’ wearables.

4.5.7. Disaster Fatality Identification

Deceased victim identification is an essential operation that, sadly, almost always accompanies the final operations of an MCI rescue. DVI procedures differ between countries and sometimes even between different parts of the same country. This happens because the laws governing them are different and often the agencies in charge are also not the same (forensic police, forensic medicine, joint task forces).

This task has important legal significance and, because of the particular type of setting. It involves the technical component (victim location, alteration of environment, mode of recovery), the police component (presumptive identification, analysis of personal effects), and the medical component (external examination of corpse and declaration of death). Not knowing DVI-related procedures can lead FRs during rescue operations to irreparably damage evidence essential to the identification of a deceased victim.

The ability to freeze the scene of the finding before modifying it, for example by acquiring the coordinates of the site via smartwatch and by capturing images of the scene and face of the deceased via wearables and transmitting them remotely would be an undoubted advantage for presumptive identification of the victim.

Another interesting idea is to be able to capture the unique code of an implantable wearable (e.g., devices that monitor the blood glucose level of diabetic patients) and correlate it with certainty to a victim.

4.5.8. Telemedicine in disasters

Telemedicine refers to the capability to use technology to deliver medical care and support at a distance. It can include providing medical instructions and advice to citizens and responders from specialists that are far from the emergency. Support can be provided using audio, video and/or chat (based on user preference, but also **service capacity**). For example, in the absence

of responders, a bystander citizen could initiate a video call with a remote expert that, using the provided video, could deliver adequate first-aid instructions, like: how to perform cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR); how to use an automated external defibrillator (AED) machine; how to stop the bleed of a seriously injured victim (24).

Telemedicine used in MCI disasters events may profit from the new smartphones' capabilities to:

- Help initial diagnostic (collect victims' data with Image, video or other data). The data is sent to remote experts to assist in the diagnostics.
- Guide the procedures to apply: Provides voice and image guidance to the "citizen responder" about the procedures to perform.
- Follow-up of the victims' status and establishing alerts to be monitored by the "citizen responder".

4.5.9. First responders training

At the technological level, FR training and education programmes should have educational software to simulate the management of multi-casualty incidents and disasters. The development of this software should allow for the registration of FRs on the specified platform and guarantee access to the training materials of the different courses and trainings.

On the other hand, to standardise reporting and debriefing after MCI and disaster management, a system could be implemented to standardise data collection, so that all institutions could share the lessons learned and improve their emergency response.

5. Identification of gaps

This section presents the analysis of technological gaps identified during the work performed by this work package. This information comes from the literature, from professional experience or from first responders answering the provided survey.

5.1. First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units

Based on the information from the surveys shown in section 4.1.2, the following gaps are identified. These gaps do not take the dataflow into consideration even though this is important for the success of the use of the systems. This will be elaborated on later.

A very recent publication by Sanz-Martos S et al. (25) address a systematic review of Drone Applications for Emergency and Urgent Care, with the aims to identify the available evidence on the use of drones in emergency health care compared to traditional health care.

Its results showed that drones covered a significantly larger area than other traditional tracking methods and were very useful for performing preliminary triage, determining needs, and knowing the scene prior to the arrival of rescuers. In addition, drones reduced the time required to locate the victim.

As negative aspect of drones, assessing all their functionalities, they pointed out some limitations regarding their use in health care. For example, they cannot carry much weight, they are challenging to use in adverse weather conditions, and their initial investment is significant, although their cost is low compared to existing standard methods such as manned aerial vehicles-helicopters (G4.1-1, G4.1-2, G4.1-3). Additionally, legislation is needed to make their use safe, regulated, and controlled. Finally, all these gaps are summarised in Table 5.

5.1.1. Building a common operation picture

G4.1-1: Accurate and live weather data.

For all disaster relief operation the weather will always be an important factor. At sea strong wind will make waves making rescue of people and vessels more demanding, heavy rain will influence search and rescue operations in the mountains and fighting fires especially with toxic smoke must know the temperature, wind direction and humidity in order to find the optimal approach. Adding unmanned vehicles to the operations will give both challenges and opportunities. A drone is very sensitive to wind and have a maximum wind speed before it is grounded. But the same drone may deploy weather sensor and/or be equipped with it. This will give all first responders live and accurate weather and with the right tools, a detailed local weather forecast. The data and information must be available as open source to everybody involved in the disaster relief.

G4.1-2: Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure.

All large-scale disasters like earthquakes, floodings or fires will change the terrain, degrade, and often destroy infrastructure and change the natural flow of rivers. Roads may be damaged, power lines broken and the terrain itself changed due to avalanches. This results in a change in

all pre-planned responses and the first responders must make new plans for disaster relief. To make these plans as effective as possible the planners must have up-to-date maps or photos of the area affected, traditionally have satellites and aircrafts given this information. This information may not be detailed enough due to dense clouds of smoke or very demanding topography.

If the first responder teams have access to drones, they can scan the area based on their own needs and can get an accurate picture of the situation for their tasks: if it is firefighting, evacuation, or logistical support

5.1.2. Aspects regarding personnel safety

G4.1-3: Tracking of personnel, casualties and equipment.

During a disaster relief operation it is many persons involved, from different departments like Fire fighters, ambulance personnel and red cross volunteers. This makes it very difficult for on-scene-coordinator (OSC) to keep track of everybody involved and heighten risk for misunderstandings regarding search planning leaving some areas unsearched. By using a tag system with a secure login, the OSC can track all involved physical presence, and build an accurate map of searched areas and future planned search areas. The tags will also give an extra safety measure for the participants since they can be warned of possible heighten risk, like flash flooding, or imminent new avalanche due to their actual positions, a recommended escape route can be suggested to the involved personnel. If any persons are injured, they can be found and given necessary assistance without unnecessary delays. A tracking system can also be used to identify casualties reducing time for assistance to reach them.

G4.1-4: Safe work environment for first responders.

Before personnel can start work in a disaster area, it is of paramount importance to know what kind of environment they will meet. Especially with fires, but also after earthquakes containers with hazardous material may be leaking or burning. The type of toxicity will decide what kind of personnel protection the first responders need. Use of drones and rovers equipped with sensors can, without harm, close in on the area affected and measure what kind of substances that are present.

5.1.3. Logistic assistance to disaster areas

G4-1-5: Building ad hoc communication grids.

In a modern disaster relief operation the dependency of communication and transfer of data (videos, plans, maps etc) is very high. This means it is vital to have a working communication grid. Under large and devastating disasters, the infrastructure will have reduced capacity even possible destroyed. Even if the communication grid is working, the system will be overloaded by all the victims, next-of-kins and other family and friends trying to get in contact with each other.

G4-1-6: Delivering equipment.

A large disaster operation will need a lot of equipment, provision, and fuel to be able to function over time. To move this from its storage areas and to the first responders are in normal situations challenging, but in a disaster area with damaged infrastructure it may easily become a nightmare. The use of transportation drones and rovers may help in this. By using large rovers to move necessary equipment from the pre-planned storage area to the forward operation bases, they can replace trucks and by that reduce the need of drivers, and remove the need for rest.

From the FOB and to the first responders in the field. It may be possible to use quadcopters. They can bypass any congestions and destroyed infrastructure and deliver small parcels of vital equipment to the area first responders' work.

G4.1-7: Supply energy and charging capabilities.

The future of disaster relief will rely even more on electronic devices than today. We have moved away from pen and paper and to tablets, mobile phones, or PC to log or to get information. All these gadgets will, together with UVs starting to be implemented, will increase the need of electric power. With power grids damaged or destroyed in the disaster area, the first responders have traditionally relied on diesel generator. By using UVs equipped with solar cells or other non-emission power systems. The first responders can charge their equipment from the UVs parked in close vicinity to the operation area. Also, UAV can automatically use the same platforms to charge.

G4.1-8: Conduct Search and relief missions.

In all disaster relief operations, the primary task is to find and assist people missing, injured, or trapped. This is time consuming and will demand a high number of people to conduct the search. By using UAV equipped with the right type of sensors (thermal camera, for instance) and using AI can detect personnel on the ground, contact them and connect them with the first responders. They can also have small emergency kits available for the persons herself or for other in the vicinity to stop bleeding or to keep warm until the first responders can arrive.

Identification of Gaps			
First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.1-1	Accurate and live weather data	Open-source data	Weather information is important in all SAR operations. Temperature, precipitation, wind speed and direction are common for all cases. Other data such as humidity, barometric data, wave height and so is important in some cases.
G4.1-2	Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure	Map information as well as pictures	In a large-scale disaster situation like earthquakes, floodings or fires, the terrain affected will change. Roads may have disappeared, or rivers have new courses. To give as effective disaster relief as possible, it is

Identification of Gaps			
First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			essential for the first responders to have an updated and accurate map. This has traditionally been done with aircrafts and satellites. If the first responder teams have access to drones, they can scan the area based on their own needs and can get an accurate picture of the situation for their tasks: if it is firefighting, evacuation, or logistical support.
G4.1-3	Tracking of personnel, casualties, and equipment	Position	A common problem in all disaster area operations is tracking of personnel. By using a blockchain based tag system on emergency response personnel and vehicles the command centre can have live updated information of where they are physically. This information has several possible benefits, such as area monitoring for better understanding of what areas have been searched (historic track data), to provide assistance to personnel in congested areas or inside buildings in order to find quickest and/or safest way to injured people for medical aid and evacuation or to get them to safe areas if the situation deteriorate.
G4.1-4	Safe work environment for first responders	Information on toxicity, radioactivity and similar challenges	In all disaster relief operations, especially in urban areas, the present of hazardous or toxic material is highly possible. To protect the personnel involved with the right protective gear and to decide the best approach to the task, it is vital to know what type of substances may be present or what the smoke from the fire contains the present of toxicity or hazardous gases or material.
G4.1-5	Build ad hoc communication grids	Physical units are placed out in the disaster area to re-establish communication	In large disasters the probability that the existing communication grids may be destroyed or overloaded. To make a temporary grid is paramount to secure the transfer of datafiles and the ability to access different databases. Drones can provide relay nodes in a grid and UGVs and USV can be base stations and battery charges.

Identification of Gaps			
First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4-1-6	Distribution of equipment	Transport of needed equipment to first responders	In all disaster relief operation, the first responders will need different type of equipment. A lot of it, such as bandages and medication, may be in continuous demand from the first responders. To get equipment from the storage areas and out to the first responder teams is logistically demanding under normal condition but in a disaster area with destroyed roads and inaccessible areas this will become a challenge. In recent years several unmanned vehicles have been developed with the purpose to transport goods. For the first leg, from main storage areas, UGVs can transport goods and equipment to the forward operation bases (FOB). From FOB, a UAV can take small parcels to the first responders in the field. Also, at sea, the possibility exists to use USV as transport units from shore to disaster area and use UAV to distribute the parcels to the different vessels operating in the areas.
G4.1-7	Supply energy and charging capabilities	All electrically driven units need charging close to the operation area	Relatively small UAV's, USV's and UGV's has a short operation time, typically 30 to 60 minutes, and a limited speed. It is often crucial that charging facilities can be moved close to the operation area. These "mother" vehicles can either be ground or water based and also act as a communication centre.
G4.1-8	Conduct search and relief missions		Unmanned systems have a potential to give first relief to casualties found by surveillance drones or by tracking of mobile phones the system can find and identify missing persons, and can deliver lifesaving equipment to the persons in need or by someone nearby with the possibilities to assists.

Table 5 - Gaps from First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units.

5.2. Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals

5.2.1. Deployment and convergence of communications infrastructure

G4.2-1: Communication coverage and availability and G4.2-2: Network recovering in case of disaster.

It is necessary to make the proper and relevant arrangements for the rapid shipment and installation of equipment, as well as any other preparatory work required for ensuring its operation,

G4.2-3: Limited coverage ranges in communications devices and G4.2-4: Communication coverage and availability.

As a disaster may evolve to larger areas, its need for coverage expands, and different technologies may be explored, due to its technical range, or by implementing relays stating to increase the communications range (26) (27).

G4.2-13: Ad hoc network coverage.

As multiple devices and these technologies will be involved in the emergency actuations, the coverage provided by ad hoc deployment could not include all of them.

G4.2-15: Accurate service provisioning.

Due to the variability of the first aid actuations, the service provisioning might be inaccurate, leading to malfunctions and security breaches.

5.2.2. Integration with existing communication technologies

G4.2-16: Ad hoc network scope.

Ad hoc emergency services networks are often developed at regional, local or even agency level in EU countries (e.g., in Spain), which runs counter to the interoperability of systems and services in emergency response.

G4.2-5: Dynamic device selection based on transmission preference and G4.2-8: Lack of secure communications.

To enable a joint force cooperating, the differences between the networks/technologies must be harmonized to achieve communications interoperability between them (28).

G4.2-27: Coms range extension, G4.2-28: Data rates, and G4.2-29: Data latency.

A primary disaster emergency communications capacity is the standby capacity for the rapid deployment of communications equipment during a disaster. Rapidly deployable emergency communications capacity requires stockpiling and maintaining communications equipment in order to establish, restore and expand communications services in the event of a major disaster. So, In response to the disaster and emergency events, first responders are deployed into the areas of impact, providing personnel, equipment, Vehicles, Software Applications, etc, including the communications infrastructures. Legacy system and new system, different technological solutions, different communications platforms are coming together into a joint response. These solution and communication resources have different performances, ranges and coverage, data rates, data latencies, using different protocols including the data referential can be different.

The wide areas radio coverage required to support the response in large areas events requires the connectivity to be dynamic and extensible as the events unfold. Also, as the number of responders increases so does the connections points and required available data transfer capacity. In turns, as the communication increases, especially with new capabilities, such as video, audio and stream, combined with platforms, such as drones (air, ground, maritime), wearables, cell phones, etc, it pressures the networks capacity to maintain a good operational level.

In such cases a critical coordination challenge is the data rates availability of the networks to fully support the communication needs, while, at the same time, network latency tends to increase, degrading the communications service. The radio-based network requires additional connection to increase radio coverage demands by using radio relays, satellite (for BLOS), or other networks technologies that enables wider coverage.

G4.2-32: IP network layer.

In order to achieve the best harmonization available, we must first set up joint mechanisms that will be used for the purposes of deployment in cases of disasters and provide a Common communication model which can easily be integrated thought a common interoperability IP Layer. All devices, application and data providers are required to support or have the means to access a common network interoperability layer, such as IP.

G4.2-39: Querying data

As multiple forces cooperate in a large emergency event Response the ability to share data in a proper and efficient way turns out to be a major issue. It is not practical and or feasible that all the data generated by all the entities and applications involved in a Response to be shared between all entities. It would generate a potentially overload the network and generate a lot of data noise to the entities, generating confusion among the FR. But the ability of any entity to obtain the relevant data from the multiple sources within the network remains as a need, in an effective and efficient federated querying way. Communications confidentiality in emergencies

G4.2-6: Lack of secure communications and G4.2-7: Lack of communications security monitoring, and G4.2-9: Lack of strategies to determine the best technology based on security constraints.

Otherwise, a lack of optimal capabilities would lead to failures, such as lack of data availability or lack of PKI coverage.

G4.2-25: FR and Victims data.

As a large emergency event expands, so does the potential number of victims and involved First responder, that needs to be accounted and continuously supported. The challenge is to manage the priorities in the field and access to the victims' and to FR data is a fast-developing event. The access to an improved situational awareness of the victim's health status as well as of FR health

status, enable a better response planning, including, if possible, the health vitals. The vitals data gathering is another challenges and current gap, that could be mitigated by using nouvelle individual health remote sensing artifacts.

G4.2-38: Share health data.

With the access to victims and FR health data, it is of the most importance that it can be properly managed and used, through the chain of processes and entities involved in the response. Because each entity has its own systems not all natively follow the same standards and protocols, which limits their response.

G4.2-14: Personal Data.

As the personal information related with emergency actuations will likely be sensitive data, data processing could be enabled only as long as confidentiality requirements and legal bases conditions are satisfied. Data protection impact is not always tailored developed.

5.2.3. Communications redundancy

G4.2-10: There are no strict guidelines for backup plans and G4.2-34: Communications redundancy.

For areas prone to major destructive disasters, reporting capacity is important as it provides redundancy and backup for existing terrestrial communications means, applications, and operational assets. To operating in a high demand Emergency event, often facing multiple communications issues, such as communication internment connectivity, coverage constraints, networks unavailability, traffic congestion, etc., End-User face the needs for multiple alternatives, with several levels of redundancy and back-up plans.

G4.11: There are no contingency plans at EU level for data restoration and G4.12: Lack of redundancy systems and services in the event of failure or catastrophe.

Such capacity should be able to withstand the initial disaster and may also be used as backup for early warning and emergency communications in the early stages of disaster management.

G4.2-20: Asymmetric information flow.

The flow of information throughout the disaster response process is neither constant, nor does it have the same amount of information in each direction. From the moment of impact until the arrival of the first responders, the flow is very irregular and occurs from the immediate vicinity of the disaster to the various institutions involved (centrifugal). When the first responders assess in-situ the extent of the consequences of the disaster, the amount of information leaving the impact zone increases greatly and can saturate the capacity of the communications systems, even saturating the input systems of the coordinating centre. After this phase, once the institutions have an idea of the magnitude of the catastrophe and interventions are underway, the bulk of the information normally enters the disaster centre (centripetal) in the form of orders, indications, etc., much less demanding in quantity.

G4.2-21: Line saturation.

In the management of catastrophes such as the terrorist attack on the Madrid train stations on March 11, during the first moments after the explosions, due to the large number of calls on the mobile network, the nearest cells were saturated, preventing access to the network. This has happened in many other disasters, in which the emergency services that have used GSM as their main communication network have had problems due to the number of calls from witnesses, injured people and emergency services in the disaster area. It is possible that this situation occurs only when the disaster occurs in densely populated areas, with a large number of people with mobile telephony and data availability. But it is also true that in less densely populated areas, cells are larger and may have less capacity to handle large numbers of calls or handle large amounts of data.

G4.2-22: Terminals that are difficult to operate in disaster situations.

On the other hand, terminals commonly used by emergency services have capabilities that allow intensive daily use but are not focused on usability in a very demanding environment. For example, the TETRA technology that we use on a regular basis requires at least one free hand for its operation, holding the transmission button during the entire communication, or even dialling certain numbers to access certain capabilities. First responders, especially in the early stages when the balance between resources and needs is so unfavourable, must have systems that ideally communicate completely unattended or with minimal handling requirements, which would in turn minimize and ideally mitigate communication issues.

G4.2-26: TETRA coms.

Although TETRA is a widely used emergency communication system, its functions and coverage are not uniform across its users, which may lead to different operational constraints and require some harmonization.

5.2.4. Difficulties in the setting up of communication links**G4.2-41: Legal and regulatory constraints.**

Disaster management authorities develop national disaster communications capacities for emergency response. However, it is recognized that there are major capacity gaps, which cannot be easily bridged by individual developing and disaster-prone countries, especially the small economies in the region. Disaster management legislation does not exist in every country and emergency communications are not seen as mandatory for many telecoms service providers (29).

G4.2-37: Blockchain redundancy.

A key element of the emergency systems is related to the capability to provide privacy security, and to ensure that the data exchanged falls under the ruling of the ethical and legal guidelines and that it can be assessed and checked, which could explore Blockchain network and features to ensure such functions.

G4.2-42: No institutional set-up for communications during emergencies.

Institutional constraints, such as no institutional/organizational set-up for communications during emergencies, insufficient or non-existent coordination among Government agencies and the private sector, an insufficient capacity to deal with different technical options and relevant operators, service providers and equipment vendors, weak negotiating power with satellite operators and equipment vendors, partly due to small markets, and no contingency plan to deal with disaster emergency situations

G4.2-43: Constraints with cross-boundary movement of communications.

Constraints with cross-boundary movement of communications facilities and telecom services, no planned management or coordination as well as limited preparedness among international agencies for mobilizing communications resources in emergencies

G4.2-17: Inadequate reliability of the 2G, 3G or 4G network in disasters.

2G, 3G or 4G are the most widely used alternative to TETRA radio systems by the emergency services, especially in terms of data transmission. But reality shown that their capacity and availability is very limited in mass casualty incidents, where these networks often have collapsed within first minutes.

G4.2-40: System fragility due to interdependencies.

Building the capacity of major disaster/emergency communications means at a fully operational level may be beyond the capability of most of the developing countries, especially the most disaster-prone. Technically, a cost-efficient disaster communications capacity should be a hybrid of all infrastructure and services available to the areas concerned in order to ensure accessibility and usefulness. Institutionally, the nature of such capacity should be such that it can be activated and put into effect on short notice. Mobile network technologies also present transmission reliability problems, making it necessary to improve transmissions in the future and adapt them to multi-victim incidents.

It's an established system that has essentially run out of steam, and it can't actually live any longer. And it's getting close to that point of fundamental transition. We are in a transition period toward the creation of a new system. While there will be a lot of failure in the current system, there is also a huge possibility for something new to develop. And when we look at the lifecycles of earlier systems, we may also learn from the life cycles of diverse ecosystems throughout history.

G4.2-36: APPS/Functions redundancy.

In response to the multiple needs and different operational capabilities made available by the different End-Users. Multiple applications from different end-users and FR can be explored in a federated approach, allowing different application that may provide similar function, thus improving the federation operational resilience and mitigates the applicational unavailability derived from connectivity loss/degradation.

G4.2-24: Local data collection.

May be required to local application to continue to operate in the cases of temporary connectivity loss or sub.-networks disconnection from the main network. Local data collection enables the re-sync of the data once connectivity is re-established.

G4.2-35: Data cluster.

In order to improve the resilience and performance of a multiple applications environment data sharing approach, clustering of the data sources and data elements may use, reducing the dissemination of the data from all thought the network consuming time and network bandwidth resources.

G4.2-31: Data protocols.

A challenge to integrate different End-Uses solution and application is the multiplicity of data protocols, data models, network structures and protocols, and information codification each ones uses. Based on the use case we will have defined the protocols for better understanding and collaboration between multiple parties operating in a common and federated context.

G4.2-33: DATA shared

For a federated approach, we need to explore the various aspects of collaboration and data exchange between the end users. So, sharing the same type of technology might not be that easy, we need to overview what tech is needed that can easily be embedded to existing system and be a valuable collaborator for the platform that supports the data sharing. The data sharing requires not only the ability to exchange data, but also that the data codification is common and its meaning is understood.

G4.2-30: Data priority.

The time criticality of the information shared and well as the bandwidth of the connection, may be different from each end-user perspective, but a proper coordination implies a minimum common vision about the data priority. Otherwise, the operational integration is not achieved as the data consumer and data producer priorities may render impossible to synchronize the actions.

G4.2-40 System fragility due to interdependencies

As different data inputs are originating from federated systems, their independencies are fragile due to different standards or definitions. As so, a common validation mechanism is required to validate and authenticate critical mission data exchanged (tactical data)

G4.2-18: Negative burden of low frequency of use and legacy solutions.

The networks used by the Emergency Services are generally adequate for their usual activity and will have involved a significant investment over time. Large new investments in infrastructure

or devices with no obvious day-to-day impact, but only for infrequent incidents such as MCIs, is an unattractive prospect for their managers.

5.2.5. Standards

G4.2-19 Consolidated reported information.

The standards provide tools, organization, and good practices within the scope for which it was designed without being restricted to a scope of business activities. Under the need for high demand and exceptionality when they acquire a special added value.

There is a need for the development of uniform organization structures at the international level. It has been identified that the structures, profiles, and roles are very different between different countries, generating a high risk of generating non-optimal information and data, causing difficulties in receiving and delivering information at equal levels of responsibility with the necessary quality. This information is generated by the devices that need to be used correctly and generate the information for third parties in the appropriate way to always maintain useful and consolidated information.

G4.2-23 Minimum acceptable technology requirements.

The continuous advance in technology and the great importance of public investment in terms of equipment, devices and technological infrastructure means that there is an implementation at different levels among all states, and where technology advances much faster than the financing possibilities of the states and, to a great extent, of private companies. This generates a necessary harmonization of minimum technological requirements to guarantee that in any circumstance the basic functions will be covered; as well as having the necessary equipment and infrastructure. In the same way, it will be necessary to consider minimum requirements based on the different roles and profiles; and respond to the demand of these needs. An example of this would be the necessary devices for decision making or information analysis and field equipment; and a degree of complexity is added considering the various technological infrastructures of each country, and additionally, service capacity under exceptional circumstances.

Table 6 summarizes all the gaps identified over “Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals”. For each gap, a traceability identifier is provided in the text, the type of input (whether it is a gap identified by professional experience, survey, or literature), the justification for its inclusion, and the partner that identifies it.

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-1	Communication coverage and availability	Professional experience	Current technologies used for communication present coverage limitations, especially in rural

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			areas. This is a drawback for emergency agencies that rely in specific technologies.
G4.2-2	Network recovering in case of disaster	Professional experience and Survey	Network architecture deployed during multiple casualty emergencies may not have adequate mechanisms to recover telecommunications services.
G4.2-3	Limited coverage ranges in communications devices	Professional experience and Survey	Due to the heterogeneity of the devices, many of which are limited in performance, data transmissions are made over short distances.
G4.2-4	Bandwidth appropriate to the level of coverage	Literature (26) (27)	The types of use cases in a disaster response scenario—sharing high resolution GIS maps, streaming video, and large amounts of voice communication—necessitate high-bandwidth and low- latency connections.
G4.2-5	Dynamic device selection based on transmission preference	Literature (28)	Particularly in disaster events, networks in affected areas typically receive very high volumes of incoming calls and data. A limiting factor is concurrency with large numbers of devices communicating simultaneously.
G4.2-6	Lack of secure communications	Survey	Certain emergency services do not use secure communications for sensitive data transmission.
G4.2-7	Lack of communications security monitoring	Survey	Most network architectures deployed in emergencies do not have network monitoring systems capable of detecting threats or anomalies.
G4.2-8	Most communication technologies are not interoperable.	Professional experience and Surveys	Technologies used nowadays in emergency scenarios work insulated from the rest.
G4.2-9	Lack of strategies to determine the best technology based on security constraints	Professional experience	There are no regulations or guidelines for selecting the most suitable communication technology or protocols based on security requirements.
G4.2-10	There are no strict guidelines for backup plans	Surveys	There is a lack of regulations that enforce emergency institutions to implement backup plans

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-11	There are no contingency plans at EU level for data restoration	Professional experience	In case of data loss, there are no clear guidelines on how to proceed.
G4.2-12	Lack of redundancy systems and services in the event of failure or	Professional experience	In the event of an emergency affecting the proposed systems, there are no identical systems to make up for this shortcoming.
G4.2-13	Ad hoc network coverage	Literature (30)	As multiple devices, and thus technologies, will be involved in the emergency actuations, the coverage provided by ad hoc deployment could not include all of them.
G4.2-14	Personal Data	Literature (31)	As the data related with emergency actuations will likely be personal and sensible data, it is possible that not all the confidentiality requirements will be satisfied.
G4.2-15	Accurate service provisioning	Literature (32)	Due to the variability of the first aid actuations, the service provisioning might be inaccurate, leading to malfunctions and security breaches.
G4.2-16	Ad hoc network scope	Professional experience	Ad hoc emergency services networks are often developed at regional, local or even agency level in EU countries (e.g., in Spain), which runs counter to the interoperability of systems and services in emergency response.
G4.2-17	Inadequate reliability of the 2G, 3G or 4G network in disasters	Literature. (Aal-Nouman M et al. 2020)	2G, 3G or 4G are the most widely used alternative to TETRA radio systems by the emergency services, especially in terms of data transmission. But reality shown that their capacity and availability is very limited in mass casualty incidents, where these networks often have collapsed within first minutes.
G4.2-18	Negative burden of low frequency of use and legacy solutions	Professional experience	The networks used by the Emergency Services are generally adequate for their usual activity and will have involved a significant investment over time. Large new investments in infrastructure or devices with no obvious day-to-day impact, but only for infrequent incidents such as MCIs, is an unattractive prospect for their managers.

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-19	Consolidated reported information	Literature ISO 22351:2015 ISO 22396:2020	Creation of communication agreements. Development of message structures. Identification of profiles, roles and protocols.
G4.2-20	Asymmetric information flow	Professional experience	In the first moments of the disaster, the avalanche of information coming from the incident site can overwhelm the coordinating centre's ability to receive and process it.
G4.2-21	Line saturation	Professional experience	The use of shared technologies (e.g., mobile network, fixed telephone network) may be saturated not only by the personnel involved in the disaster, but also by other incidental or non-participants in the disaster. Each technology has certain limits for handling concurrent calls.
G4.2-22	Terminals that are difficult to operate in disaster situations	Professional experience	Terminals commonly used by emergency services provide a service adapted to a use that can be excessively complicated in the event of disasters, requiring many operations to initiate communication, and interruptions or disruptions that make communication difficult and result in loss of information.
G4.2-23	Minimum acceptable technology requirements	Professional experience	Determine minimum technological characteristics to guarantee optimal service level in emergency and disaster situations.
G4.2-24	Local data collection	Professional experience	Explore new sensors data networks (e.g., Lora) devices to collect local data.
G4.2-25	FR and Victims data	Professional experience	Explore new devices to collect First responder and victims' data.
G4.2-26	TETRA coms	Literature (1)	Coverage of TETRA data do not uniform across the users.
G4.2-27	Coms range extension	Professional experience	Use of relay nodes to extend the RF communications coverage of or to overcome Line of sight Communications limitations.
G4.2-28	Data rates	Professional experience	Different networks data rates impact quality of the data channelling through networks.

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-29	Data latency	Professional experience	Different networks latency impact quality of the data channelling through networks.
G4.2-30	Data Priority	Professional experience	In a limited bandwidth communications context, the absence of operational data priority impacts the decision-making process and managing of critical situation.
G4.2-31	Data protocols	Professional experience	Federated data may not be transmitted to different network if data protocols are not supported.
G4.2-32	IP network layer	Professional experience	Not all communication devices or networks support IP layer as a standard.
G4.2-33	Data shared	Professional experience	Different entities codify its data communication using different data protocols
G4.2-34	Communications redundancy	Professional experience	Emergency events often face multiple communications issues, such as communication connectivity, constraints, networks unavailability, congestion, etc.
G4.2-35	Data cluster	Professional experience	As the volume of information and data increases in large scale incidents, the data loss and recover, as well as the data sharing latencies and delays may impact the overall performance of the system.
G4.2-36	APPS/Functions redundancy	Professional experience	In emergency situation, a federated solution of applications/functions may be unavailable in case of communication / connectivity loss.
G4.2-37	Blockchain redundancy	Professional experience	Operational redundancy required redundancy may not jeopardize the system security.
G4.2-38	Share health data	Professional experience	Use a common data protocol / standard to share health data.
G4.2-39	Querying data	Literature and professional experience	Query different data sources in a common, scalable and efficient way.

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-40	System fragility due to interdependencies	Professional experience	Systems that consist of interdependent services may be face loss of functionalities even if one support service (dependency) fails.
G4.2-41	Legal and regulatory constraints	Literature and professional experience	There is a lack of protocols or legal aspects for a group of countries facing the same emergency.
G4.2-42	No institutional set-up for communications during emergencies	Professional experience	Current Government agencies and the private sector have an insufficient capacity to deal emergencies with different technical options.
G4.2-43	Constraints with cross-boundary movement of communications	Professional experience	Lack of planned management or coordination, as well as poor preparedness among international organizations.

Table 6 - Gaps from Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals.

5.3. Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies

5.3.1. Dangerous Zones, Number of victims, FR Information, CBRNE and relevant locations

G4.3-1: No real-time information exchange.

Note that in terms of data sharing large number of answers by FR remark are not provided effectively. Data exchange delays affect the decision making of forward ICP as the decision making process could omit a set of essential information.

G4.3-7: Non unified COP.

SA understanding is currently out of European interdependencies. Each agency deploys their own instruments without any overall frame of reference. Thus, the insights and key deductions regarding COP will be necessary to have an intuitive application.

G4.3-8: Situational awareness uncompleted set of information.

Data exchange often miss a set of essential information such as n° of tracking, n° of victims, responders, NO-GO zones and type of responders that could be relevant to achieve a better situational awareness and provide a better decision making process.

G4.3-9: Non harmonisation of graphics symbols, views, and representations.

Many of the emergency decision-making desires on overall perspective by Agencies Commanders. Without a transversal vision the decision making it must be reduced. Therefore, basic graphical symbols and language shall be harmonised.

G4.3-13: Meeting points.

According to the survey done, there is an identified gap related to the map of the meeting points established on a cross-border emergency area, and they should be taken into consideration. This information should be available to the C2.

G4.3-14: Type of dangerous substances.

Dangerous substances present on nearby the emergency and related to it should be part of the relevant data to be gathered and analysed to complete the situational awareness.

G4.3-15: Endangered areas.

Sensitive natural areas should be managed with overprotection, at it could cause irreparable damage to the ecosystem and this kind of information should be part of the decision making process.

The critical information and decision criteria are indeed different in day-to-day situations managed by an Emergency Medical Service compared to a multi-casualty incident. This means that the solutions developed for day-to-day EMS C2 and decision making are often not suitable for disaster medical management, requiring specific new functionalities.

G4.3-35: Victim's advance information.

Victims shared data should be provided to the action FR and medical response services that actually needs it, instead of widely spread all the victim's response data (not private data) to all the medical services. In particular, hospital response capability and the victims that can be supported by such medial services should be matched,

4.3-36 Victim's health / historical data.

Victims' health records should be accessed by authorized personnel, including any clinical data that may be required to provide get a victim health understanding and provide a proper and safer medical response.

4.3-37 Victim's data traceability.

Victims' health records data access is required to provide the safer medical services. To ensure that data accessed comply with the privacy and security policies, traceability, follow-up and monitoring processes should be set in place as part of the data handling procedures.

4.3-38 FR Follow-up.

Trace and keep records of the FR position during the vents, enables a better resources ground management and accounts for tracking FR in case of potential hazardous situations.

G4.3-30: Confidentiality versus information sharing.

The need to ensure the security of information transmission and the confidentiality of the transmitted data itself, especially in relation to emergency medical services, has sometimes worked against the development of interoperable C2 and decision support solutions, as well as facilitating the exchange of information sharing.

G4.3-42: Traceability of victims.

The limited access and the absence of victim's medical history data might limit medical operations and be a critical issue. The medical facility can directly examine the victim's past data, but the knowledge of the victim identity and authorization prior to its arrival at the medical facility may delay the medical response and reaction.

We want a mechanism to access victim's medical history data anywhere, anytime but we need to make sure the confidentiality, the privacy and the transparency stays within the only necessary parties.

Blockchain technology offers everything we want in order to fill that gap. The information and the data stored into the Blockchain ensures the integrity, the security and the trust of the correct data and most importantly, the instant access to that information within seconds. All we need is a device or a smartphone that has internet access.

All participants in a public Blockchain network trust the integrity of the information since they can all view and examine it in real time. However, if all of the information is transparent, it becomes available to anybody. But no one knows which data owns to someone except if you

authorize them or give them access to it. Means, in theory may possibly utilized by unknown people for unknown purposes.

G4.3-43: Identification of dangerous zones.

The definition of dangerous zones varies not only between countries, but also between agencies within the same country. Based on that, the first limitation in this domain consists in a heterogeneous delimitation of dangerous zones during emergencies.

G4.3-44: Identification of relevant locations.

Regarding the identification of relevant locations, each organisation uses particular technologies and, typically, their own technological solutions. Based on that, there is a lack of interoperability between solutions to unify how relevant locations are identified.

5.3.2. Standards

There are many standards addressing the command-and-control topic, nevertheless, gaps still remain. The question arising is “Why do first responders’ needs in command-and-control technologies and procedures still exist, since many standards address this domain?”. According to Tsaloukidis et al. (), an important role for this, plays the fact that many first responders do not use standards or are not even aware if standards are used in their operations. On the other hand, they make extended use of widely adopted guidelines and operational procedures. The transformation of such guidelines into formal standards as well as the integration and implementation of standards in first responders’ operations is a crucial topic to be further explored in the future.

G4.3-28: The legacy of solutions for C2.

C2 solutions have been developed largely at the agency level, highly focused on their own needs and heavily conditioned by their own development or procurement capabilities, which detracts from their effectiveness and works against accessibility and interoperability between first responders in different agencies or territories.

G4.3-31: Need for specific functionalities to meet specific needs.

The critical information and decision criteria are indeed different in day-to-day situations managed by an Emergency Medical Service compared to a multi-casualty incident. This means that the solutions developed for day-to-day EMS C2 and decision making are often not suitable for disaster medical management, requiring specific new functionalities.

G4.3-29: The weight of habit.

Unified C2 solutions developed at regional or national level are sometimes less used than would be possible because they involve incident commanders moving away from their own agency tools with which they are familiar, and in situations where stress and demands are higher.

In the case of Spain, a lack of standardisation at regional level has been identified. All incident management is carried out by the community’s own emergency coordination centre. However,

in each autonomous community the emergency services have different tools, both in the emergency coordination centre and in their own emergency services. No integrations, no data gateways. VALKYRIES aims to lead a common standardization to enhance synergies. Workload balancing to optimise resources such as materials and humans as well as integration of legacy investments among C2 Applications. FR note that occasionally they can deploy their C2 due to communications issues. Rapid situational awareness is needed and can be fulfilled without right communications. TETRA, mobile network, DMR, VHF radio are not enough to guarantee communications viability. Place technologies to benefit for better results.

Although numerous standards that cover the domain of command and control exist, there are still uncovered fields, on which future research and standardisation activities should focus. Sakkas et al. (2020) (34), have conducted a broad and in-depth research in order to identify gaps in standardisation in general, and in the command-and-control domain specifically. A standardisation gap is defined as a need for standardisation in a certain domain, expressed by first responders, which is not covered by existing or under development standards. For instance, regarding command and control technologies, as a standardisation gap could be considered the lack of standards regarding the formats of Graphic User Interfaces (GUIs) in coordination centres.

G4.3-23 Development of a standardised electronic triage system for the facilitation and improvement of logistics management and the accomplishment of situational awareness.

Triage is a crucial procedure and one of the first processes that take place during first aid response to disasters. This task must be executed as fast as possible in order to increase situational awareness regarding the number of victims and the severity of injuries, to facilitate decision making regarding the number of resources (personnel, EMS vehicles, hospitals) that has to be deployed and, thus, to overall facilitate response procedures and narrow down response times. Although there are standards addressing this gap e.g., the OASIS EDXL HAVE standard (Emergency Data Exchange Language Hospital Availability Exchange) (34), there is significant room for further standardisation activities to this direction.

G4.3.24 Standardisation of systems for an automated management of resources e.g., for the assignment of resources to tasks and missions.

In order to achieve a common operational picture, it is crucial for stakeholders, especially in situations that require a rapid and efficient coordination of a large number of heterogeneous resources (personnel, vehicles, equipment from different first responders' agencies), such as multi casualty incidents, to have a bird's eye view regarding the deployed resources and the assigned tasks. It is essential for incident commanders to have perfect knowledge of the "where", and "how many" resources are operating and "what tasks" are assigned to each one. Standardised systems that provide geolocation of resources and significant information about the tasks undertaken by each resource, could greatly enhance situational awareness related to response operations. On many occasions the ineffective and time-consuming process of

assigning tasks to resources can lead to confusion with devastating consequences and delays in first response.

G4.3-25 Standardisation regarding the processing of victims' personal data.

In multi casualty incidents, during which triage procedures take place, the processing of personal data regarding the victim's medical record and other sensitive information is shared among first aid responders. Standardisation for the compliance of such procedures with legislations for the protection of personal data is required. Standards and guidelines do exist e.g., CEN TR 15872:2014 "Health informatics - Guidance on patient identification and cross-referencing of identities" (35) and CEN TR 15299:2006 "Health informatics - Safety procedures for identification of patients and related objects", WHO "The protection of personal data in health information systems – principles and processes for public health" and can be used as opportunities to address this challenge (36).

G4.3-46: Standardization of operating procedures.

The standards are general guidelines that must be adapted to the peculiarities of the field and the specific activities to be carried out. On the other hand, at the field work level, all the operational procedures, technical instructions, manuals and other documentation necessary for the personnel to carry out their work safely and optimally, such as the use of devices and equipment specially in a cross border situation between different state agencies and other organizations. The operational procedures are directly related to the standards currently approved in each organization. That is why there is a risk of a difficult adaptation of current operating procedures to international standardization.

G4.3-47: New command and control standards.

Command and Control equipment and infrastructure require technological characteristics and demanding standards. The addition of new equipment and devices add more variety of requirements and maintenance to organizations and their resources. This generates that the operating procedures are more extensive and complex, with the subsequent time necessary to acquire the necessary skills.

The standards related to Command and Control are being developed by the different technical committees and cover different interrelated areas, which requires continuous adaptation to the next updates of these committees and analyse to what extent they can optimize procedures, equipment, devices and infrastructures.

5.3.3. Sources of information

G4.3-2: Lack of sensory & communications integrations.

Relevant information can be obtained from mobile sensors, either via smartphones, drones (night and day) or other sensors carrying platforms, operationally engaged to provide the useful information / data details for the C2 decision maker. To operationally integrate these solutions

in the operational scenarios, Aerial and RF spectrum management capabilities are required. Currently there is a poor integration with the environment data.

Ground information could also be collected from the IOT deployable networks or already available network, and data sources can be extended to already available assets, such as CCTV or broadcast TV stations, or to external commercial services, such as satellite or data, providing that the interoperability and data exchange protocols interface are well established.

G4.3-4: Lack of information sharing between databases from different agencies.

A COP to provide adequate situational awareness needs to be fed by different sources of information provided by different agencies. The way to share this information between actors is mainly by entering the same data into each agency's application. Having a common way of getting/sending data from the databases of the different agencies would avoid errors and save time in the COP update and decision making process.

G4.3-5: Delays and disconnecting.

The need of data to respond to the disaster events is very wide, covering small or large areas simultaneously, provide timely and relevant information, with information granularity, accuracy and resolution that makes it actionable.

According to the survey done, the C2 commander is not able to take decisions because of the delays in gathering data or even the impossibility to connect to that data because of the network issues.

G4.3-6: Lack of C2 communication means in rural areas.

In addition to the usual network issues during and emergency, the network availability on rural areas is usually poor due to the terrain characteristics and even the investment in infrastructure, what makes difficult to establish a proper communication between all actors involved in the emergency management.

G4.3-10: Short accuracy for network transmitter.

As a specific case of gap G4.3-6, the need to extend the scope of network coverage to communicate with the 112 emergency coordination centres is detected, as not all geographical areas have connectivity.

G4.3-11: Enhance time response signal of emergency vehicles.

Related to G4.3-5, the geolocation signal of emergency vehicles deployed in a MCI is too slow. Real-time communications allow to avoid problems related to the navigation of rescuers by the operator.

G4.3-12: Video imaging (CCTV) without integrated functionality.

CCTV cameras are fully deployed nowadays. However, the use of CCTV cameras in C2 is still very limited and their data could be very relevant for situational awareness. CCTV can provide wider coverage and situational awareness, in particular at cities, as another external source of tactical data, to cover the situation as well to follow the response.

G4.3-16: No agile communications between Advanced Health Post and Incident Command Post.

The exchange of information between the Advanced Health Post and the Incident Command Post is mainly done via radio/telephone calls. Therefore, the data flow between the posts is only updated when a call is made. Providing tools capable of sharing data between posts would allow for constant data updates and speed up the decision-making process and avoid losing relevant information. It also provides supports for a faster analysis of the scenarios thus enabling a faster critical time decision-making process.

G4.3-17: Information area coverage by drones

Large areas emergency events, such as forest wild fires, floods or earthquakes, often have impact on the available infrastructure, rendering unusable or seriously damaged. In such cases to generate a response plan that fit the scenario requires a good awareness of the full area extension of the emergency. Gathering aerial data, such as image, video, terrain data etc, is of key importance to adapt the assets and strategy to the terrain conditions. A continuous streaming of scenario data gathered by swarm of drones with multiple sensors types and covering the most of the affected area, in a regular time frame, provides useful data to support the decision-making process.

G4.3-18: Improved imagery ground resolution

Aerial data resolution varies according the sensors characteristics and the altitude of the carrying platform. In case of wild fire, the extreme heat creates difficulties for aerial platforms to fly low and they tend to fly above the smog column with impact on the image ground resolution. Situational awareness requires the spot of some critical elements, such as hot spots, IR people signatures or other critical infrastructures signatures. The planning of aerial data gathering processes should take into account the required ground resolution of the information to collect.

G4.3-19: Drones' data protocols

In a demanding scenario of multiple drones carrying different and multiple high-resolution sensors (EO / IR / SAR / spectral / radar / etc), requires a communication link Air-2-Gound or Air-2- Air with a very high data rates so that all the different sensors streams can be exploited. To better exploit the data raw, the sensors metadata and the communication protocols should support the management of the stream channels that can be used at a time that better support the needs at any moment.

G4.3-20: Nigh data gathering

Large emergency events have can endure for days and weeks, day and night. Aerial data gathering is partially limited by the fly regulations and requirements. In an improved context of multiple drones flying under non segregated airspace combined with maned aircraft, is limited by nigh conditions as it requires to see and to be seen and fly in VFR conditions.

G4.3-21: Airspace management tools

Large emergency events have can endure for days and weeks. Aerial data gathering is partially limited by the fly regulations and requirements. In an improved context of multiple drones flying under non segregated airspace combined with maned aircraft, is limited by the reduce coordination processes between manned and unmanned platforms flying on the same aerial space. The aerial data gathering capabilities could be further extended by establishing dynamic assignment and aerial coordination tools.

G4.3-22: Drones RF management tools

In an improved context of multiple drones flying in the same aerial space, in a context of multiple communications channels, the management of the communications RF spectrum become critical, and needs to be managed to avoid communication conflict, communications interference and unplanned jamming of a drone radio command channel. Most of the commercial drones uses wi-fi or other commercially available frequency / channel Therefore, RF management in such scenarios should include drones radios communications.

G4.3-26 Standardisation regarding the processing of victims' personal data-Triage

As there is non common practice to handle data in the first stage triage starting from the point of where the victim was found, there is the need to introduce more flexible mechanisms to record any relevant data associated with the victim (location found with GPS and time tagging, any personal data gathered on spot, photos of the victim and the location, regardless if the first responder is medical professional or not.

G4.3-27 Clocks synchronization

Logging the transactions or data exchange with non-synchronized clocks of different federated systems or other mobile equipment can cause problems in auditing after the end of the incident.

G4.3-32: Lack of social media analysis on emergency scenarios.

The use of social media in emergency situations, and although some organisations use them, this strategy is close to be a common practise. In fact, there is an absence of guidelines and regulations offering recommendations for crawling social media data for analysing emergency situations.

G4.3-33: Lack of clear guidelines for selecting data crawling tools.

There is a wide variety of tools and technologies used for data crawling. In this context, it is difficult to identify which are the most suitable for solving this problem according to the social

networks or data sources consulted and the purpose of the actuations. In this sense, clear guidelines at EU level would be appreciated.

G4.3-34 Cross border trace of data sharing authorization

A major part of the data collected, generated or obtained in emergency scenarios, in particular data that is of confidential, security or privacy nature, have to comply with a body of law and regulation. Sharing such data between countries requires a common agreement and ruling of which data, how and when such sharing process can be done. Automatic tracing the data shared to the body of political decision and regulation that legally supports such sharing would greatly reduce the timing required to share critical data as well as to support the assessment and auditing of such data sharing processes.

G4.3-41: Wide use of sensors.

An increasingly number of potential new sensors and supporting data infrastructures are becoming available, that can add new types of data. This evolution will continue and the solution should be able to extend the number of sensors and expand the types of data streams.

5.3.4. Harmonization at national and supranational levels

G4.3-3: Insufficient the capacity of coalition cooperation.

Command and control aim to go beyond in terms of individual understanding to assume the total control a cross-border incident. The establishment of a command and control framework relies on ensure feasibility and flexibility technologies to facilitate the data gateway based on best practices. Collaborative effort shall ensure clarity in roles and responsibilities.

4.3-39: External data sources.

There are several external services that can provide valuable data and information to support the decision-making processes, originated from outside the FR federated sensors. Such as satellite, CCTV, public media, etc.

4.3-40: Social media.

Social media is another source of new data, which can be very dynamic and rich, as it is not bounded by governing models or hierarchical processes. The fluidity and speed of such sources can also generate unwanted responses on potential victims, such as misinformation and panic. Therefore, its usage, although of great interest, should be carefully handled, filtered and validated to avoid noise and mistrust.

G4.3-45: No widespread use of decision support applications.

The level of implementation of collaborative tools is very low. This represents an important gap for decision making and for collaboration between institutions at the supranational level.

The previous gaps are summarised in Table 7.

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-1	No real-time information exchange	Professional Experience	Emergency services coordination require near real-time inputs in order to avoid delays.
G4.3-2	Lack of sensory & communications integrations	Survey	Data-intensive operative environment is poorly integrated.
G4.3-3	Insufficient the capacity of Coalition cooperation	Literature	C2 overall design purpose should accomplish coalition fulfilment. (38)
G4.3-4	Lack of information sharing between databases from different agencies	Literature	The aim is to function as a cross-cutting emergency system while maintaining current tools. Tools such as the GIS have to be fed with external data. (38)
G4.3-5	Delays and disconnecting	Survey	Many times, the C2 Commander is not able to take decisions due to delays and disconnecting.
G4.3-6	Lack of C2 communication means in rural areas	Professional Experience	Prevent any comms failure due to terrain characteristics in rural areas.
G4.3-7	Disunified COP	Professional Experience	Currently there is not a common COP of the situation. Each agency has their own events and deploy their resources in function their overview.
G4.3-8	Situational awareness uncompleted set of information	Professional Experience	Missing set of essential information. To take advantage of the situation such as nº of tracking, number of victims, responders, NO-GO zones and type of responders are required.
G4.3-9	Non harmonisation of graphics symbols, views, and representations	Professional Experience	No global symbols. Add difficulties if the information is shared by third parties.
G4.3-10	Short accuracy for network transmitter	Professional Experience	Extend the range of network coverage to communicate with the 112-emergency coordination centre.
G4.3-11	Enhance time response signal	Survey	The geolocation signal of emergency vehicles deployed in GIS is too slow. Real-time

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	between Emergency Vehicles – Emergency Operator in GIS		communications prevent issues related to navigated rescuers by operator.
G4.3-12	Video imaging (CCTV) without integrated functionality	Professional Experience	CCTV Integration with external cameras. Integrations with third party SW.
G4.3-13	Meeting points	Survey	Map out the meeting points.
G4.3-14	Type of dangerous substance	Survey	Specify the types of hazardous substances to tailor deployment and mitigate negative effects.
G4.3-15	Endangered areas	Survey	Overprotecting sensitive natural areas. It can cause irreparable damage to the ecosystem.
G4.3-16	No agile communications between Advanced Health Post and Incident Command Post	Professional Experience	Communications between Advanced Health Post and Incident Command Post needs to be improved to speed-up the decision-making process.
G4.3-17	Information area coverage by drones	Professional experience	Improve the situational awareness of large areas events, to overcome the lack of aerial information and multiple sensors capacity.
G4.3-18	Improved imagery ground resolution	Professional experience	Have a high Ground imagery sensors data resolution is critical resource to manage the situation, in particular detection of hot spots.
G4.3-19	Drones' data protocols	Professional experience	Imagery quality for high quality real-time data transmission requires high bandwidth and proper metadata to enable ground applications exploitation from multiple drones' providers.
G4.3-20	Nigh data gathering	Professional experience + legislation	Aviation, including drones, have limited flying condition in night condition, from sunset to sunrise, in fire events, due to safety issues. Improved aerial coordination capability is required to plan night operations.
G4.3-21	Airspace management tools	Professional experience + Regulation	With an increased number of flying drones over the operational theatre, there is a need to improve the air traffic management capability, deconflicting

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			flight areas, establish aerial fences, and comply with safety, privacy, and air flying rules.
G4.3-22	Drones RF management tools	Professional experience	The increased number of RF communication used in MCI, including many drones operating in the same frequencies, may generated communication collision and/or loss of communication with some assets.
G4.3-23	Development of a standardised electronic triage system for the facilitation and improvement of logistics management and accomplishment of situational awareness	Literature	There is a need for a standardised system that allows for quick triage procedures to limit response times and increase situation awareness.
G4.3-24	Standardisation of systems for an automated management of resources e.g., for the assignment of resources to tasks and missions	Literature	There is a need for standardised system to be used for the management of resources e.g., geolocation of personnel and vehicles, tasks assigned to the different resources.
G4.3-25	Standardisation regarding the processing of victims' personal data	Literature	Standardisation for the compliance of sensitive data with legislations for the protection of personal data is required.
G4.3-26	Standardisation regarding the processing of victims' personal data-Triage	Professional experience	As no standard exists on who provides first phase triage (medical personnel only or and others), the initial identification of a victim, in most cases containing non-medical or other personal sensitive data, photos included, must be allowed using multi-colour bracelets supporting one form pf electronic tagging available (RF, 3DCode, NFT, etc.). Initiation and first entry of available data has to be

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			recorded in a secured way (strongly recommended in blockchain). Other important information related with the victim, such as location, time of triage/initiation, first-responder id, etc. is captured from first responder's smart phone or tablet recording the victim.
G4.3-27	Clocks synchronization	Professional experience	Different manual or computerized systems use different clock setting methods to synchronize. As the VALKYRIES system must link different federated systems all logging transactions or metadata in a common structure (blockchain logging), clocks synchronizations should be adapted through this function
G4.3-28	The legacy of solutions for C2	Professional experience	C2 solutions have been developed largely at the agency level, highly focused on their own needs and heavily conditioned by their own development or procurement capabilities, which detracts from their effectiveness and works against accessibility and interoperability between first responders in different agencies or territories.
G4.3-29	The weight of habit	Professional experience	Unified C2 solutions developed at regional or national level are sometimes less used than would be possible because they involve incident commanders moving away from their own agency tools with which they are familiar, and in situations where stress and demands are higher.
G4.3-30	Confidentiality versus information sharing	Professional experience	The need to ensure the security of information transmission and the confidentiality of the transmitted data itself, especially in relation to emergency medical services, has sometimes worked against the development of interoperable C2 and decision support solutions, as well as facilitating the exchange of information.
G4.3-31	Need for specific functionalities to meet specific needs	Professional experience	The critical information and decision criteria are indeed different in day-to-day situations managed by an Emergency Medical Service compared to a multi-casualty incident. This means that the solutions developed for day-to-day EMS C2, and decision making are often not suitable for disaster

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			medical management, requiring specific new functionalities.
G4.3-32	Lack of social media analysis on emergency scenarios	Professional experience	There is an absence of guidelines and regulations offering recommendations for crawling social media data for analysing emergency situations.
G4.3-33	Lack of clear guidelines for selecting data crawling tools	Professional experience	There is a need at EU level for providing clear guidelines indicating which tools are more suitable for crawling social media for emergency scenarios.
G4.3-34	Cross border trace of data sharing authorization	Professional experience	Data shared among countries are subjected do international agreements and authorization which, and the identification of which data is allowed to be shared at each moment is required.
G4.3-35	Victim's advance information	Professional experience	The number of victims, its status and health conditions must be matched with the hospital medical capability and reported to the specific destination medical facility. There is no point if sharing all the data of victims to medical facilities that are will not receive the victims. It will only generate noise.
G4.3-36	Victims' health / historical data	Professional experience	Absence of the medical historical data of victims can limit the medical procedures. The victim's historical data can be directly assessed by the medical facility, but the information of the victim identification and authorization prior to its arrival to thew medical facility may delays the medical response.
G4.3-37	Victims' data traceability	Professional experience	Improve the Victims traceability and tracking while in the response process to avoid victim loss in the transportation process, or loss of victim's awareness.
G4.3-38	FR Follow-up	Professional Experience	Last know position of FR and trace its position provides a valuable resource management capability.
G4.3-39	External data sources	Professional Experience	There are many potential external sources of information that can be integrated in the system, providing additional valuable data.

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-40	Social media	Professional Experience	Social media data and information usability in C2 systems requires a careful filtering and validation to avoid misinformation and data noise.
G4.3-41	Wide use of sensors	Professional Experience	There is a wide range of new sensors and protocol, easy to deploy that can provide valuable field data, and are not currently exploited.
G4.3-42	Traceability of victims	Personal experience	In MCIs, victims, especially unconscious ones, maybe transferred to a medical facility without their families being notified, rendering their tracking extremely difficult both for the families and the relevant authorities as well.
G4.3-43	Identification of dangerous zones	Professional experience	The identification of dangerous zones varies across countries and organisations.
G4.3-44	Identification of relevant locations	Professional experience	Organisations use different technological solutions to identify relevant locations.
G4.3-45	No widespread use of decision support applications	Professional experience	The use of decision support applications is not widespread in the emergency services.
G4.3-46	Standardization of operating procedures	Professional experience	The need to update current operating procedures with new standards, equipment and devices is detected.
G4.3-47	New command and control standards	Professional experience	Necessary review of command and control standards.

Table 7 - Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies.

5.4. The digitalization on first aid actuations

G4.4-1: Lack of iconographic standard.

The lack of iconographic standards poses as a threat during the emergency actuations and the communications, and hence, it is required to standardize the European iconographic representation to be used by the first responders during the emergency actuations.

G4.4-2: Iconographic discrepancies.

It is common that the signalling employed during emergency actuations will present usage discrepancies between nations/organizations and it need to be standardized.

G4.4-3: Language barrier.

Currently, every nation uses its language in emergency communications, hindering the information sharing, it may be a problem that don't use the same language.

G4.4-4: Data normalization.

As multiple digitalization instances should be interconnected, such as DTAs and Static models, the data should be normalized or standardized in a common language as seen on the last gap.

G4.4-5: Graphical capabilities.

Although the digital modelling does not require too much computing nor graphical capabilities, not all the systems currently involved during first aid actuations might be able to support its representation.

G4.4-6: Continuous communication.

As the digital representation should be a faithful representation of the emergency actuations, the information should be constantly updated.

G4.4-7: Ad-hoc network coverage.

The digitalization of first aid actuation poses as a challenge itself, and the integration with suboptimal networks might be a hard challenge that should be addressed during ad-hoc deployments during emergency actuations.

G4.4-8: Neglecting to facilitate the work of the first responder leads to the failure of proposals.

Digitalization solutions for EMS intervention in multiple casualty situations do not always identify the main objective of making the work of first responders easier in these situations, which are even more demanding and stressful than usual. This reduces the chances of success.

G4.4-9: Reliability and usability in extreme conditions, a necessity in disaster response.

The reliability and usability of electronic devices in extreme conditions is very high nowadays, but there are specific conditions in disaster intervention that still need to be improved:

behaviour in rain or blood, usability with stained gloves, use in low visibility conditions, excessive brightness or radical contrasts, etc.

G4.4-10: Generational digital divide in healthcare.

Despite technological advances and growth of social demand to incorporate them into daily clinical practice, the level of implementation of digital innovation in the healthcare sector is still limited and slow, partly due to the generational digital divide.

G4.4-11: Excessive use of non-digital communications

Currently, the systems used in healthcare do not incorporate artificial intelligence to manage information objectively. Because of this, this information management and decision-making lies in an expert person, however this person may be in situations of very high stress or where he/she must choose between life and death situations. This is why an intelligent system that provides an objective view of the situation from the data obtained, can provide a more accurate solution in certain situations.

Likewise, traditional learning systems based on simulations are currently used, which involve a large investment in time and resources. More modern forms of learning, such as the use of virtual reality or video games that simulate what would be encountered in a real use case, are not employed. By using these systems, learning could be quantified and adapted for each FR.

The low implementation of digital systems in emergency services is a crucial problem. The budgets of the various regions severely limit the possibilities for digitalization of actions. The main consequence of this problem is that most of the actions are communicated by speech, through voice channels, which is a major problem for the registration, traceability and non-corruption of information when passing from one node to another (the "telephone game" (39)). From the professional experience of experts, in very few cases, very rudimentary tools are used for decision making. In other cases, other tools (such as an Excel table via MS Teams) for collaboration between teams are used for patient registration.

G4.4-12: Digitization increases the workload of first responders

The digitalization of the first aid actuations poses as a disruptive opportunity whose implementation faces multiple challenges that should be properly addressed.

In very few cases, very rudimentary tools are used for decision making. In other cases, other tools (such as an Excel table via Microsoft Teams) for collaboration between teams are used for patient registration. And in most cases, there is no such tool in use. When emergency services have tools for digitizing their actions, such a tool is developed for use in normal circumstances. Usually, these tools have a very low level of user experience, it is not intuitive or simple. And this means that when they are attempted to be used in MCI, they are completely inadequate and divert emergency service workers from their main work of care. In principle e-tools should decrease the workload if every action is working properly. But the responders are afraid to start to use them, because of possible failure, which is common in the first phases of introducing of

new solutions. And on the other hand, learning, training and exercising is necessary in process of putting new e-tools into practice.

G4.4-13: Lack of uses of AI-based systems.

Artificial intelligence is currently used in a wide variety of scenarios to assist decision-making processes. However, such systems are not commonly applied in emergency scenarios, where the decisions are decided by experts without the assistance of technological solutions having an objective and external point of view. Particularly, human decisions and actions can be biased and subjectively performed based on previous experience, sometimes containing errors as professionals tend to be overconfident. Based on that, the use of intelligent systems to provide recommendations in emergency scenarios could be highly beneficial.

G4.4-14: Lack of ethical legal culture.

Ethical legal issues are considered only ex post as an administrative issue to be fulfilled and not as a part of the methodological development of the procedure. This creates some barriers in the solutions deployment, especially in case of cross-border scenarios, where possible national implementations could require additional technical as well as organisational safeguards to be introduced before turning on the application. Conversely, a by-design approach would avoid implementation issues in practical scenarios and increase trustworthiness in harmonised solutions.

G4.4-15: The importance of secure, immutable and privacy of sensitive data

Health is one of the most concerning issues in human society. The idea of health reflects an individual's social, economic, political and cultural conditions, which directly influence our quality of life. In this view, the need to improve healthcare quality arises. It is vital to ensure precise and concrete information for this purpose in order for the decision-making process to be relevant and valuable to the patient.

To protect and validity, privacy and security of personal and sensitive data, such as healthcare data, extra attention and a set of specialized regulations are required. Several healthcare systems face this issue in that they do not ensure the immutability of data, posing a threat to patients' privacy and security.

Blockchain technology provides a solution to this challenge by ensuring data with chronological order as well as authenticity, privacy and security.

An important feature of blockchain that is beneficial in healthcare industry applications is the decentralization. The fact that the information on blockchain is replicated between all nodes in the network offers transparency and openness, allowing healthcare patients to know how and when their data is being utilized. Because of its nature, it can secure data from potential loss, corruption or security vulnerabilities, and its immutability feature makes it impossible to alter or modify any record that has been added to the network, preserving the integrity and validity of patient information.

Blockchain are classified into three types: private, public and hybrid. Public blockchain is completely decentralized, with no entity in total control. They often use their own currencies, and anybody with access to the network may read the ledger and interact with the blockchain. Public blockchains strive to maintain individual user privacy while treating all users equally. This is problematic for many businesses including healthcare organizations. That is why private blockchain technology is gaining traction in healthcare and other industries.

While delivering all of the distributed benefits of public blockchain, private blockchain maintain some of the traits of more centralised, regulated networks. This improves privacy and eliminates many of the illicit activities often associated with public blockchains.

Without appropriate authentication, on one may enter this blockchain network. Private blockchains are by definition 'permissioned' and are typically set up for privacy concerns, where it would be inappropriate for a company to provide every member complete access to the whole contents of the database. They provide performance and accountability while being less expensive to operate.

All of this means that the private blockchain requires significantly less energy, fewer resources and fewer participants resulting in lower costs on a much more predictable scale which is very important in our case, in healthcare.

The following table presents a summary of the identified gaps within the digitalisation on first aid actuations.

Identification of gaps			
The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.4-1	Lack of iconographic standard	Professional experience	It is required to standardize the iconographic representation used by the organizations during the first aid actuations.
G4.4-2	Iconographic discrepancies	Professional experience	It is common than the signalling employed during emergency actuations will present usage discrepancies between nations/organizations.
G4.4-3	Language barrier	Literature (40)	Currently, every nation uses its language in emergency communications, hindering the information sharing.
G4.4-4	Data Normalization	Professional experience	As multiple digitalization instances should be interconnected, such as DTAs and Static models, the data should be normalized or standardized in a common language.
G4.4-5	Graphical capabilities	Professional experience	Although the digital modelling does not require too much computing nor graphical capabilities, not all the systems currently involved during first aid

Identification of gaps			
The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			actuations might be able to support its representation.
G4.4-6	Continuous communication	Literature (31)	As the digital representation should be a faithful representation of the emergency actuations, the information should be constantly updated.
G4.4-7	Ad-hoc network coverage	Literature (31)	The digitalization of first aid actuation poses as a challenge itself, and the integration with suboptimal networks might be a hard challenge that should be addressed during ad-hoc deployments during emergency actuations.
G4.4-8	Neglecting to facilitate the work of the first responder leads to the failure of proposals.	Professional experience	Digitalization solutions for EMS intervention in multiple casualty situations do not always identify the main objective of making the work of first responders easier in these situations, which are even more demanding and stressful than usual. This reduces the chances of success.
G4.4-9	Reliability and usability in extreme conditions, a necessity in disaster response.	Professional experience	The reliability and usability of electronic devices in extreme conditions is very high nowadays, but there are specific conditions in disaster intervention that still need to be improved: behaviour in rain or blood, usability with stained gloves, use in low visibility conditions, excessive brightness or radical contrasts, etc.
G4.4-10	Generational digital divide in healthcare	Literature (23)	Despite technological advances and growth of social demand to incorporate them into daily clinical practice, the level of implementation of digital innovation in the healthcare sector is still limited and slow, partly due to the generational digital divide.
G4.4-11	Excessive use of non-digital communications	Professional experience	Most emergency services in Europe use voice as their primary means of communication. Moreover, this use is sometimes not very brief and not very protocolized.
G4.4-12	Digitization increases the workload of first responders.	Professional experience	Related to G4.4-8. Many digital technologies currently used in emergency services are not useful for multiple casualty care because they require a lot of work, rather than freeing up first responders to deal with casualty care.

Identification of gaps			
The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.4-13	Lack of uses of AI-based systems	Survey	Currently there are no artificial intelligence-based systems for support in emergency situations.
G4.4-14	Lack of ethical legal <u>culture</u>	Professional experience	Ethical legal issues are not considered as a priority to be addressed by design
G4.4-15	The importance of secure, immutable and privacy of sensitive data	Professional experience	With the help of blockchain technology we can access patient's data in real time without delays risking human lives with the immutability, security and privacy that blockchain provides

Table 8 - Gaps from the digitalization on first aid actuations.

5.5. Instrumentation and health support wearable devices

5.5.1. Personal tracking

G4.5-1: Lack of user tracking.

There are currently several gaps that do not allow for proper tracking of the users involved in an incident. In the case of emergency incident management systems, they do not have methods for automatic tracking of both users and FRs in emergency incidents.

G4.5-2: Dependence of coverage on user tracking.

The use of cards as a method for identifying and triaging users leaves all the information out of the system, so it must be passed manually. This is time-consuming and very susceptible to communication failures. For the realisation of tracking, most solutions rely heavily on the available coverage. This factor needs to be considered when establishing a solution, as the incident must be carried out regardless of the coverage available at the time.

5.5.2. Identification of personnel and users of a federate system

G4.5-3: Lack of user identification.

This tracking must be adaptive, obtaining better performance as more resources are available, and reducing to the minimum functionality as these resources are limited. There are currently no systems in place to track users in emergency incidents. This is important both for locating patients within the different phases of an incident and for dynamically allocating or removing resources from a given phase. On the other hand, by tracking FRs it is possible to obtain a complete picture of where resources have been allocated and how they can be relocated.

G4.5-20: Unified User roles.

To unify the data access into a homogenous rules and accountability, the user of federated systems that are required to share data, need a common roles structure that provides the

reference guidance of the action each entity user can perform/data access within the system regardless of its specific role within the organization it belongs. This includes the roles for each user, being a FR or a victim of a disaster/emergency event

5.5.3. FR communications

G4.5-4: Current commercial devices do not have the necessary technologies.

After a review of the wearable devices currently available and sold commercially, it can be detected that there is not a wide range of technologies that they incorporate. Most of them are based on Bluetooth and RFID, leaving aside technologies such as Wi-Fi.

G4.5-5: Inaccessibility to the firmware of the devices.

In addition, in case commercial wearable devices are used which their firmware must be modified to match the required utilities. However, because these are commercial products, access to the source code is usually impossible, making modification of the source code very difficult.

G4.5-9: Different communication systems between First Responders

Different agencies (both between different countries and even within the same nation) use different communication systems.

Different technologies, e.g., VHF or TETRA radios as well as cell phones, are unable to interface properly. In addition, all these solutions depend on the presence of an active network.

G4.5-10: No common communication standard between different countries

In different countries, there are no common procedures governing communication flows between Incident Commanders of different agencies (Firefighters, EMS, Civil Protection, Military), and often the only solution is to set up liaison officers to relay information downstream. However, this creates slow news dissemination and dependence on local communication networks

G4.5-21: D2D communications integration

Some of the communication technologies used locally, by victims and FR wearables and other sensors, will have to be integrated in a communication structure to be used by the C2. So, the D2D communication protocols for the integration into federated system is a current need for an easy integration and scalability.

5.5.4. Patient monitoring of the vital signs, triage support and telemedicine

G4.5-6: Reduced device battery life.

This is dependent of batteries currently available for this type of device have a very short battery life depending on the functionality of the device. Thus, continuous monitoring of patients' vital signs or continuous sending of information may result in the device becoming unusable.

G4.5-7: Lack of use of wearable devices for first triage.

Nowadays, despite the use of wearable devices has increased, such devices are not currently implemented in those cases of assignment a first triage to patients in an emergency since the information is not reliable. Furthermore, due to this problem, there is a lack of functionalities according to medical regulations. However, first responders will be able to use information from wearables when the information given is reliable.

G4.5-8: Lack of devices to measure health status continuously in patients.

Wearable should display information according to a medical standard. On the other hand, there is currently a lack of devices for continuous monitoring of biosignals, and automatic detection of patient severity.

G4.5-22: Victims monitor data.

Monitor the victims/patient vital signs is a valuable information in demand, especially to ensure proper awareness of the victim's health situation, which is not possible with just a snapshot taken a given moment. By continuously monitor of the victim's health signs, including the time in transportation to the medical facility, and makes this historical data available for medical services, is a high need for tomorrow response services

G.5-23: Telemedicine.

The use of remote mobile technologies also enables to overcome a need of non-trained personnel to provide assistance in cases of critical need of the victims, guided from specialized remotely supporting personnel.

G4.5-25: Wearables for most critically ill patients

In disasters, many critically ill patients suffer extensive burns to the limbs, they may have very serious injuries, or even amputations. Most of the wearables that have been tested are worn on the wrists and can take vital signs in people with a certain skin colour and vitality, with structural integrity and with the absence of significant bleeding that would interfere with the sensors. In addition, the instructions for placement of these sensors should be simple and known to all rescuers. Therefore, before deciding on their use, aspects that depend on the injured and that may limit or hinder their use must be taken into consideration.

G4.5-26: Quality of wearables for medical use.

Wearable healthcare technology industry is booming and offers a huge set of functionalities such as heart rate or blood oxygen level, but those used for medical purposes should comply

with a certain level of quality. The requirement for greater quality has been underlined by the EU's recent introduction of new, tighter regulations covering healthcare wearables and other medical devices. Many products whose safety and reliability manufacturers have been able to self-certify will have to be approved by officially appointed standards certification bodies ().

G4.5-16: Lack of validated protocols for e-triage.

E-triage continuously monitors victims' vital signs and transmits them to an electronic triage system that displays victims' priorities in real time.

While experimental results show that these systems can save more lives than paper triage tags, triage protocols for ICM based on the parameters that can be monitored by the sensors currently integrated in wearables have not yet been validated and are still limited.

G4.5-27: Data format from victim's wearables must be interpretable by medical staff.

The information provided by wearables must be in line with medical requirements and interpretable by medical staff, otherwise they could be confronted with large volumes of inaccurate, incomplete, irrelevant and incomprehensible data, without sound principles to deal with them ().

5.5.5. FR protection during crisis response

G4.5-11: Difficult to report a personal threat.

Rescue operations during an MCI are a dangerous activity. The level of risk must be kept as low as possible by means of good organisation, a high level of personal preparedness and adherence to shared procedures, however, we must be aware that they can never be completely zeroed out.

Especially during the initial phases of the rescue, the situation will remain with a high possibility of sudden evolution. The presence of dangerous substances, the space in which they will have to operate, environmental conditions, safety issues and even physical fatigue and lack of food and water can put rescuers at risk.

To date, FRs' parameter monitoring systems are still extremely uncommon and the major strategies for signalling a physical threat or otherwise a dangerous situation remain.

To date, systems for monitoring the parameters of FRs are still extremely uncommon and the major strategies for signalling a physical threat or otherwise a dangerous situation remain the use of voice communications

G4.5-13: Dissemination of safety and security information to FRs.

The situation regarding safety and security issues during the course of rescue operations can change abruptly.

The problematic element is being able to transmit them to operators as quickly as possible.

Unfortunately, at present, it is not always possible to accurately locate operators at risk. In addition, communication depends almost exclusively on local systems that are not shared.

G4.5-28: Little use of wearables for the protection of first responders.

First responders are the frontline people in an ICM, so it is essential to ensure their physical health and mental resilience. It is not only the victims who need to be monitored, but also the people who care for them.

The use of wearables that provide data relevant to the protection of RFs is almost non-existent today in ICMs, although there is growing interest in this area.

5.5.6. Disaster fatality identification

G4.5-12: Not immediate detection and reporting hazards during crisis response.

An important problem is the identification of hazards within the crash.

Only the technical component of FRs, generally firefighters, have the expertise to define the presence, nature, and control of hazardous situations. At best, rescuers carry CO₂ or ambient O₂ sensors, but not explosimeters or "artificial noses" for other gases

From these considerations however comes the definition of NO-GO zones, the decision of internal road flows and the priorities for action. This information needs to get to C2, which will need to geolocate the hazards, develop the response strategy, and transmit it back to all FRs.

This creates a latency where non-technical rescuers may incur a hazard as they move around the site.

G4.5-14: Inaccurate Disaster Fatality Identification.

Anyone who has had experience of MCI knows that, however much effort is put into saving as many people as possible, a certain amount of dead people will have to be recovered.

The identification of deceased victims (DVI) during a major event is a complex process that can put forensic experts to the test. In such cases, in addition to aspects concerning the condition of the corpse, personal belongings, information about the location of the body, the surroundings and the proximity to other victims are also important.

Another important point is the presumptive identification, not performed by the forensic scientist, that can be obtained directly on the site. This operation, which, we repeat, has no legal validity, is essential for rescuers because it allows them to compare this identification with the list of missing persons. It can be carried out by direct identification of survivors, by finding identity documents on the victim or by analysing missing person's report cards and searching for a match.

There is no clear guidance on how to securely capture and transmit images of deceased victims, nor what additional data are needed (GPS location, photo environment, correlation with other victims)

G4.5-15: Problems related to mortuary laws.

Different countries have different regulatory arrangements regarding the identification of deceased victims.

Different agencies in charge of this function and different procedures make it difficult to think about handling MCI scenarios even with regard to the management of remains.

In particular, there is no consensus on how to carry out presumptive identification at the scene. In some cases, this task is entrusted to the Technical Rescue (fire brigade), in others to the Health System (EMS), and in others to the forensic police. Sometimes operations are carried out directly in a dedicated area of the worksite, in other cases the bodies are all transported directly to a mortuary away from the operations site.

Finally, the use of digital systems to aid identification procedures in the field is very uncommon and usually restricted only to the acquisition and transmission of images by more or less technological means.

G4.5-24 Cost of modern technology equipment.

Modern technological equipment, particularly gadgets directed at victims, may be extremely expensive to acquire in sufficient quantities, even for MCIs with a low number of victims, leaving FR agencies with few resources when a crisis comes.

Introducing new and modern technology for MCIs and for our system can increase or decrease the cost. The cost of technology equipment also will depend on the expenses needed to acquire and maintain the new technology.

However there are other factors besides costs to consider. A new technology may bring benefits such as transparency, maintenance, security, optimizations, and improvements in service delivery that are worth extra expenses. Before we commit to a new technology equipment we need to keep in mind the cost-effectiveness and the potential benefits should be made.

Modern technology equipment may appear to be expensive, but may be more effective and save money in the long term. It will be optimum if particularly where a low cost technological equipment and solution can be found to replace a high-cost, low tech application.

Modern technology equipment may be expensive at the early stages because of the low competition between competitors. Once competitors start to appear offering similar products the price will drop. All of this together cause prices to drop for the new modern technology as the technology is more adopted by more and more individuals/ organizations.

G4.5-17: Logistical constraints.

To be effective in an MCI, wearable devices for instrumentation and healthcare support need to be in place at the scene in the first moments of the accident. The logistics of ensuring this are complex, especially in widely dispersed emergency medical services. Conventional EMS vehicles, primarily ambulances, often have significant space constraints that leave little room for additional equipment.

G4.5-18: Relevance of investment in wearable technology in MCI.

The investment in the development or acquisition of wearables and communication solutions for the location, traceability or e-triage of victims in an MCI is considerable in large emergency medical services, being resources with a relatively low frequency of use compared to other resources destined for daily activity. Together with the fact that it does not lead to direct cost savings, it is often unattractive to the healthcare manager.

G4.5-19 Investing in acquisition may not be the best option.

The pace at which some technologies evolve, grow or expand can generate future legacy difficulties and challenges for the End Users and to keep up with the technology evolution, maintenance, personnel training and devices/devices obsolescence. A business model could be of shifting the risk to the services and technology providers.

Table 9 presents the summary of the previously indicated gaps.

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.5-1	Lack of user tracking	Professional experience - Survey	Currently, emergency incident management systems do not have methods for automatic tracking of both users and FRs in emergency incidents.
G4.5-2	Dependence of coverage on user tracking	Professional experience - Survey	Currently systems are not adapted to different needs depending on the coverage available.
G4.5-3	Lack of user identification	Professional experience - Survey	There are currently no devices that allow for the identification of users in emergency scenarios.
G4.5-4	Current commercial devices do not have the	Personal experience	Current commercial devices are severely limited in terms of the communication technologies available to them.

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	necessary technologies.		
G4.5-5	Inaccessibility to the firmware of the devices.	Literature review	Modification of the firmware that is built into commercial devices is either very costly or impossible, so it cannot be adapted to the requested needs.
G4.5-6	Reduced device battery life	Literature review	The battery life of devices can be greatly reduced when, depending on the technology they incorporate and how they are used.
G4.5-7	Lack of use of wearable devices for first triage	Professional experience	Wearable devices are not currently used to assign a first triage to patients in an emergency.
G4.5-8	Lack of devices to measure health status continuously in patients.	Professional experience	Currently no systems are used to monitor the different bio-signals of a patient and define the severity of the patient automatically.
G4.5-9	Different communication systems between First Responders	Professional experience	At present different agencies use different communication systems (VHF, mobile phone, TETRA) which may have signal problems, and which often do not “talk” to each other.
G4.5-10	No common communication standard between different countries	Professional experience	Even when, within the same country, there is a single strategy for communication between agencies in emergencies this standard is hardly ever extended beyond national borders
G4.5-11	Difficult to report a personal threat	Professional experience	The diffusion of solutions that make it possible to transmit requests for help or autonomously report dangerous situations of the FRs (e.g., panic buttons on radio equipment or position sensor) is still not widespread. In addition to this, the information is almost always transmitted to the system by voice over local networks

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.5-12	Not immediate detection and reporting hazards during crisis response	Professional experience	The use of personal sensors is often limited to CO and low O2 detection. Sensors sensitive to different substances and explosimeters are often hand-held devices. Wearables that allow a personal hazard warning to be sent are still uncommon.
G4.5-13	Dissemination of safety and security information to FRs	Professional experience	Transmission of safety- and security-related information is almost always via voice over local radio networks
G4.5-14	Inaccurate Disaster Fatality Identification	Professional experience	Only in some realities are images of the find scene captured, usually by camera, without the ability to transmit and store them quickly and safely. In addition, much other information is not detected (e.g., GPS location).
G4.5-15	Problems related to mortuary laws	Professional experience - literature	There are no shared DVI procedures between different countries. There is no clear guidance on how to make a presumptive identification already at an MCI site. The use of technological aids in the field is minimized
G4.5-16	Lack of validated protocols for e-triage	Literature (Sakanushi K et al, 2013)	Triage protocols for MCI based on the parameters that can be monitored by the sensors currently integrated in wearables, which are still limited, have not yet been validated.
G4.5-17	Logistical constraints	Professional experience	To be effective in an MCI, wearable devices for instrumentation and healthcare support need to be in place at the scene in the first moments of the accident. The logistics of ensuring this are complex, especially in widely dispersed emergency medical services. Conventional EMS vehicles, primarily ambulances, often have significant space constraints that leave little room for additional equipment.
G4.5-18	Relevance of investment in wearable	Professional experience	The investment in the development or acquisition of wearables and communication solutions for the location, traceability, or e-triage of victims in an MCI is considerable in large emergency medical services,

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	technology in MCI		being resources with a relatively low frequency of use compared to other resources destined for daily activity. Together with the fact that it does not lead to direct cost savings, it is often unattractive to the healthcare manager.
G4.5-19	Investing in acquisition may not be the best option.	Professional experience	Due to the accelerated rate of innovation in these devices, an eventual investment in procurement may quickly make these devices technologically outdated.
G4.5-20	Unified User roles	Professional experience	Each application and entity have its organizational structure, roles and accesses/permissions for their users. Sharing data in a non-coherent federation role structure can generate loss of trust and accountability.
G4.5-21	D2D communications integration	Professional experience	There is no global standard to easily integrate D2D communications assets and its data into a federated network.
G4.5-22	Victims monitor data	Professional experience	Critical data on the health status of victims are not available for medical services to prepare their response.
G4.5-23	Telemedicine	Professional experience	In fast development and large events nonskilled personnel may provide minimal assistance to victims in life threatening situation, where a remote guidance on how to provide minimal life support actions could save life. A Telemedicine service is required to provide this support.
G4.5-24	Cost of modern technology equipment	Professional experience	Modern technological equipment, especially devices aimed for victims, may be too costly to purchase in adequate quantities, even for MCIs with relatively low numbers of victims, leading FR agencies to have limited resources for when a crisis strikes.
G4.5-25	Wearables for most critically ill patients.	Professional	They may not be suitable for the most critically ill patients in whom injuries may make it difficult or impossible to place and take vital signs.

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
		experience	
G4.5-26	Quality of wearables for medical use	Literature	Wearable devices for medical purposes should ensure adequate accuracy and reliability.
G4.5-27	Data format from victim's wearables must be interpretable by medical staff	Literature	The information provided by the wearables must be in line with medical requirements and interpretable by medical staff.
G4.5-28	Little use of wearables for the protection of first responders	Professional experience	The use of wearables to protect first responders is not currently a common practice in emergency interventions.

Table 9 - Gaps from Instrumentation and health support wearables devices.

6. Opportunities

This section presents the analysis of opportunities derived from the previously presented gaps, which will be essential to identify harmonization actuations in terms of technology and, thus, be able to propose a roadmap for European pre-standardization.

6.1. First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units

6.1.1. Common operation picture

O4.1-1: Accurate and live weather data.

There are developed UAV systems using Quadro copter technology with the necessary sensors to measure all possible weather data. They are robust enough to withstand freezing temperatures and high winds, as presented in Table 10.

	Option 1	Option 2
Cost	+	++
Name	Meteodrone MM-641/SSE	Meteodrone MM-670 (ML)
BLOS	No	Yes
Picture		

Table 10 - Accurate and live weather data.

O4.1-2: Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure in the disaster area.

Aerial drones can be equipped with a variety of cameras from still photos to live video stream, both traditionally, low light and thermal images can be chosen. The drones come in a spectre of prices based on the quality of the technology from Go-pro technology with 1080 pixels up to 4k with 5000p. This gives an opportunity to make very detailed photos of the disaster area, with the possibility to zoom in on areas of interest. See Table 11.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Cost	+	+++	+++
Name	DJI Mavic 3	DJI Matrice 300 RTK	FOXTECH Great Shark 330 VTOL

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Endurance	+	++	+++
Picture			

Table 11 - Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure in the disaster area.

Another possibility are drones with First Person View (FPV) (see Table 12), where the operator sees what the drone sees, making it possible for very accurate navigation in congested or narrow areas.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Cost	+	++	+++
Name	Name Thinyhawk 2 freestyle	Walkera F210	DJI Phantom 4 pro
Picture			

Table 12 - Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure in the disaster area via FPV drones.

Another aspect of COP is the actual picture inside buildings, ruins, dense forests, and other areas where flying drones may have some limitations. The use of unmanned rovers can cover some of these needs, UGV are often classified based on the way they move, wheels, tracks, or legs (see Table 13). Regardless of this they are all very manoeuvrable and can climb obstacles.

Wheels	Tracks	Legs
University of Tallin	MSS Defence Dogo UGV	Anybotics- Anylegs

Table 13 - Up to date information about rovers.

In disasters in the sea, USV (Unmanned Surface Vehicles) may be used for, mapping and characterization of oil spills, to detect new tsunamis or earthquakes, among others. In addition, these maritime robots can be used in flood response. See Table 14 for more information.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Cost	+	+++	+++
Name	USN test drone	Kongsberg Maritime	Maritime Robotics
Endurance	+	++	+++

Table 14 - Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure in the disaster area using USV.

Unmanned under water vehicles-AUV is a smaller group of unmanned vehicles, but they have been in use for a relatively long period of time in survey missions under water. They are used in both private, civilian, and military operations. They are not necessarily important in early-stage SAR operation but may play an important part in searching drowned people, pollution, or special items like operation recorders (see Figure 8 and Figure 9).

Figure 8 - Search AUV (Norwegian Coast guard). (Wikipedia, s.f.)

Figure 9 - Mapping AUV. (Oceaneering, s.f.)

O4.1-3: Tracking of personnel, casualties, and equipment.

There are different ways to track, identify and control and it is all dependent on what level of details the disaster response teams are capable to handle. A complex system will need more dedicated competent personnel that may strain available resources. Example of systems are presented in Table 15.

	Option 1	Option 2
Type	Mobile APPS	RFID tag
How	Tracking based on Mobile phone data and GNSS	Tracking based on active Rfid transmission
Example	Salamander Mobile APPS	Wavetrend

Table 15 - Tracking of personnel, casualties, and equipment.

G4.1-4: Safe work environment for first responders .

6.1.2. O4-1-4 Safework environment for first responders

Two main approaches can be considered in case of responder’s safety in specific condition, like for example CBRN incident. The first is to train and equip as many responders as possible, so they will be able to ensure own safety from the very beginning of rescue action and not wait for specific rescuers. The second is to optimise related procedures to get special units on the site of incident and provide optimal action. While the first option relies mainly on financial sources, the second one represents room form research, development, and innovations.

- Ensuring of responder’s safety have to be analysed, divided into sub-steps, considered what can be done before arrival of special dedicated forces, by whom and how.
 - Possibilities to recognize the threat without specific equipment
 - Effective reporting by first-line responders
 - Options how to respond with limited equipment

- What are the opportunities for special units?
 - New types of PPE (personal protective equipment)
 - Body sensors and another technology, including communication tools
 - Joint multiagency / cross-board trainings and exercises (including VR, AR, etc.)
- Standardization and harmonization of procedures
- Effective inter-agency (inter-unit) communication and optimization of gathered information sharing.
- Cooperation with other RDI projects and initiatives.

Aspects affecting the above are:

- Training and education
- Procedures
- Technologies

Drones can be equipped with sensors able to find radioactive material or toxic substances in area where first responders must operate, as presented in Table 16.

	Air	Ground	Water
Picture			
Type	UAV with radiation sniffer.	UGV with sniffers for radiation, chemical and biological compounds.	USV for water sampling and monitoring
Name / manufacturer	Norse asset solution	Vehicles research development establishment of the Indian Ministry of Defence	OceanAlpha Group USV ESM 30

Table 16 - Safe work environment for first responder personnel.

6.1.3. Logistical Support

O4-1-5 Building ad hoc communication grid

In disaster area with severely damage to infrastructure drones is very suitable ad solution to act as communication relay stations. The standard equipment (like cell phones and tetra net) can be used a normal.

O4.1-6: Delivering equipment.

Drones is suitable to deliver parcels from storage areas to the first responders. This is a field where a multitude of different UAVs, UGVs and USVs are on the market offering this service some examples are shown below: f UAV for logistical assistance, presented in Table 17.

	Option 1	Option 1	Option 3
Cost	+	+++	+++
Name	DJI Mavic 2	Griff 200	Foxtech Great Shark 330 Pro VTOL
Endurance	+	++	+++
Cargo	800 g	60 kg	3 kg
Picture			

Table 17 – Examples of UAV for logistical assistance.

UGV for logistical assistance, introduced in Table 18.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Cost	+	++	+++
Name	Warthog UGV	Titan Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV)	Oshkosh Defence UGV project
Cargo	300 kg	700 kg	
Picture			

Table 18 – Examples of UGV for logistical assistance.

USV for logistical assistance, as depicted in Table 19.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Cost	+	++	+++

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Name	Unmanned system technology – AMY	Martac Mantas T38	Yara Birkeland
Cargo	35 kg	2500 kg	30 000 kg
Picture			

Table 19 – Example of USV for logistical assistance.

04.1-7: Supply energy and charging capabilities.

Several companies provide solutions to charge unmanned vehicles when in operations. Rovers have charging stations and UAVs can charge by inductive solutions. The main challenge with these solutions is the need for a working power grid. For the first responders out in the field this may not be available and traditionally they solve the challenge with additional batteries replacing in the UAV when necessary, or sending them back to command centres, and by that reducing the operation time.

A solution on its way to the market is UGV with solar panels and power storage bank. They will work as a charger for UAV, in or close to the disaster area. This will increase time the UAV are available for operations.

04.1-8: Conduct search and relief missions

Unmanned vehicles are ideal to use as an early asset to search disaster areas for casualties and give them some medical assistant while they report their findings. Based on the proximity of other persons they can give blankets, medicines, or defibrillator to let other give emergency assistant. At sea drones can work as a life buoy sailing out to personnel in the water. This information is summarised in Table 20.

Area	Technology	Graphical representation	Information
Air	Iris Automations Ambulance Drone		
Water	JTT Marine Search and Rescue Equipment R2 Pro		Remotely operated buoy with cameras, speakers

Area	Technology	Graphical representation	Information
Water	Unmanned system technology		

Table 20 - Drones in search and relief operations.

In disasters in the sea, USV (Unmanned Surface Vehicles) may be used for search and rescue, mapping and characterization of oil spills, to increase communication range, to detect new tsunamis or earthquakes, among others. In addition, these maritime robots can be used in flood response. These opportunities are summarized in Table 21.

Opportunities			
First responder vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.1-1	G4.1-1	Accurate and live weather data	There are developed UAV systems using Quadrocopter technology with the necessary sensors to measure all possible weather data. They are robust enough to withstand freezing temperatures and high winds.
OP4.1-2	G4.1-2	Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure in the disaster areas	Aerial drones can be equipped with a variety of cameras from still photos to live video stream, both traditionally, low light and thermal images can be chosen. The drones come in a spectre of prices based on the quality of the technology from Go-pro technology with 1080 pixels up to 4k with 5000p. This gives an opportunity to make very detailed photos of the disaster area, with the possibility to zoom in on areas of interest.
OP4.1-3	G4.1-3	Tracking of personnel, equipment, and casualties	A common problem in all disaster area operations is tracking of personnel. By using a blockchain based tag system on emergency response personnel and vehicles the command centre can have live updated information of where they are physically.
OP4.1-4	G4.1-4	Safe work environment for first responders	In all disaster relief operations, especially in urban areas, the present of hazardous or toxic material is highly possible. To protect the personnel involved with the right protective gear and to decide the best approach to the task, it is vital to know what type of substances may be present or what the smoke from the fire contains the present of toxicity or hazardous gases or material.

Opportunities			
First responder vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.1-5	G4.1-5	Build ad hoc communication grids	In large disasters the probability that the existing communication grids may be destroyed or overloaded. To make a temporary grid is paramount to secure the transfer of datafiles and the ability to access different databases. Drones can provide relay nodes in a grid and UGVs and USV can be base stations and battery charges.
OP4.1-6	G4.1-6	Distribution of equipment.	In all disaster relief operation, the first responders will need different type of equipment. A lot of it, like bandages and medication, may be in continuous demand from the first responders. To get equipment from the storage areas and out to the first responder teams is logistically demanding.
OP4.1-7	G4.1-7	Supply energy and charging capabilities	Relatively small UAV's, USV's and UGV's has a short operation time, typically 30 to 60 minutes, and a limited speed. It is often crucial that charging facilities can be moved close to the operation area. These "mother" vehicles can either be ground or water based and also act as a communication centre.
OP4.1-8	G4.1-8	Conduct search and relief missions	Unmanned systems have a potential to give first relief to casualties found by surveillance drones or by tracking of mobile phones the system can deliver lifesaving equipment to the persons in need or by someone nearby with the possibilities to assists.

Table 21 - Opportunities from First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units.

6.2. Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals

6.2.1. Coverage ranges in data transmissions, network availability, and specific technology

OP4.2-1: Use of alternative communication systems and OP4.2-2: Extend network coverage.

To face current limitations in terms of network availability and coverage, telecommunication companies and governments could invest in extending the network coverage to improve their capabilities in emergency scenarios. Moreover, first responder agencies could implant alternative communication technologies suitable in case traditional systems such as TETRA are not available in specific occasions. In another sense, current issues regarding the absence of institutional set-up for communications during emergencies could be solved improving network

coverage, network availability and network compatibility. Thus, government agencies and private companies could have an easier technological integration, thus easing the interconnection of technological solutions in emergency scenarios.

OP4.2-3: Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture and

OP4.2-4: Use of technologies that favour the extension of coverage to devices with fewer resources.

Satellite communications networks can provide communications services in disaster emergency situations. Communications systems based on satellite technology are vital until other means of communications, such as terrestrial communications networks, are fully restored.

OP4.2-38: Sectorization.

The restoration period may depend on the magnitude and intensity of the event, as well as the impact on relevant communications systems and infrastructure such as the electric power system. Satellites are the only wireless communications infrastructure that is not susceptible to damage from disasters, as the equipment sending and receiving signals (the satellite spacecraft) are located outside the Earth's atmosphere. A satellite-based communications system is an effective solution for disaster-related emergencies.

6.2.1.1. Sufficient connectivity in disaster areas

OP4.2-5: Use of mobile technologies to facilitate service delivery.

Furthermore, some emergency teams rely on traditional communication systems instead of TETRA, such as 2G, 3G, 4G, and 5G infrastructures, providing both audio and data transmission between first responders with an excellent data transfer and coverage. This has the advantage of using regular smartphones, reducing the cost and complexity of the technological solution implanted. It is interesting to note that nowadays, the 5G technology is not fully deployed by operators. Although it offers an improvement in data transmission compared to 4G, key features for emergency scenarios, such as quality of service or network slicing, are not yet available.

There is a certain variety of technologies that can be applied in emergency scenarios that occur in areas with sufficient connectivity. These scenarios are the most common since disasters do not normally provoke the alteration of communication capabilities, such as a traffic accident with multiple victims in a metropolitan area with good telecommunications coverage.

In this sense, one of the most used technologies in emergency scenarios is TETRA, a radio architecture based on trunking principles that allows the automatic management of radio equipment. Besides, it offers both individual communication between two terminals and conversations with groups of users, while keeping the protection of the shared information using encryption.

Finally, geolocation based on satellite communications, with technologies such as GPS and Galileo, are widely used for locating emergency vehicles and different resources, such as logistic ones. Moreover, they are commonly used by emergency teams to provide orientation both in

metropolitan areas and outside rescue missions. Despite the advantage that these technologies provide, the communication capabilities can be disrupted by a wide variety of causes. For example, in metropolitan areas, it is common to lost communication in large human concentrations such as concerts or sport events. In these situations, technologies should adapt to continue their functioning, although some capabilities could be lost. Nevertheless, the communication could be completely lost, and other technologies could solve these unusual limitations.

6.2.1.2. Difficult emergency areas: network adaptability

OP4.2-6: Use of UAVs for coverage extension in areas of difficult access or poor coverage and

OP4.2-7: Use of balloons to create communication routes in rural or poor coverage areas.

Series of mobile elements could be deployed to create a significant coverage radius and create a gateway to the satellite. These elements are usually vehicles such as vans or cars, however, in places where that allows connections to the outside. Thanks to this wired connection, connect an antenna located in the emergency center to connect to the users' devices and link it to an external antenna that allows output to the network.

Although the outdoor use of radio frequencies (RF) for communication has been a well-established and convenient technique for a quite long time, in areas with no robust network infrastructures to ensure sufficient coverage or indoor environments, RF signals may not be used to be the most appropriate solution. On the one hand, there may not be base stations that allow communication between entities involved in data transmission. On the other hand, the characterization scenario may not allow RF to work well due to attenuation, reflection, refraction, diffraction, and scattering that have a negative effect on RF signals.

Rock absorbs the frequencies we normally use for radio communication. This means that our phones, walkie-talkies, and other equipment cannot be used. However, the low-frequency magnetic field from 1 to 100 kHz can be used for communications. For example, 32 kHz and 87 kHz have been commonly used. Communication is usually possible over several hundred meters of rock. For example, in caves, obstacles such as walls, rocks, and curvatures with rough surfaces amplify the adverse effects of the above distortions on RF signals, making wireless voice communication especially difficult.

Nowadays, there are tools used for safety and rescue purposes to inform those waiting on the ground about the progress of an exploration party. The party can indicate whether it is proceeding according to plan, is behind schedule, or needs help. And if there is an emergency, knowing the location of cavers is essential.

There are different types of cable-based systems used for communication when there is insufficient wireless coverage. One is known as a single-wire telephone (SWT). SWT, also known as ground return telephone, uses the conductivity of the ground to provide a return path for the current. In some scenarios, coaxial cables such as single copper core cables become bulky and heavy, especially as the cable length increases.

Therefore, more weight-efficient solutions are preferred for communication inside caves. One such solution is the use of optical fibers, weighing less, which have higher bandwidth and noise immunity than copper cables, which tend to pick up random noise from the environment when cable lengths are longer. Although the problems of cable noise and weight can be compensated using optical fibers, there are still problems associated with installing these cable-based communication networks in some scenarios, such as caves or mines. For example, multi-path caves require cables to be split into multiple branches, with each branch requiring a connection to the main cable. These connections can be made relatively easily with copper cables, but each new connection has a negative effect on communication quality.

From the RF perspective, there are also so-called Through-the-Earth (TTE) signaling solutions. These solutions offer a type of radio signaling used in mines and caves that uses low-frequency waves to penetrate the earth and rock, which are opaque to conventional higher frequency radio signals. In emergency areas with no wireless coverage, these signals can propagate at low frequencies underground or infrastructures through the various antenna, repeater, or mesh configurations, but communication is restricted to the line-of-sight of these antenna and repeater systems.

6.2.2. Communication and data Integration towards interoperability

OP4.2-8: Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted.

The difference network performances and the routing of the data, according to the network's delivery capability and the data priorities have to be managed and bridged between the networks implemented to transfer data from one network to the other, converting data protocols, and establish a common reference networks protocol, such as IP.

OP4.2-9: Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency.

To integrate the different communication solutions, provided by the many First Responders from different countries involved in emergency/disaster response, in a federated/joint solution, the networks must be balanced, managed and data converted in order achieve a minimum interoperability between them.

OP4.2-20: Victims and FR data gathering.

Wearable's sensors can collect victims and FR health data via Bluetooth and transmit them the network, thought a gateway to account for the different network technologies, and push the date to the same protocol as the remaining federation of assets and applications.

OP4.2-21: Bridge between network and OP4.2-23: Gateway.

To enable a wider network coverage, and overcome networks differences between entities, a bridge between the different networks can be used to interconnect the networks at specific nodes, enabling the different communication Technologies and networks to complement and provide a wider coverage.

Combined with the bridge between the networks, the gateway can provide multiprotocol transfer and translation, implementing the data protocol that, in the case of VALKYRIES, could be an harmonized reference data protocol.

OP4.2-24: IP LAYER.

To enable an easier interoperability of the data exchange, the same common network distribution protocol can be used, combined with the gateways to set the reference data exchanged at the IP layer. Enabling each entity / application joining the federated network to exchange data with other applications.

OP4.2-26: Data Conversion.

The data conversion could be a pool of service that enables an application in the federation to request a conversion of its data produced or consumed (which can be from a data format, a sensors data structure or format, taxonomies, a language conversion, etc), so that other application can consume and correctly interpreter the data.

OP4.2-25: Data Priority.

Use gateways functions and applications rules, to implement data priority models according to the needs established by the Command Centre. The data transfer, once all work in the same IP layer, is to by using SLA and QoS, to ensure data transfer end-to-end. The data priority is established by the producer and o transfer model handles the data package according to the priority. in the absence of other ruling the FIFO is the default data priority model.

OP4.2-35: Querying data.

Use of MQTT protocol, combined with the RestFul, to integrate data sources and data gathering within the SIGRUN sources. The MQTT acts as a distributor of the data an application produces, and delivers to the consumer that requests it.

OP4.2-34: Shared Health data

Explore the potential use of EHR to exchange data between medial services. EHR services can be set as an external source and, when queried with the correct credentials, makes available health records of the victim, if available.

OP.4.2-38: Sectorization

Faced with increasing demand, many EMS in business-as-usual situations use sectorisation to divide the workload. In large cities such as Madrid, an Emergency Coordination Centre such as 112, not only sectorises by type of demand (security, rescue and fire, health), but also by geographical areas in the case of health emergency calls. The experience gained after the explosion of COVID-19 cases during the first wave showed that segregating calls with a "fever" or "respiratory illness" consultation reason facilitated the offloading of 112 and the application of specialised protocols for the group in charge of handling these calls. In the event that a multi-casualty incident is declared, the ability to segregate all calls accessing the system from the

geographical area where the disaster is occurring allows a specialised team to handle them, without interfering with the normal operation of the rest of the calls.

OP4.2-39. Network access limitation

It is known that there is a possibility to limit access to the network for certain types of protocols or subscribers. It is also known that nowadays, a large part of the Internet bandwidth is consumed by streaming services. Here, we propose that in the event of a catastrophic situation and network saturation, methods be put in place to limit access (at least during times of greatest need for first responders) to the network by subscriber and by type of streamed traffic. Telephone companies may have a list of subscribers listed as "first responders" and enable a limitation for all other subscribers at times of peak network saturation.

OP4.2-40. Specific terminals for disasters

It is essential to have all the necessary equipment available for a disaster before it happens. This requires a specific stock of dedicated equipment for first responders. This equipment, if not used, has to be checked and replaced at regular intervals. In the case of terminals, due to their high cost, this rule is not always complied with. We therefore propose to establish a specific stock of terminals for use in disasters, to be renewed every two years, and to be used for each of the drills. During these drills, the capacity of the terminals, their operability and their deterioration should be assessed. If necessary, their replacement should be proposed. These terminals should be different from those used in the usual activity of the first responders, or should allow for simple programming that drastically facilitates their use in disaster situations (e.g. by means of an emergency button or key combination).

6.2.3. Extending area coverage of communications

OP4.2-19: Extend IOT data range.

Communication coverage are limited by the radio power, antenna, line of sight, altitude tx-rx, frequency used, obstacles, etc. While some overcomes the range by increasing power, which is limited by the available power and antenna, others use relays or establish a grid of connection/access points supported by a backbone infrastructure. In many cases the full network is not available or can be seriously degraded. In other cases, natural obstacles limit the communication Range far below the Line-of-Sight range. Possible option for IOT extended range is the LoRA Network.

Other options could be the use mobile, land or air, relay stations, providing a local network capability, increase the communication data throughput.

OP4.2-22 Increase RF area coverage.

In more recent technologies approaches drones equipped with relays can provide a fast and easy deployable solution to overcome the terrain communication obstacles or just extend the coverage area.

Specialized communications equipment, such as satellite phones and ultra-high frequency radios, have been a mainstay of disaster management communications systems in recent years (43). In addition, the use of Cell on Wheels (COW) cell phone towers is common as a temporary solution to quickly resume mobile services in the most affected regions (see Figure 10). Along the same lines, UAVs can be a good option to extend coverage in those areas with difficult terrestrial access (see Figure 11 and Figure 12). With these two approaches, scenarios emerge that maintain a hybrid approach such as, where both complement each other to create a disaster resilient architecture. In addition to professionally trained users, there is an important community of radio amateurs who can operate these emergency communication systems when traditional telephone and data transmission systems are not available.

Figure 10 - Example of system to extend coverage in multiple casualty scenarios: Cell on Wheels (CoW).

Figure 11 - Example of system to extend coverage in multiple casualty scenarios: drones equipped with antennas.

Figure 12 - Deployment of CoW and drones for coverage extension in emergency areas (45).

6.2.4. Resiliency of communication infrastructure

OP4.2-12: Improve intercommunication between technologies.

Enhanced cooperation including formalized agreements and frameworks between the telecommunications sector and national disaster offices is necessary for more effective disaster response and recovery operations.

Current telecommunications infrastructure is extremely vulnerable to disaster impacts, such as flooding, landslides, and high winds. This is compounded by aging infrastructure, poor maintenance, and reinforcement as well as the location of critical telecommunications infrastructure in hazard prone areas.

Efforts should therefore be intensified to ensure the resilience of telecommunications infrastructure given the invaluable support they provide in post-disaster situations by facilitating communication, coordination, and intelligence collection.

6.2.5. System redundancy

OP4.2-14: Definition of backup guidelines at EU level.

The lack of regulations at EU level indicating in a clear way how backup plans should be managed in emergency agencies opens the door for great improvement. Thus, clear guidelines could be provided to emergency institutions to clearly state how to store information in the way that it cannot be lost in case of adverse situations, human errors or even cyberattacks. For example, one of the possibilities could be to enforce the implantation of physical redundancy in data storage, ensuring that data is replicated in two or more physically separated facilities.

OP4.2-15: Creation of data restoration contingency plans.

In a similar way to the previous opportunity, the lack of regulations and recommendations at EU level regarding data loss is a big opportunity for improvement in emergency scenarios. In this

direction, EU guidelines and contingency plans could be of much value, clearly defining procedures to recover data and, thus, ensuring the continuity of

OP4.2-16: Deployment of redundant services to provide back-up support in case of failure.

To improve the redundancy of the solution to be used in the operational scenario of emergency and disaster events, a strategy of data decentralization and alternatives communication solutions can be used. As different communications technologies are used by different entities, they can be used to set-up redundancy of the communication, by connecting them through gateways. Thus, in case of a network congestion or communication loss, alternative routing of the data can be used to deliver to the users. Based on this situation, the EU could provide recommendations and guidelines for deploying auxiliary systems in emergency scenarios to ensure the availability of resources.

OP4.2-17: Developing national ad hoc emergency networks.

The creation of ad hoc national networks for emergency services (e.g., in Portugal, Ireland or Denmark) would help to ensure interoperability between the different emergency services.

OP4.2-18: Leveraging 5G networks.

The 5G network could provide an affordable, stable, and low-latency communications solution for autonomous and teleoperated vehicles and human intervention teams. In addition, functionalities such as Network slicing could guarantee quality of service in crowded environments and ensure the confidentiality of a particularly critical network.

In emergency situations, first responders must have the necessary tools to be able to respond quickly, which implies increased network capacity in difficult conditions and when the general population may also demand the need for connectivity.

In this situation, 5G technology offers significant advantages for the public safety sector:

- Network availability in all possible emergency situations, also in harsh environments.
- Network Slicing: virtual layers can be created on the same physical network allowing different use cases to be realised depending on their characteristics. This allows public safety agencies to dynamically optimise network functions such as speed, capacity, coverage and connectivity.
- Network virtualisation and service-based architecture: bringing data processing resources as close as possible to the end-user device.
- Low latency for data exchange: Ultra-reliable low latency communication (uRLLC).
- Support of a large number of connected devices that can communicate with each other, exchange data and enable process automation: IoT.
- Higher quality voice communication.
- Secure authentication and information protection by having a service fully isolated and protected from other services, reducing the possibility of external attacks.

Deploying new 5G telephony networks to their full extent is costly for telecom operators, but this cost would not be specifically borne by the emergency services. On the other hand, in 5G, telephony-specific hardware is no longer used in favour of general-purpose equipment, which represents an advantage in terms of cost and deployment flexibility, and also makes the infrastructure interoperable and accessible by equipment on the internet. Furthermore, the use of commercial telephony networks offers the possibility of a wide range of terminals with easy availability, high performance, constant upgrades and lower costs.

OP4.2-27: Communications redundancy and OP4.2-28 GATEWAYS network redundancy.

Establish a redundant communications solution by integrating different networks and communication solutions into a common communications framework enables multiple communication paths between different applications in the network. As the number of networks increases the more redundant paths are available to route the data from data producers to data consumers.

The adaptability and agility of having multiple networks can be managed by using Software Defined Networking (SDN), thus optimizing the data transfers. To account for the Quality of Service or Service Level agreement required and balance the processing charge, clustering of the data can be used, which natively provides redundancy of the data services. To complement the redundancy, a backup strategy based on Blockchain, for shared metadata and transactional data is used, while non-transactional files and stream data can be backed up by a network of server nodes.

In the same way, Blockchain smart contracts can help when coming to creating backups and setting up new methods for communication. Being a decentralised database, blockchain information can be accessed at any given point and no data will be altered. By defining the right way to store this data, we can retrieve backup from communications that occurred and set up new models by making use of the full potential of blockchain.

OP4.2-29: Data cluster.

By using data clusters in VALKYRIES interoperability model, it allows for a higher redundancy, increase SLA and QoS performance and higher services availability.

OP4.2-30: Data backup.

Data backup is used to ensure the recovery in case of damage or loss of the information during the events. Although a recovery plan during the event is of reduced applicability as the time elapses the data validity reduces. However, to improve the data redundancy, it should be included the backup capability functions. The backup can be done in specific network nodes, but local connection should have a minimum backup capability in case of temporary connection loss and requires to recover of the last available data after the reconnection.

OP4.2-33: Data backup servers.

Use of backup servers for the non-transaction and streaming data. Transactional data is stored natively by blockchain network, but non transactional and large files / streams should be stored in dedicated server for later recovery.

OP4.2-32: BlockChain redundancy.

Use of Blockchain as a backup of transactional data and all the metadata generated by the federation.

OP4.2-31: APPS/Functions redundancy.

The federation does not establish a specific function provider, as multiple applications can provide the same function. Is it up to the consumer to establish which data to consume. As there are multiple applications that can provide the same function, when an application that provides a specific function is removed from the network, or becomes unavailable due to network connectivity issues, other application that provides the same function can replace the previous one.

6.2.6. Optimal confidentiality

OP4.2-10: Unified regulations for data protection in emergency scenarios.

The absence of secure communications to ensure the privacy of the data transmitted in certain emergency services could be improved by defining unified regulations for data protection at EU level. Thus, first responder agencies would require adopting these regulations and, thus, ensure that data transmissions are performed in a secure way, preserving the confidentiality of the information exchanged.

OP4.2-11: Use of monitoring technologies or services capable of detecting threats that may affect the network.

Since communications networks and technological architectures in emergency scenarios do not implement monitoring systems able to detect threats against the infrastructure, there is a great opportunity for improvement from a technological point of view. In particular, the alternatives such as honey pots, or security information and event management strategies, aim to identify attacks over the elements composing the network and, thus, perform actions to benefit the integrity of the network. Based on the knowledge acquired from the attacks, the network can then perform actions to reduce or mitigate the impact caused by these malicious entities.

OP4.2-13: Used of technologies based on security constraints.

To efficiently control the data access and confidentiality during first aid actuations in order to provide enough confidentiality to the personal and sensitive data, it is possible to use light and precise confidentiality mechanisms. In this sense, two main opportunities have been identified.

6.2.7. Standards and protocols

OP4.2-36: Light cryptographic protocols.

The use of light cryptographic protocols reduces the computing time and computing requirements.

OP4.2-37: RBAC/ABAC.

The use of RBAC will atomize data access which will allow optimal control.

OP4.2-41 Standard training in device use.

Being based on the standards to carry out the acquisition of technological training guarantees optimal results for your organization and coordination, streamlining all decision-making. This is a benefit for the optimization of human resources with significant savings in training, since it is considered that all members will benefit from standardized training in the use of devices, skills, communications, among others.

The use of approved technological, organizational and emergency nomenclatures in a standard allows optimal communication to all those who implement it. The implementation of consolidation levels will allow the sharing of resources and their dynamic management on a temporary basis.

This training must be related and adapted according to the level of use and responsibility of each user. Technological tools require a period of adaptation and simulation to be used correctly and to generate and receive the information and data to be managed.

OP4.2-42 Standard capabilities of emergency devices.

Devices, equipment and infrastructure must be designed under recognized standards, with special emphasis on determining the minimum requirements necessary for all countries to adhere to whatever the hierarchical level of their infrastructure and possibilities, although it is true that the minimum requirements would cover the basic functionality and the deployment of a complete functionality would be in accordance with the desired requirements of the infrastructure, taking into account that the information generated and distributed must be consolidated in any case.

The maturity in the consolidation of the infrastructure and training allows an improvement in the relations between private entities and public organizations since a business opportunity is opened to companies interested in the areas within the scope of the VALKYRIES use cases, indirectly providing added value to the unity of the European Union and its professionals.

Table 22 summarizes all the opportunities identified over “Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals”. For each opportunity, a traceability identifier is provided in the text, the gap to which it is related, the opportunity name, the justification for its inclusion, and the partner that detects it.

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-1	G4.2-2 G4.2-8 G4.2-34 G4.2-42	Use of alternative communication systems	First responder agencies could use alternative communication systems in case of a system or network failure.
OP4.2-2	G4.2-1 G4.2-27 G4.3-6 G4.3-10	Extend network coverage	The different countries could improve the network coverage of the most used communication technologies to improve current coverage limitations.
OP4.2-3	G4.2-2 G4.3-5	Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture	The VALKYRIES project identifies the adaptability of network technologies in the face of environmental adversities, with communications being fundamental to the transmission of critical data.
OP4.2-4	G4.2-3 G4.3-5 G4.3-6 G4.3-10	Use of technologies that favour the extension of coverage to devices with fewer resources	The use of technologies that create wide coverage ranges favours the connection and, therefore, the transmissions of constrained devices.
OP4.2-5	G4.2-3 G4.2-18 G4.3-6 G4.3-10	Use of mobile technologies to facilitate service delivery	Due to environmental adversities, the use of miniaturized cell phone technology, commonly known as decode-and-forward relays, can extend the coverage of mobile services to include hard-to-reach areas. This approach enables transmissions to large crowds, such as in relief camp settings, hard-to-reach urban areas, or rural locations where ground transportation has been disrupted.
OP4.2-6	G4.2-3	Use of UAVs for coverage extension in areas of difficult access or poor coverage	Emergency areas may be in poor coverage or difficult to access locations, the use of devices that can extend existing coverage is critical to the interoperability of VALKYRIES.
OP4.2-7	G4.2-3	Use of balloons to create communication routes in rural or poor coverage areas	Sometimes emergencies occur in remote locations or where a robust communications architecture does not exist, therefore, deploying devices that meet the needs of a fixed network architecture is necessary.
OP4.2-8	G4.2-4	Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted	The selection of technologies must be made depending on the type of data to be transmitted, being critical the relevant and indispensable information for the emergency.

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-9	G4.2-5 G4.3-5	Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency	It is necessary to ensure that data transmissions over the communications networks are preferential to favour the exchange of data to devices operated by first responders and not by other entities (e.g., curious citizens, nearby personal vehicles, commercial radio stations, etc.).
OP4.2-10	G4.2-6 G4.3-30 G4.4-14	Unified regulations for data protection in emergency scenarios	There is an opportunity for a homogenised regulation regarding securitization of communications in emergency scenarios at EU level.
OP4.2-11	G4.2-7	Use of monitoring technologies or services capable of detecting threats that may affect the network	There is an opportunity for substantial improvement in network security by using active and passive monitoring systems capable of detecting threats to assets in real time.
OP4.2-12	G4.2-8	Improve intercommunication between technologies	There is room for standardisation work regarding interconnection of different technologies to allow changing easily between technologies.
OP4.2-13	G4.2-9	Use of technologies based on security constraints	EU regulations could focus on providing clear guidelines regarding which technologies or protocols are more suitable according to data security constraints in each scenario, also according to the ethical legal framework
OP4.2-14	G4.2-10	Definition of backup guidelines at EU level	There is an opportunity for defining and implanting strict backup regulations enforcing emergency institutions to store sensitive data with redundancy to avoid information loss.
OP4.2-15	G4.2-11	Creation of data restoration contingency plans	The EU could design and implement recommendations or guidelines on how to proceed for data restoration in case of incidents.
OP4.2-16	G4.2-12	Deployment of redundant services to provide back-up support in case of failure	The EU could provide recommendations for the deployment of auxiliary systems in multiple casualty scenarios.

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-17	G4.2-13 G4.2-16	Developing national ad hoc emergency networks	The creation of ad hoc national networks for emergency services (e.g., in Portugal, Ireland or Denmark) would help to ensure interoperability between the different emergency services.
OP4.2-18	G4.2-17 G4.2-18 G4.3-5	Leveraging 5G networks	The 5G network could provide an affordable, stable, and low-latency communications solution for autonomous and teleoperated vehicles and human intervention teams. In addition, functionalities such as Network Slicing could guarantee quality of service in crowded environments and ensure the confidentiality of a particularly critical network.
OP4.2-19	G4.2-24	Extend IOT data range	Long range local data gathering using Lora Network.
OP4.2-20	G4.2-25	Victims and FR data gathering	Wearable's sensors can collect victims and FR health data via Bluetooth and transmit them the network.
OP4.2-21	G4.2-26 G4.3-6 G4.3-10	Bridge between networks	To enable a wider network coverage, and overcome networks differences between entities, a gateway/bridge approach can be used to interconnect different networks and jointly cover a wider area.
OP4.2-22	G4.2-27	Increase RF area coverage	Use of drones with communications relay payload to increase the coverage of the FR communications.
OP4.2-23	G4.2-28 G4.2-29 G4.2-31	GATEWAY	To establish the connectivity bridge between different networks and translate from one network protocol to another network.
OP4.2-24	G4.2-32	IP LAYER	Establish IP layer as the reference network protocol for all the entities and communication that want to share data, within SIGRUN, to communication at IP level.
OP4.2-25	G4.2-30	Data Priority	Use gateways functions to implement the data priority established by the Command Centre, by using SLA and QoS, to ensure data transfer end-to-end based on the data prioritization.
OP4.2-26	G4.2-33	Data Conversion	APIs used by the SIGRUN, and the GATEWAYS provide the function to convert data formats, taxonomy, language, etc, between the application

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			to the SIGRUN refence established or other agreed by the entities.
OP4.2-27	G4.2-34	Communications redundancy	Establish a redundant communications solution by integrating different networks and communication solutions into a common communications framework and architecture that enables bridging and multiple paths between different networks.
OP4.2-28	G4.2-34	GATEWAYS networks	By having gateways between different networks increases the redundancy by adding alternative so the communications.
OP4.2-29	G4.2-35 G4.3-5	Data cluster	Data servers aggregated in clusters enables a higher redundancy, increase SLA and QoS performance and higher services availability.
OP4.2-30	G4.2-35	Data Backup	To improve the data redundancy, it should include data backup capability.
OP4.2-31	G4.2-36	APPS/Functions redundancy	An application agnostic federated system with the data status distributed enables a system function redundancy, in case of a function unavailable, other application can be deployed.
OP4.2-32	G4.2-37	Block Chain redundancy	Use the Blockchain networks to store shared metadata and transactional data.
OP4.2-33	G4.2-35	Data backup servers	Use of backup servers for the non-transaction and streaming data to add additional non-real time redundancy capability.
OP.4.2-34	G4.2-38	Shared Health data	Explore the potential use of EHR to exchange data between medial services.
OP4.2-35	G4.2-39	Querying data	Use of MQTT protocol to integrate data sources and data gathering within the SIGRUN sources.
OP4.2-36	G4.2-14 G4.2-15	Light cryptographic protocols	The use of light cryptographic protocols reduces the computing time and computing requirements.
OP4.2-37	G4.2-14 G4.2-15	RBAC/ABAC	The use or RBAC will atomize the data access which will allow to optimal control.
OP4.2-38	G4.2-20	Sectorization	Division or sectorization of incoming information.
OP4.2-39	G4.2-21 G4.2-41	Access limitation	Limit network access and type of communication to a certain group of subscribers.
OP4.2-40	G4.2-22	Specific terminals for disasters	Either purchase or program existing terminals for unattended and simple use.

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-41	G4.2-19	Standard training in device use	Implementation of training standards and use of devices.
OP4.2-42	G4.2-23	Standard capabilities of emergency devices	Implementation of device technical requirements standards.

Table 22 - Opportunities from Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals.

6.3. Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies

6.3.1. Dangerous Zones, Number of Victims, FR Information, CBRNE and Relevant locations

Functional C2 ecosystem relies on capacity towards being able to asset through decision superiority. New C2 applications technologies such as Virtual Reality, Public publish content, Artificial Intelligence aims to predict fast-changing environments among many others provide robust and complete solutions. A complete situational awareness picture is provided by storage of significant data. It should be noted that the location where the events of the catastrophe occurred must be stored.

OP4.3-1: Virtual reality debriefing systems.

In last decade, AR and VR have become very popular and multiple fields of research have been opened, due to the release of mobile hardware and software that have become affordable and are quite mature to develop custom applications.

There is a growing interest in improving the design and ability to integrate a human in the loop command and control for robot control. For this, human factors such as trust, stress and situational awareness of the operation must be taken into account.

Another field that can benefit from VR control scenarios development is UAVs, in handling and training aspects. Full immersion for high-quality three-dimensional space should enhance the characteristics of 3D and 2D map display models.

VR has also been used to test and measure the efficiency of existing or innovative security systems. Studies and work have been carried out on disasters based on fires in buildings, tunnels and underground fires, where the effectiveness of emergency evacuation routes, exit signs and other orientation systems were measured.

In terms of teaching and training, education has changed in terms of approaches and applied techniques. Students feel comfortable with online education and using the internet to find content. An immersive environment allows students to be fully immersed in a self-contained artificial or simulated environment while experiencing it as real, offering students rich and complex experiences that help hone their technical, creative, and problem-solving skills. The need for disaster management training is expected to grow in the next decade due to climate

change. Specialists can gain invaluable experience from VR environments where different disaster scenarios can be simulated and personnel trained to respond in critical situations. Such training can be tailored to specific users, or organizations based on resources, and vulnerability analysis. Training programs can be created with task-focused instructions where the program generates instant feedback. These trainings allow evaluating emergency plans and identifying gaps and areas for improvement.

OP4.3-3: Location of near/nearest vehicles.

Vehicle Tracking (VT) is becoming the core item for an intelligent vehicle fleet system. GPS system (Global Positioning System) is the vehicle fleet tracking system, which uses technologies such as the General Packet Radio Service (GPRS), Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM) or the Internet itself or the World Wide Web.

One of the main problems that can arise in a collaboration scenario between emergency services is the difficulty in being effective by coordinating their fleet of vehicles and mobile assets to manage the incident. The lack of a mechanism to share this information and achieve greater efficiency in the use of available assets creates a great opportunity to improve the technological mechanisms involved.

The fleet management systems of the different agencies that are going to intervene jointly in a disaster have the opportunity to implement an integration service that implements a standard that allows sharing the data of their assets and the location of said assets with other agencies, through standard mechanisms not dependent on the technology used.

There are mechanisms and standards already implemented that could be useful in this opportunity:

- Fleet Management System (FMS) is a standard interface for industrial vehicle data, managing vehicle fleets efficiently through intelligent resource allocation. It implements functionalities such as vehicle location, tracking, routing, shipping, and on-board information. The data is encoded according to the SAE (Society of Automotive Engineers) J1939 standard followed by brands such as Hyundai, MAN AG, Volvo, Renault, Scania, etc.
- Fleet Engine API from Google, allows modeling vehicle fleet activities. This API is exposed through an SDJ and can be used directly through HTTP REST calls. This API complements Google Cloud services, Kubernetes, and Kibana Fleet APIs for the data visualization front-end.
- AWS IoT FleetWise from Amazon collects, transforms, and transfers vehicle data to the cloud in real time. This uploaded data can be used to analyze the state of the fleet, identify problems and use data in Machine Learning models.

OP4.3-4: Georeferenced recording of events on the ground.

Regarding relevant locations, an opportunity for improvement consists in unifying the technological solutions used for this purpose.

Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) brings together a group of public and private organizations to reach standardization agreements that enable interoperation in geoprocessing systems and facilitate the exchange of georeferenced geographic information. It offers open standards for online geospatial development software that offers data services. Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) is used to represent all the components that allow access to spatial data. Using electronic media, SDI connect distributed geospatial information repositories through a single entry point called a “geoportal”, making it easy for users to provide information for the discovery, evaluation and application of spatial data in different sectors. Global Spatial Data Infrastructure (GSDI) Association links national SDIs to establish connections so that all users around the world can share and reuse available data sets.

It's also worth noting, there are ISO standards (International Standardization Organization) to take into account for the standardization of information:

- ISO 19107, Geographic information — Spatial schema.
- ISO 19111, Geographic information — Spatial referencing by coordinates.
- ISO 19136, Geographic information — Geography Markup Language.
- ISO 19136-2, Geographic information — Geography Markup Language - Extended schemas and encoding rules.
- ISO 19148, Geographic information — Linear referencing
- ISO 15926-3, Information Technology – Database languages – SQL multimedia and application packages – Part 3: Spatial

Eurostat and the European Commission have a service called Geographical Information System of the Commission (GISCO) that covers the needs for geographical information at the level of the EU, its member states and regions. GISCO database contains core geographical data for all of Europe such as administrative boundaries, roads, hydrography, ports and airports, digital elevation model, population distribution, land cover and land use information, and more.

OP4.3-25: Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones.

It should be recommended that members of EU establish some procedures to allow identifying those zones which are a danger. In addition, a dangerous zone can be defined as any location where there is any kind of risk. However, every dangerous area is different, and each has specific requirements depending on the nature of the atmosphere and the elements that are present.

OP4.3-26: Identification of relevant locations.

In addition to OP4.3-23, there is the need to identify important locations in emergency scenarios. For that, members of EU could define and unified technologies that allow recognizing new relevant locations.

6.3.2. Standards

OP4.3-28: Creation of operating procedures.

The standards are created and improved by the various technical committees, mentioned above, and receive regular updates that have their origin in continuous improvement, responding to the needs and requirements of different sources, such as technology and new areas in development, for example Command and Control. The adoption of standards or the creation of new ones, based on current standards, results in their implementation and deployment at all levels, from decision-making or strategic levels to field or operational teams, in a consolidated manner.

OP4.3-29: Incorporation of new standards.

From VALKYRIES, an emergency response service is pursued in border areas with the goal of the best security response for citizens. Therefore, it is necessary to generate operational procedures based on these standards. The equipment and devices must especially comply with security standards since the integrity of the technology in adverse circumstances becomes critical since it is related to the participation of state security and/or health bodies and other private organizations; without downplaying the importance of the protection of information and data outside or within an emergency scenario. These standards also try to cover the needs for the protection of information, in the case of information of high importance since it may be related to national security resources and confidential information of the citizens of the different countries.

With this, an excellent level of security, confidentiality, and consistency is sought at a technological and resource level with the implementation of the most demanding standards and in a uniform manner for all countries, creating an international security network that can exceed current levels.

6.3.3. Sources of Information

OP4.3-6: Health and Usage Monitoring Systems (HUMS).

The sources of information that can be explored by the system in MCI Disaster /Emergency events, present a wide range of opportunities, and can be expanded in the support of more communications capabilities. Data provided from in-filed sensors, such as deployable sensors / IOT sensors can provide local ground and air information which provides awareness to the end-users of the situation in the field. Another great opportunity refers to data from victims and FR that can be gathered by using wearables to monitor their health status (Temperature, heart rate, etc.) and location. This greatly improves the ability of the command to better manage the distribution of the FR forces in the terrain while increase their safety. FR and Victims can also explore their smartphones capabilities to provide in-filed local data video, photos and audio, contributing to a better understanding of the multiple situations faced by FR.

On wider areas, or in cases where air view provides an improved situation awareness, technologies such as drones equipped with multiple sensors and the data extracted from their

sensors data enable a tactical understanding of the terrain situation, helps command centre to establish tactical approach to the situation. This information can also be complemented by a number of other data sources, from CCTV a TV broadcast network, which are already used by the civil protection entities.

In addition to the data provided by the FR information sources, there are wide number of external data services to incorporate in the response, some are already used, such as weather forecast or satellite imagery/data such as Copernicus, but new opportunities are available such as terrain data models, networks of commercial IOT sensors, etc.

HUMS provides a better and accessible safety guarantee for FR. Is able to recap measures of their system/device and reduce cost through efficient equipment maintenance. Several benefits associate such as less mission aborts, reduction of maintenance or even optimize testing phase.

OP4.3-7: Asset's responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios.

Acronym VUCA stands for volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity, giving meaning to an increasingly unstable and rapidly changing scenario,

Changes in circumstances require innovation to develop strategy and operations and respond appropriately to new challenges. It is necessary to correctly understand the circumstances so as not to misinterpret them and be prepared to avoid developing strategies based on the wrong scenario and go in the wrong direction.

This justifies the need to examine and understand the differences between the four VUCA concepts.

Table 1. Distinctions within the VUCA framework

	What it is	An example	How to effectively address it
Volatility	Relatively unstable change; information is available and the situation is understandable, but change is frequent and sometimes unpredictable.	Commodity pricing is often quite volatile; jet fuel costs, for instance, have been quite volatile in the 21 st century.	Agility is key to coping with volatility. Resources should be aggressively directed toward building slack and creating the potential for future flexibility.
Uncertainty	A lack of knowledge as to whether an event will have meaningful ramifications; cause and effect are understood, but it is unknown if an event will create significant change.	Anti-terrorism initiatives are generally plagued with uncertainty; we understand many causes of terrorism, but not exactly when and how they could spur attacks.	Information is critical to reducing uncertainty. Firms should move beyond existing information sources to both gather new data and consider it from new perspectives.
Complexity	Many interconnected parts forming an elaborate network of information and procedures; often multiform and convoluted, but not necessarily involving change.	Moving into foreign markets is frequently complex; doing business in new countries often involves navigating a complex web of tariffs, laws, regulations, and logistics issues.	Restructuring internal company operations to match the external complexity is the most effective and efficient way to address it. Firms should attempt to 'match' their own operations and processes to mirror environmental complexities.
Ambiguity	A lack of knowledge as to 'the basic rules of the game'; cause and effect are not understood and there is no precedent for making predictions as to what to expect.	The transition from print to digital media has been very ambiguous; companies are still learning how customers will access and experience data and entertainment given new technologies.	Experimentation is necessary for reducing ambiguity. Only through intelligent experimentation can firm leaders determine what strategies are and are not beneficial in situations where the former rules of business no longer apply.

Figure 13 – Distinctions within the VUCA framework (What VUCA really means for you - Bennet y Lemoine, 2014 - <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263926940>)

In the figure below these fields are ranked according to the predictability of the results and the availability of the data.

Figure 14 – VUCA challenges and responses (Approaching VUCA Environment with Enterprise Agility in Government Organization – Emmi Kuusisto, 2022 - <https://osuva.uwasa.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/14079/Emmi%20Kuusisto-Master's%20thesis.pdf>)

Decision making becomes a fundamental part in this VUCA environment for problem solving. The decision-making capacity is based on data, whether structured or unstructured, that is correct, precise and of quality. Under this premise, Big Data helps and increases the quality of decision-making by correlating various factors such as data sources, and performing analyses, and taking into account the resources and skills of the people involved in the processes. This is all about data security and data collection methods.

OP4.3-8: Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) can improve our ability to strengthen natural disaster management and reduce the risk of such disasters occurring. In other fields such as finance or medicine, AI has gained momentum due to advances in the development of algorithms, processing power and the availability of huge sources of data.

AI has the potential to accelerate our understanding of natural hazards by analyzing large volumes of data and images from different sources and enhancing proactive rather than reactive actions for disaster risk reduction.

It is expected that vast amounts of geospatial data can be managed to help improve our situational awareness of natural disasters, improve forecast accuracy, and improve communications efficiency. AI methods offer new opportunities related to applications in the pre-processing of observational data as well as in the post-processing of forecast model output.

Procedures for collecting sensor data from topographically complex regions and with large spatiotemporal resolutions have been improved. They have served to improve probabilistic scenarios for exposure to floods or avalanches, tsunami amplitudes or earthquake triggers. There are ML approaches that are being used to improve warning and early warning systems and to help generate hazard and susceptibility maps through ML driven detection and forecasting of various types of natural hazards.

To avoid biases in collection and handling of data, it is necessary there is a significant sample so that the data has a sufficient representation of the pattern of the problems to be solved. These data are limited since, due to the rarity of these events that generate disasters, the samples can generate incorrect predictions or biased results. Because AI relies on complex machine learning algorithms to stream data and compute, centralized data processing and management can be a challenge as real-time disaster applications, and ML requires training data is fused on data servers. Data sharing between countries needs strong partnerships as well as building trust with end users to comply with GDPR regulations.

A group of experts and stakeholders has been created to explore current practices and uses of AI for natural disaster management: Focus Group on AI for Natural Disaster Management (FG-AI4NDM). It brings together the information and communication technology expertise of International Telecommunication Union (ITU) with the natural hazard and disaster expertise of World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). They are intended to help with data collection and management, improve modeling across spatiotemporal scales, and provide effective communication.

OP4.3-9: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.

Knowledge and understanding that guide expert decisions come from a broad understanding of the history of events, that is, learning from the past. However, intuition and experience tell us the opposite, because no two disasters are the same.

Even so, expert opinions always continue to guide management decisions and resource allocation. Mapping data is the key element for rescue operations, but it must be interpreted effectively. Therefore, the role that predictive analytics is beginning to play is crucial, helping to calculate potential risks and develop better plans for disaster management.

Generated models and quantitative methods focus on separating the causal factors that cause a disaster, from those that simply appear by chance or bad luck, with the aim of evaluating the

risk of the danger and damage that can be generated, and in this way be able to more adequately dimension the management of resources.

Predictive analytics takes a multi-layered approach to data mapping, as many dangerous elements need to be considered, and neglecting one can lead to fatality. Geographical data must be combined, with real-time image, reconnaissance and verified checks, telephone calls and data provided by mobile operators, data from remote sensors, satellite images, etc.

OP4.3-10: Social network data visualization on C2.

Regarding social media data acquisition, there is a clear opportunity for using data acquisition tools on different social media formats, such as social networks or forums, as they are not widely used at EU level by emergency institutions and their data could provide a better understanding of the global situation.

OP4.3-14: Guidelines for social media crawling.

Based on the opportunity OP4.3-10, there is an opportunity for EU members to develop guidelines and strategies for these tasks.

OP4.3-15: Guidelines for selecting social media crawling tools.

We identify an opportunity regarding data acquisition tools and technologies used for social media data acquisition. In this sense, EU members could unify which approaches are better according to the type of resources to be queried.

OP4.3-16: Drones' imagery data.

An opportunity is the automation of multiple sensors streams collected from drones' platforms (air, land or other). Optimize the deployment of drones' platforms to cover the scenario area, combined with the sensor that can provide the needed situational awareness. Tools to support the planning mission of the drones to establish the motions paths that optimises the sensors vs platforms vs data goals.

OP4.3-17: Obtain high ground resolution data.

Opportunity to explore multiple sensors fusion to generate the details of a specific location of the operational theatre. By fusion air, ground, IoT, smartphones, and other sensors tools, and metadata, enables the generation of an improved scenario awareness to support the decision-making process.

OP4.3-18: Airspace coordination with drones

Opportunity to harmonize the procedures to integrate drones in the emergency airspace. Managing the airspace in an increasing drone congestion scenario can be exploited following U-SPACE EASA rules.

OP4.3-19: RF space management.

Managing the RF space spectrum used by drones (UAV, UGV, USV, and other auto0nomous systems). A management tool for coordination of RF assets can be a valuable opportunity for the future harmonization of drones in such emergency scenarios.

OP4.3-20: Cross border data trace.

Establish and define a data registration models schema to record the agreements and political authorization, allowing to trace the data shared under which cross border agreement. This enables an assessment of the data sharing process as well as to automate the sharing process.

OP4.3-21: Victims advanced information.

The medical data / info collected thought the event, including the transportation health signals should be forwarded to the medical service. Only the information of the specific victim is shared, not of all the victims of the event.

OP4.3-22: Victims' historical data.

As victim is assigned to a specific medical service, under an emergency event, the medical service should be able to monitor the medical situation to best prepare the treatment at arrival of the victim. Not uncommon victims' health status changes from the moment it is triaged to the moment it arrived to the medical service. Historical medical data of the victim, when available, should be made available to the medical service.

OP4.3-23: Traceability of victims and FR.

Opportunity to explore the use of wearables and other portable sensors combined with communication capabilities, to enable the C2 and medical services to locate and trace the FR and victims. Each data to the specific needs. Victims and FR health signals can be collected and monitored in order to identify potential issues, as well as its locations. By tracking its location, allows the improvement of the assets and response management process.

OP4.3-24: External Data.

Opportunity to specify an API protocols and standard to enables external services to interface/share data with the SIGRUN and harmonize the data integration process for emergency events. External data are widely used as a source of information, from weather, terrain, satellite data, etc. which greatly improve situational awareness.

OP4.3-27: Use of decision-making applications.

The lack of collaborative and decision support tools can be easily overcome. There are some solutions on the market that, with a little education and training, can be implemented by emergency services, and that would drastically improve C2 operation.

6.3.4. Harmonization at national and supranational levels

C2 future for Emergency Services is rising curiosity in order to get social benefits. As Agile Warrior Quarterly mention: "a range of C2 approaches from fully autonomous decision-making

at speed to directive C2 that can better ensure C2 survivability, flexibility and efficiency in the context of mission accomplishment” ().

Equip forward command posts with advanced technologies and sensors to be able to analyse disruptive events. Capabilities such as generating early warning will prevent possible large-scale population damage ().

OP4.3-2: Multiplatform. Run different OS.

In computing, an application or software is considered to be multiplatform when it is able to operate on multiple computing platforms. Compatible types of computing architecture, operating system, programming language or user interface are established as platforms.

Cross-platform integration is based on the ability to provide supported architectures for different environments, eliminating dependencies and decoupling systems that exchange services or data.

- **Services:** Software as a Service (SaaS) is a model in which the provider hosts applications and makes them available to their customers through the Internet, regardless of whether you are using a Windows/Linux or Mac computer, or if you use a Smartphone, a tablet or a PC, the user having a similar experience regardless of the device they use. This model makes it possible to offer services at all levels and directed towards any of the actors, from RFs to people affected by disasters, being able to offer all kinds of useful services accessible from any personal device with Internet access. There are different types of cloud to host the service, being able to make services more public or more private depending on the scope it must have. It is interesting to note that there are Community Clouds, where different organizations can gather a pool of resources in the same cloud to solve common problems.
- **Middleware oriented to information exchange:** Message brokers are intermediary programs with an architectural pattern for message validation, transformation and routing. It is a mediator that allows minimizing the degree of mutual knowledge between the applications that use it to exchange messages, implementing a decoupling between them, and allowing the scaling of systems in a simpler and more powerful way. Today, there are messaging brokers capable of processing large volumes of data generated at high speed. Apache Kafka is a multi-tenant event streaming platform focused on Big Data projects and capable of processing large volumes of data in real time. There are many others, each with their advantages and disadvantages, such as Apache ActiveMq, RabbitMQ, Amazon MQ, Red HAT AMQ, RocketMQ, IBM WebSphere MQ, etc.
- **Software development:** API Restful is a programming interface that connects systems for information exchange through networks, following secure, reliable and efficient software communication standards. It is independent of the technology used, being able to write client applications in various programming languages without affecting the

design of the API, and it allows the underlying technology to be changed at any time on either side without affecting communication.

OP4.3-5: COP standardization.

The goal of a COP is to provide situational awareness at all levels of incident management and across all jurisdictions. To do this, a continuously updated general overview of the incident is achieved throughout its life cycle, through integrated communication, information management and intelligence and information exchange systems.

Multilateral Interoperability Program (MIP) is a Community of Interest that develops technical specifications (MIP solution) for the interoperability of Command and Control information systems. The core of the MIP solution is based on a fully documented C2 information exchange standard model, the JC3IEDM, produced by the MIP-NATO. Its general objective is to enable the interoperability of C2 information systems at all levels to support multinational operations.

Figure 15 – Architecture model for interoperability and interconnectivity for C2 Systems by NATO – (source: <https://www.systematicinc.com/products/a/command-and-control-information-systems/mip/>)

OP4.3-11: Open source C2 applications.

C2 purpose relies on protect as many societies as possible within accessible resources. An open-access C2 applications try to achieve a common framework of possibilities independently their economic status. Government institutions and educational organizations will be able to access these applications. The advantages will be that we will reach a larger number of the population and there will be an increase in the level of education. The information cycle in C2 environments is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16 - Information cycle in C2.

OP4.3-12: Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer

As weather prediction services use different standards and methodologies, this could be a critical gap in cross-border incidents effecting many parameters in decision making or logistics deployment. Recording such data, through available APIs, from ESA and/or NASA and/or ARATOS satellite systems, can resolve the gap through COP exchange between agents and countries by sharing the Hybrid Digital Twins recorded data.

OP4.3-13: Common Operational Picture exchange

As different agents within a country usually operate their own C2 systems, COP within a country using the VALKYRIES system and standards can be defined as al recording in the Hybrid Digital Twins of the VALKYRIES Core System. Then the COP exchange between countries (parametrized on permissions/restrictions as per bilateral agreements) can be easily performed.

OP4.3-30: OASIS EDXL HAVE Standard

The Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards has developed the Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) Hospital Availability Exchange Standard, the purpose of which is to facilitate information exchange regarding the capacities of hospitals e.g., bed counts and other resources. This information enhances the situational awareness of first responders and facilitates them in decision making during operations for multi casualty incidents. With this standard both the hospitals and the emergency manager can have a clear picture regarding the availability and capacity of hospitals and where the victims can be dispatched to. This standard could be used as an opportunity to address G4.3-23 “Development of a standardized electronic triage system for the facilitation and improvement of logistics management and the accomplishment of situational awareness” but there is significant room for further and more direct standardization activities towards this direction.

OP4.3-31 and OP4.3-32: CEN TR 15872:2014 and CEN TR 15299:2006

The European Committee for Standardization has developed two technical reports, CEN TR 15872:2014 “Health Informatics – Guidance on patient identification and cross-referencing of identities” and CEN TR 15299:2006 “Health informatics – Safety procedures for identification of patients and related objects”. Both these technical reports are related to patients’ and victims’ data and can be used as opportunities to address G4.3-25 “Standardization regarding the processing of victims’ personal data”. In addition to the above standards, the WHO guideline “The protection of personal data in health information systems – principles and processes for public health” could be another potential solution to this challenge.

The opportunities related to the command and control technologies are gathered in Table 23.

Opportunities			
Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.3-1	G4.3-1 G4.3-2 G4.3-28	VR debriefing systems	Backing to Virtual Reality systems for FRs may be implemented to C2. Items likely training performance or training outputs might be improved the results. <i>Technological</i>
OP4.3-2	G4.3-3	Multiplatform. Run different OS	Interlinking applications. Note is a basic characteristic to standardise. <i>Technological</i>
OP4.3-3	G4.3-11 G4.3-24	Location of near/nearest vehicles	Not enough traceability of vehicles location from other organizations. Which technology could fulfil this opportunity? <i>Technological</i>
OP4.3-4	G4.3-11 G4.3-13	Georeferenced recording of events on the ground	Know-how disaster events. Monitor the location of the events and display by C2 application. Chance to track events in terms of geo-referencing. <i>Technological</i>
OP4.3-5	G4.3-7 G4.3-8 G4.3-13 G4.3-14	COP standardization	Provide a global and real-time overview of the environmental situation and resources in the field.
OP4.3-6	G4.3-11 G4.3-35 G4.3-36	HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces	Opportunity to have a constantly metrics of your vehicle, device or system. <i>Cross-border and Technological</i>
OP4.3-7	G4.3-3 G4.3-4	Asset’s responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing	Deploying emergency items in VUCA environments (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity). <i>Cross-border, Technological and Procedural</i>

Opportunities			
Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
		environments, mission needs and scenarios	
OP4.3-8	G4.3-2	Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness	AI capable of performing tasks commonly associated with human intelligence.
OP4.3-9	G4.3-5 G4.3-32	Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	Predicting trends from previous exercises. Collecting and processing data to improve decision support.
OP4.3-10	G4.3-32 G4.3-40	Social Network data visualization C2	Recap data from social network such as pictures, videos or current states in order to increase decision-making and have a better understanding of the global situation. <i>Technological</i>
OP4.3-11	G4.3-28	Open Source C2 App	Providing technologies to the most vulnerable and under-resourced societies. <i>Technological</i>
OP4.3-12	G4.3-31	Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer	As weather prediction services use different standards and methodologies, this could be a critical gap in cross-border incidents effecting many parameters in decision making or logistics deployment. Recording such data, through available APIs, from ESA and/or NASA and/or ARATOS satellite systems, can resolve the gap through COP exchange between agents and countries by sharing the Hybrid Digital Twins recorded data.
OP4.3-13	G4.3-7 G4.3-4 G4.3-29 G4.3-26 G4.3-27	Common Operational Picture exchange	As different agents within a country usually operate their own C2 systems, COP within a country using the VALKYRIES system and standards can be defined as ai recording in the Hybrid Digital Twins of the VALKYRIES Core System. Then the COP exchange between countries (parametrized on permissions/restrictions as per bilateral agreements) can be easily performed.
OP4.3-14	G4.3-32	Guidelines for social media crawling	EU members could elaborate recommendations for implementing social media crawling strategies.

Opportunities			
Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.3-15	G4.3-32 G4.3-33 G4.3-40	Guidelines for selecting social media crawling tools	EU members could develop guidelines indicating the best tools and technologies used for social media data acquisition according to the type of platform consulted.
OP4.3-16	G4.3-19 G4.3-17	Drones' imagery data	Explore of multiple deployed drones in the field theatre to collect aerial view data (from EO/IR/ Lidar sensors) and increase the covered area, in particular for wide areas events.
OP4.3-17	G4.3-8 G4.3-15 G4.3-18 G4.3-19 G4.3-22	Obtain high ground resolution data	Combine multiple data to improve the coverage and details of the in-field situation: 1) Drones imagery high resolution sensors and its flight level; 2) ground data sensors, from IOT deployable sensors of external IOT services; 3) In field imagery from FR and victims Smartphones.
OP4.3-18	G4.3-20 G4.3-21 G4.3-22	Airspace coordination with drones	New capability is required to manage the increasing number of flying elements in cases of Emergency / Disaster event, this can be used by new solution or integration with external services.
OP4.3-19	G4.3-6 G4.3-10 G4.3-21 G4.3-38	RF space management	Add new capabilities to manage the RF spectrum as the number of communication infrastructures and radios is used with deployable sensors (Ground/ Air / Mobile /etc.).
OP4.3-20	G4.3-34	Cross border data trace	Data shared between countries could be traced by establishing a countries agreement reference, as a sharing authorization schema, for which the data is validated prior to be shared, and enables trace of the that data.
OP4.3-21	G4.3-35	Victims advance information	Only the data from victims assigned to a response medical facility is shared, from the moment it is assigned and including during transportation.
OP4.3-22	G4.3-36	Victims' historical data	The historical data collected during the event should be shared to the medical facility assigned to provide the medical service, including the information enabling its access to the victim EDR.
OP4.3-23	G4.3-37 G4.3-41 G4.3-42	Traceability of victims and FR	Use of wearables and other portable sensors combined with communication capabilities to enable the C2 and medical services to locate and trace the FR and victims. Each data to the specific needs.

Opportunities			
Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.3-24	G4.3-39 G4.3-12 G4.3-16	External data	Specify API protocols and standard to enables external services to interface/share data with the SIGRUN
OP4.3-25	G4.3-9 G4.3-43	Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones	EU members could elaborate regulations and guidelines to harmonise the procedures of identifying dangerous zones.
OP4.3-26	G4.3-44 G4.3-15	Identification of relevant locations	EU members could define recommended technologies for the identification of relevant locations in emergency scenarios.
OP4.3-27	G4.3-16 G4.3-45	Use of decision-making applications	Implementation of decision support applications in emergency services.
OP4.3-28	G4.3-46	Creation of operating procedures	Create operating procedures that collect the requirements of the standards used in equipment and devices.
OP4.3-29	G4.3-46 G4.3-47	Incorporation of new standards	Create procedures to adapt equipment, devices, and infrastructures to the appearance of new standards.
OP4.3-30	G4.3-23	EDXL HAVE Standard	Increase situational awareness in a short time frame in order to reduce response time.
OP4.3-31	G4.3-25	CEN TR 15872:2014	Both these standards might provide guidelines regarding the protection of the victims' personal data.
OP4.3-32	G4.3-25	CEN TR 15299:2006	

Table 23 - Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies.

6.4. The digitalization on first aid actuations

Consequently, to the previously identified gaps, the following opportunities could pose as solutions to ease the digitalization of the first aid actuations.

OP4.4-1: Digital Skills Improvement.

To improve the digital skills of the first responder with plans such as the 'European Skills Agenda' (46) of the European Commission that could be used to improve digital literacy.

OP4.4-2: Wearable's implementation.

As it is expected to track information using smart instrumentation and wearables, it poses as a great opportunity to include their information in the digital environment.

OP4.4-3: European Iconographic Standardization.

There is an opportunity to create an iconographic standard that accomplish with the desired requirements and avoid discrepancies.

OP4.4-4: European data standardization.

To define a common standard for communications would ease the information sharing during emergencies and the connection with digitalization instances.

OP4.4-5: Device's upgrade.

To assure that the devices involved during first aid actuations accomplish with the required computational and graphical requirements, they should be evaluated and upgraded.

OP4.4-13: Use of AI-based systems.

stressful situations.

OP4.4-14: Reduce voice communication.

As digitalization tools are developed and their use becomes easier, communication by non-digital means will be reduced. The digitized information objects, moreover, will not be corrupted when passing from one node to another, allowing all participants to have "first hand" information.

Much information can be obtained automatically without the need for manual recording by the emergency services involved in disasters. At present, for example, a lot of time is spent on precisely locating each of the disaster sites. A detailed study must be made of each one to assess the possibility of automatic recording without the need for human operation.

OP4.4-15: Reduce digital workload.

By facilitating the acquisition of information that needs to be obtained through human operation, emergency services would collect it more efficiently. For example, the use of voice recognition technologies can also help to collect this essential information without the need to operate with hands on the device. Machine learning technologies can help "fill in" for information that cannot be provided at peak times.

OP4.4-16: Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions.

Strong relationships with first responders are an R&D investment. Their knowledge and experience should be harnessed to highlight shared capability needs and guide R&D and S&T procurement decisions for disaster response.

First responders not only help to chart a technology roadmap based on their current and future needs, but also inform every step of the process, from initial design to operational testing of prototypes and preparing for the transition of technologies to the commercial market.

Taking first responders into consideration in the design of solutions for operational and C2 support in MCI and disasters is necessary to ensure that it provides them with the support they

need with adequate usability, facilitating their tasks and not hindering them, and with reliability in real working conditions.

OP4.4-17: Instant access with transparency to crucial information in a secure way

In many situations immediate data/ information retrieval can be major for someone's life. Immediate fetch of specific data in a simple and secure way can be done with the help of blockchain technology.

In an industry troubled by data breach, blockchain can help enhance data security while making it simpler while making it simpler to share records across systems and organizations. The participants retains the control over access of their own data, which increases trust and confidentiality.

Without blockchain technology each organization must maintain its own database. Transactions and data are recorder identically in a different locations because blockchain uses a distributed ledger. All network members with appropriate permissions can view the same information at the same time, ensuring complete transparency. Every transaction is immutably documented and datetime stamped. This allows members of the network to see the whole history of transaction, practically eliminating the possibility of fraud.

Blockchain generates an audit trails that documents an asset's origins at each stage of its travel trail. This helps for the verification of the members when participants worried about environmental or human rights concerns around a product or in industries troubled by counterfeiting and fraud. It is feasible to share data and information about provenance directly to the source through blockchain.

OP4.4-18: Best practice for introducing the e-tools/innovations.

It is obvious that the world of ICT is changing very fast and number of available e-tools is growing. It brings a lot of new features with potential to make the life of responders much easier. It brings also some difficulties and threats, or let say security issues. It requests also certain level of user's digital skills. Sometimes, it is not easy to orient in all the available e-tools and choose one, which fits to our needs the best. These are only some of the issues, which have to be overcome.

Best practice, respectively experience sharing represent very efficient mean, how to go through this. Especially if this information comes directly from a practitioner. This goes double in the world of responders. Recommendation from another end-user is exactly what is needed, it can confirm functionality, usability and reliability of the tool and in the language of this specific group of people.

All the opportunities are summarised in Table 24.

Opportunities			
The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.4-1	G4.4-10	Digital Skills Improvement	To improve the digital skills of the first responder.
OP4.4-2	G4.4-2	Wearable's implementation	As it is expected to track information using smart instrumentation and wearables, it poses as a great opportunity to include their information in the digital environment.
OP4.4-3	G4.4-1 G4.4-2 G4.3-9	European Iconographic Standardization	There is an opportunity to create an iconographic standard that accomplish with the desired requirements and avoid discrepancies.
OP4.4-4	G4.4-3 G4.4-4	European data standardization	To define a common standard for communications would ease the information sharing during emergencies and the connection with digitalization instances.
OP4.4-5	G4.4-5	Device's upgrade	To assure that the devices involved during first aid actuations accomplish with the required computational and graphical requirements, they should be evaluated and upgraded.
OP4.4-13	G4.4-13	Use of AI-based systems	It is possible to use AI-based systems for decision making or other considerations.
OP4.4-14	G4.4-11	Reduce voice communication	Digitization of first responders' actions will reduce reliance on voice communications.
OP4.4-15	G4.4-12	Reduce digital workload	Automating as many information flows as possible.
OP4.4-16	G4.4-8 G4.4-9	Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions	Taking first responders into consideration in the design of solutions for operational and C2 support in MCI and disasters is necessary to ensure that it provides them with the support they need with adequate usability, facilitating their tasks and not hindering them, and with reliability in real working conditions.
OP4.4-17	G4.4-17 G4.4-15	Instant access with transparency to Crucial information in a secure way	Immediate retrieval of specific crucial data in a simple and secure way via Blockchain Technology.
OP4.4-18	G4.4-10 , G4.4-11	Best practice for introducing the e-	To intermediate experience with use of e-tools from EU countries where it exists.

Opportunities			
The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
		tools where it is missing.	

Table 24 - Opportunities from the digitalisation on first aid actuations.

6.5. Instrumentation and health support wearable devices

OP4.5-1: Use of wearables for tracking.

It is possible to use certain wearables incorporating a range of technologies as a method of obtaining information about the stage of development of individual users, whether they are patients or FRs.

OP4.5-2: Use of wearables for tracking.

For this, RFID technology can be used, which allows the linking of a certain identifier to a piece of information. In this way, every time a user changes a zone, they can register that they are there by simply bringing the wearable close to them. In addition, this system does not need a power supply or coverage to work.

OP4.5-3: Use of wireless technologies in wearables.

Another opportunity that may arise is the use of wearables that incorporate GPS location, to know where each subject is. In this way, they can be associated with the nearest post. The main advantage of this is that the tracking is more accurate, and the user does not have to take any action. As disadvantages, it can be noted that it is necessary to have at least satellite coverage for this system to work, as well as a power supply for the wearables that can be degraded.

OP4.5-4: Use of RFID-based wearables for identification and OP4.5-5: NFC printing on traditional cards for identification.

On the other hand, there are several techniques that allow the localisation of users both indoors and outdoors through the use of wireless connection points, e.g., Wi-Fi. This system is based on the proximity to the APs that exist in each of the phases, however, the main disadvantage of this is the need for a large, meshed network for the correct tracking of users.

For the identification of participating users, RFID technology provides one of the best solutions. It is based on assigning an identifier to a certain RFID tag that is aligned with a user on the stage. In this way, the necessary medical information can be assigned to a specific tag. If there is no coverage, the traditional system can still be used.

OP4.5-6: Prototyping with own technologies and OP4.5-7: Firmware prototyping and OP4.5-8: Adaptive data delivery.

Since commercial solutions do not cover the needs required in this type of scenario, it is possible to create a prototype specifically designed for this task. In this way, it is possible to add modules with the technologies of interest, as well as the installation of its own firmware to cover the functionalities.

OP4.5-9: RFID to avoid batteries.

Active RFID tags are known to have a battery life of roughly three to five years, even some types of tags lasting up to 10 years.

OP4.5-10: Communicate by voice.

The ability to communicate vocally via wearables would allow you to use an instrument that is probably lighter than a radio and possibly usable hands-free.

OP4.5-11: Communicate by text.

Many wearables are equipped with a more or less large screen, the ability of the C2 to send text messages to the FRs, but also images or nav points, would allow information to be disseminated on a large scale asynchronously, i.e., without the need for a one-to-one communication via a radio channel.

OP4.5-35: D2D network gateway

Many wearables, local devices and IOT components use D2D communications, such as Bluetooth, RFID, etc, that do not provide network layer connection, which requires another device to connect it to the network. A gateway supporting multiple D2D protocols and providing plug&play connection to the network would facilitate and easy integrate the non-network enabled devices to the SIGRUN. Victims' vital signals monitoring and triage support.

OP4.5-21: Collect victim's vital signs.

There are a large number of possible victim's vital signs that can be explored and used, but it is not possible to collect them all, and only critical vitals should be collected. By using smart wearables, devices, and smartphones to collect in near real-time victim's vital signs, possibly including, but not limited:

- Heart rate
- Body Temperature
- Oxygen levels and saturation
- Abrupt movements
- Blood pressure

The above vitals are gathered and recorded for alter usage.

OP4.5-22: Monitor patient vital signs.

The vitals collected from the victims are of the most importance to the medical service. Therefore, these vitals are collected and send in real-time to the medical service to which the victim was transferred to. The medical service can monitor and generate a dashboard of the key information of the victims, raise alerts, and help planning the response.

OP4.5-25: Victim's vital signs on route.

The vitals collected from the victims can be continued collected not only at the triage / emergency local but also during the transportation to medical facilities.

While on route, the ambulances carrying the victim, is equipped with the means to, either directly collect the victim's vital signs or to recover that data from the victim's sensors artifacts (wearables, smart devices, etc), and send them to the medical service of destination.

In addition to the victims' vital signs, the ambulance location, route and ETA at the medical facility is of key importance to better prepare the medical teams and manage the hospital logistics.

OP4.5-31: Use of wearables on critically ill patients.

The sensitivity and accuracy of wearables, as mentioned above, needs to be studied in depth. As technology advances, new wearable models incorporate artificial intelligence and cloud computing techniques, which can help mitigate the measurement gap in critically ill patients.

OP4.5-23: Pseudonymisation.

For purpose of privacy protection, the identification data of the victims and the victims' vital signs could be masked with alias. Only the identification service would be able to cross this information by authorization of the victims. Therefore, the collection of the data from the triage until the medical service can be anonymized.

OP4.5-24: Patient vital signs management and interoperability for healthcare.

Victims' historical data is a valuable information resource to support correct and a more complete diagnostic and informed decision-making process by the medical services. Victims' medical history is of private nature and, usually, spread over different entities, from private to NHS services. By establishing an interoperability solution to collect the historical data as well as the current vital signs, and by sharing these data with the assigned emergency medical service enables a more adjusted medical treatment, a more complete informed decision-making, and a better medical resource and logistics management process.

OP4.5-32: Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations.

There are a large number of healthcare-related consumer wearables on the market, often designed to collect general wellness data (heart rate, sleep quality, etc.), but their application in MCI remains still very limited due to factors such as inaccurate calibration, lack of a suitable data format for medical exploitation, transmission problems, etc., which lead to a lack of confidence in clinical decision making.

The adaptation of these consumer wearables to regulatory and medical requirements would allow manufacturers to access a huge new market and would guarantee FRs the quality of data to improve monitoring and triage procedures during an ICM.

OP4.5-33: Use of wearables to support triage.

The use of wearables to support triage could speed up the process, allowing skilled personnel to focus on the most serious victims without neglecting other victims who would continue to be monitored and reported to the system with the support of less qualified personnel. Automation and artificial intelligence could perform data processing to obtain triage status and support victim prioritisation.

OP4.5-26: Victim ID.

Use of pre-tagged RF, QR code, and marked colour devices to triage the victim. The registration of the victim with personal data can be done by FR by exploring such technologies in a more automated process. The patient is assigned with a unique identifier which is used to track all the data in the system, thus enabling improved privacy as the data collected is not directly linked to a name or photo but to a generated ID., Only the medical and authorized personnel may be able to cross the victim ID with the private data, on a need-to-know basis.

6.5.1. FR protection during crisis response

OP4.5-12: Warning of a danger for FRs.

Moving around a worksite to carry out rescue operations can become a dangerous activity.

Following the assessment phase, operational zones, NO-GO zones and 'safe' passageways are defined, however the situation can be highly evolving (think for example of after-shocks in the event of an earthquake, the release of hazardous substances, fire and smoke, structural collapses). The ability of FRs to signal a personal danger situation via a function of their wearables without the need to depend on the radio channel is extremely interesting.

In addition, these devices may be able to detect the position and activity level of the FRs, promptly signalling to C2 certain changes as critical (man down or prolonged inactivity).

OP4.5-13: Automatic transmission of vital signs of FRs.

There is a plethora of wearable devices (smartwatches, embedded sensors in wearable tech, etc.) on the market that could be used to monitor when a first responder is suffering from physical overexertion or even stress during its work.

Protecting and monitoring the safety of first responders will put them in a better position to focus on the incident and have confidence in their own safety.

OP4.5-14: Integration of sensors for hazardous substances.

Rescue operations during an MCI can be complicated by the presence of hazardous substances. Regardless of the presence of visible fumes, there are situations where it is possible that FRs we

are not immediately aware of a hazard. Low concentrations of Oxygen, presence of Carbon Monoxide, methane, propane gas just to name the most frequent situations up to and including, for example, radioactive sources.

The possibility of integrating sensors within wearables that can autonomously detect the presence of these substances would certainly increase the level of safety for operators.

Finally, it might be interesting to be able to acquire the location and type of a hazard via wearables and transmit this information to C2.

OP4.5-15: Broadcasting of safety and security information.

From what has been said so far, it is clear how important it is to be able to alert responders engaged in MCI in a timely manner to the presence of sudden hazards and threats to their safety (e.g., evacuation order in case of after-shocks during earthquakes or the presence of threats to physical safety). In addition, it would also be desirable to have a broadcast system to transmit operational messages (locating a target, perhaps providing navigation via NAV points, or exchanging information between distant teams), reporting a NO-GO area or presence of hazardous substances.

Several of these functions could be performed in the form of audible alarms, audio messages, or short texts using wearables

OP4.5-16: Create common procedures for disaster fatality identification between different countries.

Obviously, the primary drive that drives all rescuers to get involved is to be able to save a human life. However, those who intervene in an MCI know full well that they may have to confront the failure of this aspiration; they will have to deal with the death of human beings.

This aspect, however, although left as the last phase of rescue operations, for reasons of human mercy cannot and should not be overlooked. The recovery of bodies must be carried out with all possible care the deceased person and respect for local customs.

The critical issue in these cases is often related to victim identification, as the time lapse between death and discovery or the traumatic nature of the event can complicate the work of forensic examiners. the deceased victim identification (DVI) procedure require the acquisition of as many elements as possible to arrive at a secure attribution of the victim's identity

Often then there is no real synergy between those who do the search and recovery and those who have to do the identification as a forensic act.

In this case, it would be desirable to be able to harmonize missing person report forms with deceased victim recovery reports so as to focus attention on all those aspects that can lead to safe identification as quickly as possible. Identifying data that can be retrieved from wearables should be included within these information collection forms.

OP4.5-17: Freezing the scene of a deceased victim discovery.

In relation to the above, the acquisition through wearables of the images and the exact location of finding of the deceased victims should be proceeded.

This information should be able to be transmitted to C2 and securely stored there.

This would allow two important advantages: first, it would facilitate the rapid presumptive identification of the victim through recognition by relatives and acquaintances, thus enabling a name to be crossed off the list of missing persons. Second, if this were not possible, it could provide important guidance to the work of forensic scientists.

OP4.5-18: Acquire unique IDs of implanted wearables.

The use of implanted devices is certainly not new in medicine. Pacemakers began to be implanted around the 1950s, and in more recent times automated internal defibrillators, the Left Ventricular Support Devices, have been added. If we then leave the field of cardiology we find implanted sensors for blood glucose control, micro infusers for insulin and neuronal electro-stimulators to finally arrive at the implanted chips.

These chips are powered by an electromagnetic circuit, which feeds on the communication platforms found in smartphones, they don't need a battery or wires, which means they require only minimally invasive injection and removal procedures. They are hard to break, and provide, as tests have shown, more reliable data.

The latter technology is still in the development phase; however, it could lead to the detection of numerous parameters such as temperature, pH, blood pressure, blood glucose, blood oxygen, etcetera.

If it were possible to capture the IDs of these implanted devices and correlate them with the personal health records of MCI victims in a reliable manner, this would allow for rapid and unambiguous identification, at present, however, this possibility seems very remote.

OP4.5-19: Record victim's data in blockchain

Modern technologies are beneficial. Oftentimes, when organizations consider investing in new technologies then usually focus too much on the price and underestimate the benefits of the solutions. You need to think long term when it comes to modern technologies and what benefits they can offer you in the long time. Not every expense is a cost. For the best results sometimes have to invest and take the risk first in order to gain something later on. In the future you may find out that the benefits exceed the costs multiple times.

Tap2sos for example, a product solution developed by blockchain2050, a reliable and low-cost NFC modern wrist band that can be crucial for our lives. A medical ID bracelet for secure retrieval of medical data through healthcare blockchain technology. Tap2Sos contains information about your health, so that the first to respond in case of emergency can offer you the right help with the help of real time medical data retrieval from the blockchain in a simple and secure way. It

can be used by hospitals, social services, healthcare professionals, medical doctors, pharmacists and other organizations are given the option to write on a wristband for their patients, members or clients.

OP4.5-20: Use of first responder's telecom devices to record victim's data as per its wearable unique id.

Continuing with OP4.5-20, Tap2sos bracelet allows immediate recording, registration and identification of the person wearing it and of any chronic health problems he or she may have while blockchain technology safeguards all his/hers personal and sensitive data transparency and integrity and with full compliance with GDPR.

OP4.5-34: Technology update business services model.

Technology, application solution and digital infrastructures have nowadays a high innovation pace. New function and capabilities are available and more added each day. Some of the technologies also completely transform the landscape of the User's operational models and performance. At the same time their acquisition costs and maintenance costs also increase, with the risk of compatibility and loss of performance as the systems become obsolete and legacy. To maintain the technology edge available for FR, new business model based on technology update services or turn-key full services can be exploited, thus enabling that legacy systems are update faster and reducing the technological gap between EU FR forces.

6.5.2. Telemedicine

OP4.5-27: Telemedicine Service.

A telemedicine service can be set-up to provide assistance to responders aiding a victim. or to enable nonprofessional personnel, in the absence of alternatives, to perform assistance to victims.

OP4.5-28: Telemedicine Guidance.

The Telemedicine service can make use of the mobile phones cameras and audio to guide FR in the proceeding, and to help no professional and FR assistance personnel in performing basic lifesaving procedures and to guide the victim's health status assessment. The service could be provided via voice.

OP4.5-29: Telemedicine Data Collection.

The telemedicine service can receive imagery from the victims to be used by remote experts to confirm/help achieve a diagnostic, and to support the above opportunity to guide non experts responders.

OP4.5-30 European Health Data Space.

The EU Proposal aiming to expand the reuse of electronic health data will boost research and innovation in health care related sectors. The instrumentation and health support wearable devices may contribute to the purposes and actions envisaged under the EU Health Data Space

strategy included in the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Space Act published on May 3rd 2022¹. The proposal aims at promoting the secondary use of health-related data when the following conditions are met i) a robust legal basis for processing in line with EU data protection law is verified, ii) a strong data governance mechanism and effective safeguards for the rights and interests of natural persons that are fully compliant with the GDPR are established. Therefore, such an opportunity is addressed when data are processed in a lawful, responsible, ethical management anchored in EU values manner by each instrument and support.

OP4.5-31: Use of wearables on critically ill patients.

The use of wearables is a technological challenge. It is necessary to advance in alternative technologies that allow their use in patients with severe lesions. On the other hand, the sensitivity and accuracy of existing solutions should be explored for cases in which patients have lesions that prevent placement or make it difficult for sensors to read them.

All these opportunities are presented in a brief way in Table 25.

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.5-1	G4.5-1	Use of wearables for tracking	It is possible to employ wearables that incorporate technologies such as RFID or NFC to track the stage of the incident each user is in.
OP4.5-2	G4.2-1 G4.5-2	Use of wearables for tracking	Use of wearables incorporating GPS technology to track the location of each user in an emergency scenario.
OP4.5-3	G4.5-2	Use of wireless technologies in wearables	It is possible to use wearables that incorporate GPS technology for real-time location of the users' position and thus associate them to a certain position/phase.

¹ EU Proposal for a Regulation on European Health Data Space, COM(2022) 197 final 2022/0140(COD)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52022PC0197&from=EN>

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.5-4	G4.5-1	Use of RFID-based wearables for identification	Through the use of RFID devices, it is possible to assign a unique identifier that allows users to be uniquely identified within an emergency scenario.
OP4.5-5	G4.5-3	NFC printing on traditional cards for identification	It is possible to print NFC tags on top of traditional cards to avoid a collapse due to lack of coverage.
OP4.5-6	G4.5-4	Prototyping with own technologies	It is possible to create a prototype of wearable devices that incorporates those modules to enable the necessary technologies to meet the needs raised.
OP4.5-7	G4.5-5	Firmware prototyping	It is possible to design firmware that incorporates a prototype to meet the needs that are required in such scenarios.
OP4.5-8	G4.5-6	Adaptive data delivery	To save battery power, data sending can be adapted depending on the patient's situation, sending data more continuously or in a reduced form.
OP4.5-9	G4.5-6	RFID to avoid batteries	RFID-based devices avoid the use of batteries in these devices and therefore the limitation of the lifetime.
OP4.5-10	G4.5-11 G4.5-13	Communicate by voice	It would be possible to implement the functionality of wearables that do not have them with a microphone and a speaker to allow local communication between FRs.
OP4.5-11	G4.5-17	Communication by text	Wearables that have screens could transmit and receive text messages to and from C2.

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.5-12	G4.5-11	Warning of a danger for FRs	<p>There are integrations in some wearables that allow you to report a personal physical threat via an easy action (panic button) or detection of lying position and lack of movement. This information is correlated by the GPS coordinates of the RF and also the opening of an ambient microphone. The use of these solutions should be more widespread.</p> <p>In addition to this it could be interesting to be able to report via the wearable the localization of different dangers (fire, smoke, collapse) that identify NO-GO zones to report them to FRs approaching that zone.</p>
OP4.5-13	G4.5-1 G4.5-8 G4.5-25 G4.5-26 G4.5-28	Automatic transmission of vital signs of FRs	<p>It would be possible to transmit to C2 automatically (continuously, at defined intervals, on request) vital signals of the FRs detected by the wearables. For example, heart rate, oxygen saturation, but also lack of movement could be detected. This would allow to monitor the physical and mental condition of FRs</p>
OP4.5-14	G4.5-14 G4.5-12	Integration of sensors for hazardous substances	<p>The possibility of integrating sensors for various hazardous substances within wearables (e.g., helmets) would allow continuous monitoring of dangers.</p> <p>The possibility of transmitting this information, correlated for</p>

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			example by the GPS coordinates, to C2 would make it immediately available to all FRs in the area, triggering an alarm when they approach danger.
OP4.5-15	G4.5-13	Broadcasting of safety and security information	Ability to transmit information on the safety and security of FRs through wearables. Preceded by a pre-established warning signal, they can be short text or audio messages or, in the case of devices with larger screens, contain images relating to the location of the danger.
OP4.5-16	G4.5-15	Create common procedures for disaster fatality identification between different countries	Sharing certain information about deceased victims obtained through wearables can provide a common basis for the harmonization of DVI procedures among different countries. The more accurate and verified the identification, the easier it will be to agree on a shared regulation. This solution may be difficult to implement due to political problems.
OP4.5-17	G4.5-14	Freezing the scene of a deceased victim discovery	The ability to capture via a wearable device (body cam, smart glasses) images and the exact location of a scene before recovering a deceased victim would provide authorities responsible for identifying the victim with valuable information.

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			This data could be securely transmitted and stored.
OP4.5-18	G4.5-18	Acquire unique IDs of implanted wearables	The ability to “read” an implantable wearable and correlate its ID with a person’s medical record would allow a person to be identified with certainty and quickly.
OP4.5-19	G4.5-14 G4.5-24	Record victim’s data in blockchain	The ability to log data in blockchain will be provided by the VALKYRIES’ system for all crucial transactions and metadata. This can also cover the recording of all medical data gathered in different stages of triage or handling of the victim between different agents, up to the entry of the victim to the final hospital to take care.
OP4.5-20	G4.5-10 G4.5-20	Use of first responder’s telecom devices to record victim’s data as per its wearable unique id	In case we use the combination of NFT wearables and blockchain, then the communication to the appropriate C2 or supporting federated software can be performed using the communication capabilities of the smart phone/tablet of the first responder initiating/updating or retrieving information on a trusted “need to know” basis.
OP4.5-21	G4.5-25 G4.5-26	Collect victim’s vital signs	Use of smart wearables, devices, and smartphones to collect in near real-time victim’s vital signs, possibly including, but not limited to:

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Heart rate ○ Body Temperature ○ Oxygen levels and saturation ○ Abrupt movements ○ Blood pressure
OP4.5-22	G4.5-26	Monitor patient vital signs	The vital signs collected can be transmitted to the medical centre that records the vital signals history and generated a victim's dashboard, monitoring the key values of the patient signals and raise alerts.
OP4.5-23	G4.5-22	Pseudonymisation	For purpose of privacy protection, the identification data of the victims and the victims' vital signs could be masked with alias. Only the identification service would be able to cross this information by authorization of the victims.
OP4.5-24	G4.5-20	Patient vital signs management and interoperability for healthcare	The victim current and historic vital signs data can be shared with the assigned medical service for processing and management purposes
OP4.5-25	G4.5-17 G4.5-22	Victim's vital signs on route	While on route, the ambulances carrying the victims are equipped with the means to, either directly collect the victim's vital signs or to recover that data from the victim's sensors artifacts (wearables, smart devices, etc), and send them to the medical service of destination.
OP4.5-26	G4.5-18	Victim ID	Use of pre-tagged RF, WR code, and marked colour to mark a victim. Registration of the

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			victim with personal data can be done by FR. Victim's signals are mask with the TAG, not with the victim's name or ID.
OP4.5-27	G4.5-23	Telemedicine service	A telemedicine service can be set-up to provide assistance to responders aiding a victim.
OP4.5-28	G4.5-23	Telemedicine guidance	Telemedicine can provide audio assistance to responders to 1) guide them in applying lifesaving procedures and, 2) help performing assessment of the victim's health condition and basic diagnostics.
OP4.5-29	G4.5-23	Telemedicine data collection	The telemedicine service can receive imagery from the victims and use of remote experts to confirm/help achieve a diagnostic.
OP4.5-30	G4.5-22	European Health Data Space	EU Proposal to expand the use of electronic health data to deliver health care to the individual from whom those data were collected ("primary use") and to improve research, innovation, policy making, patient safety, personalised medicine, official statistics or regulatory activities ("secondary use").
OP4.5-31	G4.5-16 G4.5-25	Use of wearables on critically ill patients	The use of wearables in critically ill patients should be analysed in more detail.
OP4.5-32	G4.5-26 G4.5-27	Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations	Implementing medical regulations in wearables, these devices would be more useful for first responders and open a

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			new market to the manufacturers.
OP4.5-33	G4.5-16 G4.5-7	Use of wearables to support triage	Automation and artificial intelligence could perform data processing from wearables used in triage process to obtain triage status and support victim prioritisation.
OP4.5-34	G4.5-19	Technology update business services model	To maintain the technology edge available for FR, new business model based on technology update services or turn-key full services can be exploited, thus enabling that legacy systems are update faster and reducing the technological gap between EU FR forces.
OP4.5-35	G4.5-21	D2D network gateway	A gateway supporting multiple D2D protocols and providing plug&play connection to the network, would facilitate and make it easier to integrate the non-network enabled devices into the SIGRUN.

Table 25 - Opportunities from Instrumentation and health support wearable devices.

7. Conclusions

7.1. General conclusions of WP4 gaps and opportunities

To sum up this version of deliverable D4.6, a total of 142 gaps and 132 opportunities related to WP4 have been identified. The following table shows the number of gaps classified by source and by WP4 task in which they are included.

	Gaps	Opportunities
T4.1: FIRST AID VEHICLES AND SUPPORTIVE AUTONOMOUS UNITS	8	8
T4.2: TRUSTED COMMUNICATION INFRASTRUCTURE AND END-USER TERMINALS	43	42
T4.3: MOBILE COMMAND AND CONTROL AND OPERATIONAL COORDINATION TECHNOLOGIES	47	32
T4.4: THE DIGITALIZATION ON FIRST AID ACTUATIONS	15	18
T4.5: INSTRUMENTATION AND HEALTH SUPPORT WEARABLE DEVICES	28	35
Total	141	135

Table 26 - Summarize of gaps and opportunities found for D4.6.

7.2. Conclusions of T4.1: First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units

The use of different unmanned vehicles are very suitable to assist first responders in the field especially UAV (Drones) and UGVs (Rovers) can make an impact.

Drones can contribute in the building of situation awareness, reduce risk and conduct search and relief missions. The exists already systems available.

There are some challenges when regarding the procurement of such systems for first responder organisations.

Firstly, is the trade-off between complexity in the system (the ability to provide several services) and the easiness of use. Especially volunteers have limited time to train and to learn new skills. They usually choose the usability before the possibilities. They need as system easy to use, logical in the system and do what the first responder need assistance in.

Another challenge is price. First responder organisations have limited budgets and thinks smartly when they acquire new gadgets. A common system for connecting sensors, transferring data and ability to read it regardless of technological solution (PC, cell phone, tablet etc). This

standardisation will reduce the need to by several UV systems but can use one UAV and just add on sensor when needed.

7.3. Conclusions of T4.2: Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals

The use of secure and reliable communications is nowadays essential. In the context of emergency situations, it is even more necessary since the response time and the security of the communications that are being carried out in these situations is paramount. This can be seen in the large number of gaps and opportunities that have been defined in this task, with a total of 43 gaps and 42 opportunities to fill these gaps.

Any possible security failure or communications failure could trigger a failure in the performance of first responders or in the management of incidents that are appearing at any given moment.

For these reasons, the document has carried out an analysis of the main problems that this type of situation has at the communications level and several solutions have been proposed to create a system capable of providing security and reliability at this time.

The main gap found in this task is the lack of a communications architecture that can group different types of devices that generate information by different means. This is a big problem since each country works differently and uses or does not use certain devices through a different network (Wi-fi, Bluetooth, TETRA, etc).

For all the above reasons, different opportunities have been defined to unify all the types of communications used by the different countries and to provide security and reliability in the network.

7.4. Conclusions of T4.3: Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies

The deliverable has been structured in a taxonomy divided into three stages. Based on literature, studies and surveys of first responders, the consortium has identified which capabilities are required based on their needs. The improvement of the identified capacities will serve to:

- Improve the reach of resources in a multi-casualty incident
- Integrated C2 systems would increase the deployment of devices in the field
- Harmonization of the roadmaps for first responders

The second point was the identification and subsequent gap analysis. Overall, interoperability between systems is very weak. Data sharing between agencies is practically non-existent and makes it difficult to improve a universal framework for logistical and material support of the resources to be deployed. The implementation of cutting-edge devices and technologies would provide better capabilities in order to increase data rescue statistics. Finally, the third phase has been the identification of opportunities. In other words, explaining which solutions and products can fill the technological gaps for C2 applications. The consequent analysis of the gaps detection has been that many of the current applications are obsolete. The C2 developments does not fit

according to the real needs. Thus, multi-layers such as sensor data collection, devices like smartphones or drones aims to expand the user's understanding of the disaster situation. Note that is strongly necessary to cover real-time coordination of the injured. Finally, there is no doubt that with an improvement in current operations, user training will become much more didactic in a few years. The data storage from other disasters will become to create training tool based on real scenarios.

7.5. Conclusions of T4.4: The digitalization on first aid actuations

Although this task is focused on the technological aspects, many identified gaps are not strictly related to the technological aspects of the digitalization, and they are related with the procedural aspects instead.

On the one hand, the focus of the technological gaps does not relapse on the digitalization and is more related to the implementation of other technological requirements, such as the use of wearables, the communication between devices or the continuous communication coverage. On the other hand, the procedural aspects pose as a risk to the digitalization as it should be faced from a human-centric perspective.

The identifies gaps and opportunities confirm that the digitalization is a relevant procedure that implies many dimensions, including technological and non-technological, highlighting the relations of the digitalization and other aspects of the emergency actuations.

7.6. Conclusions of T4.5: Instrumentation and health support wearable devices

The use of different devices to provide our first responders with greater capabilities, as well as to facilitate and speed up their actions, is currently underutilized. The use of these devices to obtain information from the environment, from patients or from any other place will enable us to act more effectively in these emergency situations.

The main opportunities obtained in this task are all related to the use of devices for patient care, observing their vital signs, monitoring them, or helping first responders with triage, among others. These opportunities will facilitate the tasks of the first responders and thus their actions will be faster. On the other hand, there is a problem associated with the use of these devices and it is the high cost of these devices since they are equipped with very modern technologies.

If we look at the summary table of gaps and opportunities, we can see that this is the only task that has more opportunities than gaps. This is because there are many solutions that can fill these gaps currently but are not used due to their cost, the big change that had to be made in organizations both learning and communications and software etc... VALKYRIES will oversee demonstrating its potential in emergency situations and will be able to take this type of devices to a pre-standardization.

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9. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AED	Automated External Defibrillator
AGL	Above Ground Level
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
API	Application Programming Interfaces
C&C	Command and Control
C2	Command and Control
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
COP	Common Operational Picture
COW	Cell on Wheels
CPR	Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation
DMO	Direct Mode Operation
DVI	Disaster Victim Identification
EFFIS	European Forest Fire Information System
EIDO	Emergency Incident Data Object
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EMS	Emergency Management Service
EMTEL	Emergency Telecommunications
ERM	Radio Spectrum Matters
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FIRMS	Fire Information for Resource Management System
FPV	First Person View
FR	First Responder
GDPR	General Framework of the Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GTRF	Galileo Terrestrial Reference Frame
HAZMAT	Hazardous Material
ICP	Incident Command Post
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
MCI	Multi Casualty Incident

Acronym	Description
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
ML	Machine Learning
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NFC	Near Field Communication
OASIS	Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OODA	Observe, Orient, Decide, Act
QoS	Quality of Service
RF	Radio Frequency
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RPAS	Remote Piloted Aircraft System
SA	Situational Awareness
SAR	Synthetic-aperture radar
SDN	Software Defined Networking
SMS	Send Text Messages
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TTE	Through-the-Earth
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
USV	Unmanned Surface Vehicles
VR	Virtual Reality
WHO	World Health Organization
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity

Table 27 - Glossary